

**The Impact of Entrepreneurial Training in Sub-Saharan
Africa:**

*An exploration of entrepreneurial intentions within Ghanaian and Kenyan
SMEs*

Thesis submitted by

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DECLARATION

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Date: 14th December 2023

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**In loving memory of
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ABSTRACT

The collapse of most SMEs still continues to raise alarming concerns for educators, legislators and government officials. They often ask whether entrepreneurial-trained business owners have what it takes to ensure business sustainability in most developing countries. This study area gives a vivid understanding of how entrepreneurial training influences SMEs' intentions in Sub-Saharan African countries.

This thesis consists of an exploratory qualitative design conducted in two African countries, Ghana and Kenya. The research design adopted an inductive approach where themes were generated from the participant responses to describe the phenomena implemented compromises of a sample size of twenty-two (22) SMEs (owners/managers) from diverse businesses (manufacturing, service and tourism industry). The rationale for selecting each participant for the study included an individual with an established and operational business with at least three years standing. This is because most businesses fail between 3 to 5 years, and this methodological approach intends to gain detailed answers on SMEs' attitudes, behaviours, and intentions. The findings attest that start-up motivations are subjective, emphasising personal truth, intrinsic values and beliefs of the individual.

Furthermore, negative experiences trigger start-up motivation, including lack of recognition, promotion, acknowledgement, recognition and benefit. Individuals with previous business and trade experience are likelier to start a business than those without personal experience. Entrepreneurial education from the university is essential for individuals to become entrepreneurs because they provide the necessary skills to prevent mistakes and errors in the early stages of the business.

This thesis advances from the theory of planned behaviour and the entrepreneurial event model. A new framework called the "Triadic" influence of entrepreneurial intention was developed to analyse entrepreneurs' intentions. Practically, this thesis identifies limitations in current government policies and their communication regarding SME support. Recommendations are made for improving policy effectiveness and defining clear guidelines to address these issues.

From a theoretical perspective, this thesis provides and contributes to the development of the intention of SMEs through entrepreneurial training. Contextual, conceptual and legacy models were developed to prescribe practices and drive relevant SMEs' entrepreneurial intention and job creation. This also contributes to entrepreneurial stability and resourcefulness literature by describing how small businesses and entrepreneurs anticipate and respond to measures to ensure business success. This thesis recommended how entrepreneurial training should be moderated and the vital measures most governments in Sub-Saharan Africa should adopt. A notable result of this thesis is developing a novel model that prescribes practices and informs SME policies. The model encompasses start-up triggers, start-up motivation (pull and push factors), the outcomes of entrepreneurial training, and a process model of entrepreneurial intention.

This thesis highlights the role of entrepreneurial training in fostering SME development and sustainability in Sub-Saharan Africa. It underscores the need for effective policies, improved communication, and the continuous adaptation of training programs to meet the dynamic needs of SMEs. This research promotes entrepreneurship, job creation, and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa by bridging the gap between theory and practice.

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***Unique contribution to knowledge**

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***Unique contribution to knowledge**

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADB	African Development Bank
ATB	Attitude Towards Behaviour
ATP	Apprenticeship Training Programmes
BI	Behavioural Intention
COVID 19	Coronavirus Disease of 2019
EC	Entrepreneurial Capacity
EE	Entrepreneurial Education
EET	Entrepreneurship Education and Training
EME	Entrepreneurial Event Model
ET	Entrepreneurial Training
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIPC	Ghana Investment and Promotion Centre
IMF	International Monetary Fund
NBSSI	National Board for Small Scale Industry
NEIP	The National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programme
PBC	Perceived Behavioural Control
PE	Personal Experience
QAA	The Quality Assurance Agency
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SE	Self- Efficacy
SI	Subjective Influencer
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SN	Subjective Norm
TPB	The Theory of Planned Behaviour
UN	United Nations
YALI	Young African Leader Initiative
YIEDIE	Youth Inclusive Entrepreneurial Development initiative for Employment

Chapter 1: INTRODUCTION

A tremendous amount of research has been conducted to address the importance of entrepreneurial training among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) (Henry et al., 2005; Santoso, 2017; Adenle, 2017; Truman, 2021; Yitbarek et al, 2021). Santoso (2017) perceived SMEs as the engine of growth of every economy. Research findings from Truman (2021) also suggested that entrepreneurial training is the pivot for SMEs to overcome the challenges associated with the COVID 19 pandemic. Over the years, governments of different African countries have focused critically on entrepreneurial training opportunities as a potential means to widen the scope of SMEs within the entrepreneurship ecosystem (Boukamcha, 2015; Adenle, 2017; Obi-Berko, 2020). Research findings related to entrepreneurship training and SMEs activities have focused on key thematic areas to address efficiency issues, spot market opportunities, and promote managerial skills among entrepreneurs within the ecosystem (Sheriff and Muffatto, 2015; Asongu & Odhiambo, 2019; Obi-Berko, 2020; Porffrio et al., 2022).

Unquestionably, the current trending global economic crises demand a review of entrepreneurship activities. The repercussions of the COVID-19 pandemic have led to a substantial increase in global debt levels, impacting businesses across the globe (Truman, 2021). According to recent reports in 2020, the overall global debt reached around 263 percent of GDP, marking its highest level in the last 50 years (Dube & Naidoo, 2020; Truman, 2021).

In most African countries, this pandemic affected SMEs and upcoming entrepreneurs in pivotal ventures such as agriculture, tourism, supply chain, sports, aviation, production, and many more (Sane, 2020). It is essential to understand entrepreneurial activities among SMEs in the context of Africa considerably, undertake measures to change the business

environment, and outline key factors that affect their business operation to ensure sustainability in their venture (Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). Eid, Badewi, and Selim (2019) argued that developing countries could create an avenue that will enable entrepreneurs to nurture innovation and create new business ventures to facilitate economic growth.

However, many researchers acknowledged SMEs' impacts and their curial role in Africa despite increased entrepreneurial training (Jurie & Botha, 2010; Sheriff, 2015; Adenle, 2017; Amoah & Amoah, 2018; Sane, 2020). The critical issues associated with SMEs' failure cannot be written off in the past decade (Kiggundu, 2002; Dube & Naidoo 2020; Porfírio et al., 2022). The point of undertaking entrepreneurial training or completing entrepreneurship training and not yielding the correct result can be a significant concern for most SMEs. This entrepreneurial training can be in the form of short or long-term training programmes (Lorz, 2015). Nevertheless, many entrepreneurial training projects do not address SMEs ' vital needs (Adenle, 2017; Agyemang, & Ankomah-Asare 2020). Sheriff (2005) argued that there is often a significant gap between the perceptions of the training delivered and those of the SME's training needs. SMEs' activities in Sub-Saharan African countries can be seen in several diverse forms and can be found in cities and rural communities across the region. Although positive indicators suggest that SMEs contribute significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by creating employment opportunities, improving living standards, and many more, they face several challenges (Chinomona et al., 2020). For businesses to thrive, they depend intensively on entrepreneurial access to training programmes and business development services (Jurie and Botha, 2010). Owusu (2014) argued that more entrepreneurship opportunities that have not been identified could be seen more in developing nations than in developed nations.

Therefore, most Sub-Saharan African countries need entrepreneurship training and business incubators to capitalise on these opportunities. Notwithstanding these numerous

opportunities existing in the Sub-Saharan African region, many SMEs are coupled with many challenges that always hamper their growth. These have triggered many Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), international organisations, and private institutions to collaborate with Government institutions. The purpose is to instigate diverse entrepreneurship training programmes to address the reasons SMEs collapse at their early stage (Mathibe & Vanzyl, 2011; Trends, 2019; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). It is critical to distinguish between the intention to start a new business and the intention to sustain and grow an existing one. Throughout this thesis, the focus underpins understanding and analysing the intentions of SMEs related to continuing and developing their current operations.

This chapter seeks to establish the research problem, justify the rationale, state the aim, and explain the research objectives. Furthermore, attention is given to the study's implication and an overview of entrepreneurial training, education involved in this investigation, and the administrators involved in the key triggers of intentions of SMEs.

1.1 Background of the study

The term entrepreneurship is nothing new, and in the past decades, several kinds of research have been conducted in this area (Dugassa, 2012; Owusu, 2014; Dzisi & Odoom, 2017; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). Many developing countries across the globe perceive entrepreneurship as a core determinant of economic prosperity, impactful innovation, and increased social mobility for individuals and groups (Santoso, 2017; Jones, 2018; Chinomona, 2020; Aljuwaiber, 2021). This study area gives a vivid understanding of how entrepreneurial training influences SMEs' intentions in Sub-Saharan African countries.

The study area highlights motivation traits that will influence the intents of entrepreneurs in Sub-Saharan African countries. Entrepreneurial training can contribute to poverty reduction by promoting economic growth and creating employment opportunities

within the SME sector. The prestigious role entrepreneurs create in establishing new ventures can be seen in the impact on the countries' economic and social conditions (Arthur & Hisrich, 2011; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). To achieve financial stability and growth within Africa's context, the tendency to innovate, diversify, and establish new ventures is essential (Adenle, 2017). Most Sub-Saharan African countries are currently associated with a high unemployment rate and sluggish. The economic growth than other developing countries on different continents, such as India, China, and Brazil (ILO, 2020). The Sub-Saharan region is associated with flourishing opportunities with its challenges. However, it serves as the world's free trade zone for most entrepreneurs (World Bank Review, 2020).

1.1.1 Research Problem

Over the years, there has been an influx of support from diverse stakeholders to foster and enhance entrepreneurship activities in Sub-Saharan Africa. The absence of entrepreneurial training and education can hinder the growth and sustainability of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa (Nafukho & Helen, 2010; Boukamcha, 2015). For instance, Mastercard Foundation, Youth African Leadership Initiative (YALI), International Labour Organisation (ILO), Agricultural Development Bank (ADB), World Bank, and other organisations have partnered with government institutions in various countries to offer support to aspiring entrepreneurs and SMEs (Thamahane, Chetty, and Karodia, 2017; Adenle, 2017; Porfírio et al., 2022). However, the collapse of most SMEs still raises the alarming concerns of most legislators and government officials. They often ask questions about whether entrepreneurship training business owners undertake is inefficient enough to ensure business sustainability in most developing countries (Nwangwu, 2007; Looi & Maritz, 2021).

Therefore, addressing the lack of entrepreneurial training and education becomes crucial in improving the success rates and overall entrepreneurial ecosystem in Sub-Saharan Africa. Despite several support and initiatives from these stakeholders, little effort has been

displayed to foster entrepreneurial activities in the Sub-Saharan region (Adenle, 2017). This is because the persistent increase in business failures in the sub-Saharan area raises alarming concerns about the kind of entrepreneurial training SMEs to go through despite a considerable amount of investment or completing an entrepreneurship training and not yielding the correct result can be a significant concern for most SMEs (Aljuwaiber, 2021). Business failure does not necessarily mean the business is entirely not operational (Davis, 2015). However, when a company is associated with non-reasonable income for the entrepreneurs, underperformance may be characterised as failure (Ucbasaran, Westhead, and Wright, 2009; Short et al., 2010; Aljuwaiber, 2021). Some researchers have associated the persistent increase in business failures with a lack of entrepreneurial training and education (Nafukho & Helen, 2010; Boukamcha, 2015; Mukata, Ladzani, and Visser, 2018; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). Therefore, it is essential to analyse the critical role entrepreneurial training plays in the intentions of SMEs.

1.2 Purpose of the Thesis

The aim of this research is to highlight the impact of entrepreneurship training with respect to the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa (Ghana and Kenya).

This research area is an important approach to analyse entrepreneurship training programmes' critical role in recent working environment among SMEs. The current rise of entrepreneurial training programmes offered is increasing among SMEs in Africa, and however, there is no vivid evidence to justify the impact of the training received among SMEs. The research area will describe the impact of entrepreneurial training on the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in some selected African countries (Ghana and Kenya). Entrepreneurs play a pivotal role in the success of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) (Louise, 2018; Yitbarek et al, 2021). This thesis recognises this fact and focuses on understanding the entrepreneur as the

primary unit of analysis. The decisions, intentions, and actions of these entrepreneurs can make or break the growth and performance of SMEs (Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). Therefore, it is crucial to consider the human factor when evaluating the impact of entrepreneurial training programs.

This thesis focused on the critical concept of entrepreneurial education and training to establish prominent traits and understand its impacts on entrepreneurs already in business. Undoubtedly, SMEs' contribution to developing countries' economies cannot be underestimated (Adenle, 2017; Owusu, 2014; Boso, Debrah, and Amankwah-Amoah, 2018). Entrepreneurial training and education have been promoted across the region to enhance SMEs' activities to foster and stimulate sustainable growth in the long run (Mukata, Ladzani, and Visser, 2018). The topic involves exploring the impact of entrepreneurial training, which indicates a focus on education and skill development for entrepreneurs in Ghana and Kenya. International organisations such as MasterCard Foundation, World Bank, United Nations (UN), and other governmental organisations have invested massively in training initiatives, business advisory services, and financial packages to promote start-up businesses and entrepreneurs who are already in business, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa (Adenle, 2017; Elmansori, 2014; ILO, 2015; Trends, 2019). These approaches ensure that SMEs can materialise the knowledge gained and implement them in businesses. Davis (2015) described these approaches as practical experiences that will enable entrepreneurs to understand their intention, perceive, and express their business operation experiences.

Many Sub-Saharan African governments are introducing policies promoting positive entrepreneurship intentions through entrepreneurial education and training to promote economic growth (Louise, 2018; Yitbarek et al, 2021). This triggers the troubling question of how government policies may influence the intentions of SMEs. The study area is an essential platform for understanding how existing entrepreneurs and SMEs initiate their intent

after entrepreneurial training. The motivation behind the drive their intention will encompass a range of internal and external influences, including policy frameworks, entrepreneurial training and education initiatives, and financial opportunities. This study's primary purpose is to attempt to address and expand the knowledge base of literature from the perspective of SMEs' entrepreneurial training, intentions, and motivational traits during their business operation. Hence, it will aid scholars, academia, policymakers, and other interested organisations to understand better and provide the necessary support for upcoming and existing entrepreneurs. This thesis involves addressing the impact of entrepreneurial training on SMEs, which aligns with the goal of fostering innovation and promoting sustainable industrialisation in Sub-Saharan Africa.

1.3 Research Questions

The following gaps in recent literature regarding the impact of SMEs' entrepreneurial training and education, especially in the Sub-Saharan African context, need review to address this thesis's objectives. The following research questions are selected to guide understanding of the subject area and its practical implication in the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

1. *What impact have entrepreneurship training programmes had on entrepreneurs' capacity and determination in light of efforts by policymakers, educational institutions, global organisations, private entities, and NGOs?*

The first research question of this thesis intends to investigate the general areas of policymakers, educational institutions, and other organisations that have contributed to enhancing the activity of entrepreneurs. Governments worldwide, particularly in developing countries, are exploring strategies to increase the progress of Small and Medium Enterprises

(SMEs) (Aljuwaiber, 2021). At the same time, there is growing pressure to integrate SMEs into the mainstream economy to benefit the entire country in terms of revenue generation and improving the overall welfare of citizens. This question provides an insight into how SMEs' intentions develop and their applicability in reality, especially from the perspective of the public resources available to the SMEs in the region. It also explores the general motivation factors that enhance positive intentions toward success.

2. How can the persistent rise in business failures among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Africa be interpreted in the context of efforts to enhance entrepreneurial capabilities through educational reforms and training initiatives?

This question tends to highlight various parameters that cause business failures among SMEs. Several challenges pinpointed in the literature lead to the persistent increase rate of failure amongst SMEs in Africa. These include a lack of access to finance (Sheriff and Muffatto, 2015; Ssenyonga et al., 2020), lousy business management practices (Sane et al., 2020), a lack of skills to run successful businesses (Mukata et al., 2018), as well as competition from more extensive firms or other companies such as foreign-owned SMEs (Aljuwaiber, 2021). Attempts to address these challenges have not yielded desirable results as the failure rates of SMEs continue to be high (Naicker and Nsengimana, 2022). This will highlight the multiple assumptions that entrepreneurial training and education among SMEs positively impact their intention to strive for success. This will help understand the strength of purpose, considering several business failures despite government policies and educational and training reforms in recent years.

3. 'What factors influence SMEs' desire to develop the intentions to undertake entrepreneurial training initiatives?'

The research question will outline various trigger events that induce existing and upcoming SMEs to adopt positive or negative traits that influence their intentions. These critical questions will help address the gap existing in literature, clear the perception factors for recent business failures, and highlight SMEs' motivation factors and how they navigate through the external environmental factors surrounding their business ecosystem. These questions will aid and contribute a quota to the vast knowledge of literature and enable policymakers and other institutions to adopt the right policies, training, and strategies to promote entrepreneurs' business activities.

1.4 Thesis Objectives

In meeting the aim of this thesis, a series of chronological objectives were set to address the mounting criticism levelled at entrepreneurial training scholars for spending arguably insufficient attention to contextual factors when examining entrepreneurial phenomena such as entrepreneurial training and small businesses (Davis, 2015; Akinso, 2018; Musambayi, 2018; Nsengimana, 2022). These objectives include:

1. To critically review the literature on entrepreneurship training (ET), entrepreneurial intention (EI), and its impact on SMEs, specifically within the African context, namely Ghana and Kenya.

This objective seeks to discuss new variations and alternative approaches to entrepreneurship training initiatives that will analyse current issues within an entrepreneurial ecosystem with their impact on SMEs' intentions. As indicated in the studies' introduction and background, there are little or no thorough studies in Sub-Saharan Africa.

2. Devise and construct an appropriate methodological approach to explore whether entrepreneurial training predicts SMEs' behaviour.

The methodological chapter of this thesis seeks to evaluate numerous research designs and explains the adopted strategy. This objective seeks to explore the link between entrepreneurial training on the operational activities of SMEs.

3. Analyse various factors that influence SMEs' stability of entrepreneurial intention after entrepreneurial training.

This third objective seeks to analyse the sustainability of a job creation after the entrepreneurial training and education programmes. The chosen analytical technique described in the methodology chapter is adopted to meet this objective. This will create an avenue to understand the various issues surrounding SMEs' intentions after their training. This will highlight the different concepts of business failures despite the considerate training and support available. These objectives address whether entrepreneurial training and vocational education account for positive intent towards business success rather than failure.

4. Conclude on, presenting unique contributions for SMEs within entrepreneurial and industry contexts.

The fourth objective seeks to investigate both positive and negative factors of trigger-event of intentions of entrepreneurs. Trigger events are desirable situations that encourage an individual to become an entrepreneur. In this context of entrepreneurship training initiatives, there are quite a few questions as to whether there are situations that influence entrepreneurs' mindsets. Because of that, this objective seeks to present a new models, outline key principles and practise which influence SMEs' intention to strive for success and sustainability in their business operation.

1.5 Geographical Scope of this Thesis

In Africa's context, for those who are not familiar with the nature of the continent, it is not a homogeneous continent. The continent has 55 countries in five (5) sub-regions: north, east, central, west, and southern Africa, with over 2000 other languages from different tribes (Ifedapo, 2020). In this area of study, the study will focus on the Sub-Saharan region. Sub-Saharan countries are countries below the Sub-Saharan belt. The region is associated with different economic indicators, political orientations, cultures, religions, languages, and colonial rulers. Any general thought should be distinguished in Africa and its sub-regions, although there are apparent similarities among many countries.

The research area turns to highlight two Sub-Saharan African countries as the geographical area of study, namely, Ghana and Kenya. The rationale behind the selected countries is that they were part of the top 10 contributors to the region's growth in 2018 and 2019 (IMF Regional Outlook data 2019). The study focuses on Ghana and Kenya as the primary area of study, underpinned by several vital academic and empirical justifications, which includes the rationale behind the shift of the narrative away from the traditional focus on US and European contexts.

Firstly, Ghana and Kenya have emerged as part of the geographical area within the global entrepreneurship and economic development context. This offers a unique divergence from the often Eurocentric discourse. Both countries, Ghana and Kenya, have demonstrated impressive growth in their respective entrepreneurial ecosystems, which presents a compelling case for investigation (Boso et al., 2018; Amoah and Amoah 2018). This shift in narrative away from traditional Western and European settings allows for a more diverse and critical understanding of different approaches to entrepreneurial intentions and SME dynamics. Interestingly, many researchers ascertained that Africa is blessed and opportunities which are similar to any other place in the world (Boso et al., 2018; Amoah and Amoah

2018; Ejesi, and Ejem, 2021). Herrington and Coduras (2019) argued that many countries worldwide perceive Africa as a lost continent coupled with fragile institutions, poor infrastructure, unstable economy, poverty, and diseases that are widely spread across regions.

In recent years, there has been a rise in the number of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana and Kenya (Adenle, 2017; Ejesi, and Ejem, 2021). These SMEs are crucial in creating jobs, promoting innovation, and driving economic growth, making them critical areas for studying entrepreneurial intentions. Exploring these emerging markets in this geographical context revealed unique insights into the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions within a non-Western setting.

In 2018, the World Bank population index projected a Sub-Saharan African of about 1.1 billion. In 2014, the region has seen a rise in the unemployment rate from 5.9% to about 6.2% in 2019 (World Bank, 2020). The Sub-Saharan African region's economic growth has seen an increase in 2017 from 2.5% compared to 2.3% in 2018 (World Bank, 2019). The economic growth in the region remains below the target in comparison to the population growth. Amusingly, the contextual richness of other developing regions, such as (the Middle East, South, and Central America) has received considerable interest from scholars in terms of their rich potential in entrepreneurship, such as oil, tourism, and technology industries (Bastian et al., 2018; Khalifa, 2019). In this view, the two countries have a diverse socio-cultural landscape that can significantly influence entrepreneurs' motivations, aspirations, and outcomes (Elikem and Ofori, 2020). The cultural diversity in the study area makes the research more profound and provides a comprehensive understanding of how entrepreneurial intentions are shaped in different environments.

Nevertheless, there is considerable interest from the public and other international organisations in entrepreneurial activities in Sub-Saharan Africa due to their rich potential

opportunities similar to different continents. Most of the international organisations' engagements were to promote entrepreneurship training initiatives worldwide, especially in developing countries (Boso et al., 2018). The region has attracted massive investment from local governments and international organisations such as MasterCard Foundation, World Bank, YALI, International Labour commission (ILO) for the past decades (Alsheikh, 2009; Adenle, 2017; Mpogole and Baiyegunhi, 2020). Recent attention to entrepreneurial training initiatives in Sub-Saharan African countries should not be surprising, primarily for three reasons.

First and foremost, an institutional failure, such as a history of high corruption and low accountability, leads to the misalignment of capital (Barnard and Luiz, 2018). Secondly, the high unemployment rate in the region has led to a high dependency of graduate students on the government for jobs after completing university or vocational schools (Amoah and Amoah, 2018). Finally, the socio-economic situation in the region can be attributed to the political climate (Ifedapo et al., 2020). Most businesses in Africa depend massively on the political agenda depending on the countries of the establishment (Ifedapo et al., 2020). Sub-Saharan Africa is perceived to be one of the fastest-growing economies in the world, with regional integration of markets to enhance free trade across boundaries to promote entrepreneurship in a different dynamic business environment (Ifedapo et al., 2020).

In 2019, just like in 2018, Sub-Saharan Africa was classified by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) as the fastest-growing world economy (IMF Regional Outlook data 2019). According to Brahim (2019), the Sub-Saharan region was home to the majority of the world's fastest-growing economies over the previous five years. Approximately 20 countries in the region experienced economic expansion at a rate of 5% or higher, surpassing the projected global growth rate of 3.6% in 2019. The 2018 World Bank report indicated that SMEs contribute to over 90% of private businesses in the Sub-Saharan region and contribute

to more than 50% of employment and GDP. Most SMEs are young and often perceived as the core for innovation, economic growth, and job creation opportunities in most countries (Jones et al., 2018; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). SMEs in the region are more labour-intensive (Boso et al., 2018) and demand low capital costs to operate than large firms (Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Adenle, 2017; Elikem and Ofori, 2020).

Table 1.1 Population, Real GDP and SMEs contribution of selected countries

Country	Population (2019) million	Real GDP (2018) %	Real GDP (2019) %	Expected Real GDP (2020) %	SMEs employment contribution (2019) %
<i>Ghana</i>	29,767,108	6.3	6.5	1.5	71
<i>Kenya</i>	52,573,973	6.3	5.6	1.0	81.1

Source: (IMF Data, 2020; World Bank data 2020; Budget Reports 2019-Ghana, Rwanda, Kenya)

1.5.1 Ghana

The significance of SMEs in Ghana cannot be overlooked, as they play a crucial role in the country's economy. These enterprises provide employment opportunities for approximately 85% of the manufacturing workforce, encompassing both rural and urban areas. (Amoah and Amoah, 2018). These projects the vital role the SMEs sector contributes to the Ghanaian economy's socio-economic development, which enables policymakers, investors, and business owners to initiate a pragmatic approach to ensure the development of the sector.

Several reports from the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), African Development Bank (ADB), and budgetary information in Ghana address the region's unemployment and living conditions (Abor and Quartey, 2010; Amoah, and Amoah 2018;

Owusu-ansah 2012). SMEs in Ghana are mostly family-owned businesses transferred from one generation to the other (Pearl, 2018). The crucial role of SMEs in Ghana is essential, yet the sector is associated with uncertainties, leading to the collapse of most businesses in the country (Dankwa, 2018). Therefore, it is essential to train students, young entrepreneurs, and existing SMEs to have a positive intention towards adapting to the dynamic nature of business operating activities in Ghana (Dzisi and Odoom, 2017).

To achieve this, Ghana's government established Polytechnics and vocational schools in most of the regions in Ghana (Owusu-Ansah, 2012). Entrepreneurship modules have been incorporated into the education curriculum from lower to higher-level education to expose students to the risk and opportunities associated with starting new ventures across the country (Dzisi and Odoom, 2017). Yearly, the budgetary report makes provision for SMEs and business training activities in the country. This is to ensure individuals can create jobs, reduce the unemployment rate, and provide the gap created by the universities in terms of providing practical and employment skills are bridged.

Furthermore, other international organisations and other philanthropists such as MasterCard Foundation and the World Bank has also invested immensely in Ghana to promote the activities of SMEs by providing them with access to business advisory services and financial opportunities in the country (Adenle, 2017; Reeta 2006; MasterCard Foundation report 2015). These opportunities were initiated to provide practical application of skills to their business operation. In order to attain this objective, it is crucial to comprehend the impact of entrepreneurial education and training programs initiated by the Ghanaian government and other local and international organizations on the aspirations and motivations of these entrepreneurs. The aim of this thesis to establish prominent traits of entrepreneurial training and understand its impacts on entrepreneurs already in business.

1.5.2 Kenya

The Kenyan economy is challenged by a high unemployment rate, low business activities, and a declining level of entrepreneurial activities, which hinders economic growth. Over the years, several graduates from universities and other vocational institutions have put pressure on the government for jobs (Hunter and Lean, 2018). The government has taken strategic measures to incorporate integrated entrepreneurship and other business modules in the education curriculum to enable innate talented individuals to spot opportunities and successfully execute them (Kinya, Wanjau, and Omondi, 2018). Start-up businesses and existing SMEs have been grappling with succeeding in this challenging business environment across the globe.

Since the outbreak of COVID-19, Kenya's flower industry, which serves as an employment podium for many SMEs, has financially impacted and threatened most businesses' existence (David, 2020). Mang'unyi, Mwanzia, and Govender (2018) also argued that 95% of SMEs and entrepreneurial activity contribute to Kenya's economy from their vibrant informal sector. As a result, various local and international institutions, including the Youth and Women Enterprise Development, MasterCard Foundation, and IMF, have taken action to facilitate access to information and business guidance for SMEs in Kenya, aiming to foster the development of their businesses within the country (World Bank, 2017; Mang'unyi, Mwanzia, and Govender, 2018). The government has also provided support by establishing business incubation services that offer advisory assistance to SMEs, with the aim of ensuring their long-term growth and contributing to sustainable economic development and goals in the country (Micro and Small Enterprises Authority, 2013).

The study in Kenya's context is essential because it pinpointed various concepts to understand how entrepreneurs positively intend to succeed after undergoing different entrepreneurial and management training. This will help various business incubatory service

providers from high education or private institutions to embrace and understand entrepreneurs' perceptions, mainly in Kenya and Sub-Saharan African countries. This will help the government understand various parameters to consider promoting job creation in the region. An exploratory qualitative methodological approach was employed for the studies. This approach was adapted to explore new insights and trend into a relatively new area of research. This will help understand the rationale behind with 'how' and 'why' research questions to address the aim of the study.

1.6 Implications for the Researcher

Many researchers have contributed to the discussion about SMEs' vital role in solving unemployment problems, reducing poverty, and underpinning SMEs' constraints. Previous findings contributed to and addressed various diverse factors resulting in the high failure rates of small businesses. The implications of this research for the researcher involve; the adoption of a more inclusive sample, addressing research gaps and methodological deficiencies, considering a holistic approach to entrepreneurship support, and expanding the geographical scope of future studies.

The review indicated that a few empirical studies on the influence on intentions of SMEs' survival and the very high failure rates of SMEs justified the need for this study. The study's findings filled the gap concerning entrepreneurial training actions contributing to SMEs' survival. This this thesis

- SMEs play a vital role in addressing unemployment problems and reducing poverty. This implication aligns with SDG 1 No Poverty. Entrepreneurial training can be seen as an avenue for poverty reduction by promoting economic growth and creating job opportunities within the SME sector.
- Previous research has identified various influences that contribute to the high failure rates of small businesses. This thesis also addresses key elements and

factors needed to address the persistence of business failures. This is because entrepreneurial training help promote the capacity and skills of SMEs, leading to increased productivity, job creation, and economic growth within Ghana and Kenya.

- The thesis also aimed to fill a gap in the literature regarding the influence of entrepreneurial training on SMEs' survival. Several theoretical was reviewed to understand the various gaps in the literature by exploring the impact of entrepreneurial training, and how they influence the intentions of actual entrepreneurs which indicates a focus on education and skill development for entrepreneurs in sub-Saharan Africa to ensure sustainability and growth of business.
- The research findings will contributed to understanding and addressing the challenges faced by SMEs. This thesis seek to gain to provide insights and actions that can support the survival and success of SMEs. Entrepreneurial training can enhance the capacity and skills of SMEs, leading to increased productivity, job creation, and economic growth within Ghana and Kenya. The study aims to provide practical implications and recommendations for supporting SMEs in overcoming challenges in Sub-Saharan African countries.

1.6.1 Relevance of the Study

The problem of how entrepreneurial training influences the intentions of SMEs is essential to address for diverse reasons. Firstly, the dynamic nature of the world demands a knowledge-driven approach where the societal expectation is that entrepreneurial training promotes national and economic development (Jones et al., 2018). Secondly, Understanding this role requires new approaches and principles (Baloch et al., 2017). Thirdly, It is vital for

the active labour force in most developing countries to understand their aspirations and desires to achieve economic independence in society rather than relying on their government for employment.

There have been significant concerns about the global job crunch, such as the high unemployment rate, unfavourable conditions for start-up businesses, business failures, and vulnerable people, especially in most Sub-Saharan African countries. Business failures are rampant in most African countries (Adenle, 2017; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). Most businesses in Africa fail between three to 5 years of operation (Jones et al., 2018). This discourages most promising entrepreneurs from venturing into entrepreneurship and most SMEs in sub-Saharan Africa. Davis (2015) suggested that many barriers influence SMEs' intentions, especially in their early business operation stages. These calamities have affected many people to migrate from their countries to seek greener pastures in other countries (Pearl, 2018). This study area was motivated by the current perception of African entrepreneurial activities and served as a platform for African scholars' and academia's interest in entrepreneurship, SMEs, start-up businesses, and business sustainability research to voice out. As Bastian et al. (2018) described in developed countries, the concept of entrepreneurship themes, which encompasses 'intentions, behaviour, motivation, education, and training,' is well-posed in many journals and academic literature. Surprisingly, despite a growing interest in entrepreneurship among various governments, organisations, and other philanthropists in Sub-Saharan African countries, available literature on such entrepreneurship themes as training, education, intention, and motivation is less prominent in most international journals.

Interestingly, over the past decade, in areas where such journals exist on entrepreneurial training and intention in the context of the African continent, most available literature primarily focuses on students and graduate students as their case study (Nafukho &

Helen, 2010; Yabashaija, and Katono 2011; Owusu-ansah, 2012; Shonubi and Taiwo, 2013; O'leary, 2017). More literature needs to be available on the context of entrepreneurial training and its impact on existing entrepreneurs and SMEs already operating a business (Davis,2015; Louise, 2018; Adenle, 2017; Amato et al., 2018).

This research area can make an impact on adding knowledge and understanding insight into entrepreneurship activities. The outcome of this thesis provides as the foundation for governments and stakeholders to implement the necessary assistance, strategies and techniques to address these crucial global crises in the business ecosystem.

1.6.2 Post-Pandemic SME prosperity

The hit of COVID-19 cases in Sub-Sahara Africa hindered most SMEs in relation to free trade movement since most borders were closed. Other Sub-Saharan African countries whose economic activity depends excessively on tourism sector engagement, aviation, production, manufacturing, exportation, and many more faced severe disruption (Dirk, 2020; United Nations report 2020). For example, countries like Rwanda and Ethiopia, the leading producers of coffee in the region, experienced a decline in revenue since the prices fell by 10% in the first quarter of 2020 (Dirk, 2020). The flower industries in Kenya noted for exporting flowers to European countries such as the United Kingdom, Netherlands, and Germany cut down production by 80%, and over 80% of their workers across the flower supply chain were either sent home or out of business since the outbreak of the COVID-19 in the first quarter of 2020 (David 2020; Dirk, 2020). The Ethiopian airline, one of Sub-Saharan's most successful aviation networks, has lost about \$550 million from January to April since the pandemic outbreak (Tewolde,2020). The impact of the pandemic in the Sub-Saharan region disrupted every economic activity from aviation to hospitality, schools, and people's social lives. *This is because most SMEs in the region are doctrine to define their*

purpose of operating by maximising their long term-value of selling goods and services (Jones et al., 2018).

1.6.2 Expected Audience

This thesis addresses and make an argumentative assertion about the idea of entrepreneurial training and its impact on SMEs, and the conclusions specifically highlight to address the needs of the various stakeholders below;

Policymakers: To understand and ensure the right policies are implemented to promote entrepreneurship within the context of SMEs.

Educational institutions: Ensure the right training needs are incorporated into the educational curriculum. Non-compulsory education in university; potentially more vocational and experiential if more SME-based.

NGOs, Investors: Understand entrepreneurs' intentions and ensure that appropriate investments are made to prevent the waste of resources.

SMEs, Promising and young entrepreneurs, and individuals: for the purpose of this study, these key stakeholders are classified as the end-users of entrepreneurship training and education. The majority of this training is centred around them. The study will highlight how they see themselves in the business ecosystem and pinpoint some push and pull factors that influence their intentions as entrepreneurs.

1.7 Structure of the Thesis

The organisational structure of this research area will be segmented into nine chapters.

Table 1.2 Structure of the Thesis

Part I:	Chapter 1	The thesis opens with a background to the study area. The research area's importance, research questions, aim, and objectives will be underpinned and outlined
Theoretical Review		

		<p>vividly in this chapter. Furthermore, this chapter clarifies and describes the scope and structure of the dissertation.</p>
	Chapter 2	<p>Focused on a detailed existing literature review on entrepreneurial education and training, distinguish between education and training, the impact of entrepreneurship training, and various policies initiated by the various governments to promote SMEs activities</p> <p>Apprenticeship Training Programmes and the SME Context. The chapter explores the role and importance of apprenticeship programs in the context of small and medium-sized enterprises. It explores how apprenticeship training can contribute to developing a skilled workforce, innovation, and sustainability in SMEs. The chapter provides insights into the practical implementation and benefits of apprenticeship programs for SMEs and aspiring entrepreneurs.</p>
	Chapter 3	<p>This chapter highlights and explores the unique challenges and opportunities faced by small and medium-sized African enterprises. It examines the socio-economic factors, government policies, and institutional support that impact the growth and</p>

		development of SMEs. The chapter highlights the importance of entrepreneurial education and training in addressing these challenges and promoting sustainable SME growth in Africa. It provides valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners seeking to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem and support SMEs in Africa.
Part II: Methodology and Collected Data	Chapter 4	<p>Entrepreneurial Intentions: Models and Practicalities</p> <p>Development of Conceptual Framework and Summary of thesis with lead to clear strategy of methodological approach to adopt for the study.</p> <p>This chapter underpins various factors, including the level of entrepreneurial education and training individuals receive. Understanding the relationship between SMEs, entrepreneurial education/training, and entrepreneurial intention is crucial for developing a comprehensive conceptual framework that guides policy and practice in fostering entrepreneurship and supporting SME growth.</p>
	Chapter 5	<p>Gives a detailed approach of the methodologies adopted, justification of methods, sampling techniques, data analysis, and ethical issues in acquiring data concerning the study area. The methodological chapter details further as displayed in Table 1.2, this thesis follow a deductive approach in</p>

		acknowledging relevant theories and discussion points towards the sub Saharan entrepreneurial SMEs context.
Part III: Analysis and thesis contributions	Chapter 6	The analysis chapter of this thesis delves into the data collected from the participants, providing a detailed examination of their responses and insights. Through an inductive approach, themes and patterns emerge, underpinning the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions and the impact of entrepreneurial training on SMEs' success and sustainability
	Chapter 7	This chapter highlights the contributions to theory, practice, and research methods by underpinning the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions in the SME context. It provides valuable insights to inform the development of effective policies, training programs, and research methodologies to foster entrepreneurial success and sustainability in Sub-Saharan African countries
Part IV: Conclusion	Chapter 8	Conclusion and Implications: This chapter underpins the implications of this thesis twofold. First, it highlights the need for policymakers and educators to design targeted entrepreneurial training programmes that address SMEs' specific needs and challenges. Second, it emphasises the importance of considering personal motivations, experiences, and support

		systems in fostering entrepreneurial intentions and success.
	Chapter 9	Recommendations : This chapter also recommends that policymakers, educational institutions, and other stakeholders prioritise the development of comprehensive and tailored entrepreneurial training programs. These programs should focus on enhancing business acumen, addressing risk mitigation strategies, and providing support networks for aspiring and existing SME owners. Additionally, there is a need for improved communication and dissemination of government policies to ensure their effective implementation and impact on SMEs.

1.8 Conclusion

This chapter highlighted and underpinned various gaps and the purpose of the study. Over the years, there has been an influx of support from diverse stakeholders to foster and enhance entrepreneurship activities related to entrepreneurial training in Sub-Saharan Africa. This chapter highlighted the vital role of understanding the essence of entrepreneurial training and its impact on the intentions of SMEs. It is crucial first to understand and elaborate on the importance of entrepreneurial the four key objectives as clearly stated in section 1.4. Specifically, it is vital to review the literature on entrepreneurship training (ET), entrepreneurial intention (EI), and its impact on SMEs, specifically within the African context, namely Ghana and Kenya. The next chapter will establish a solid connection to theoretical fundamentals to answer the various research questions.

The next chapter will focus on reevaluating academic literature to understand entrepreneurial training and education areas, which will provide a logical approach to establish a connection to construct a theoretical framework to measure the extent of its impact on the intentions of SMEs. Understanding these critical entrepreneurship concepts, entrepreneurial training, and entrepreneurship education will provide in-depth knowledge to understand SMEs' various trigger and motivational traits. Furthermore, SME dimensions that inspire the desired behaviour of entrepreneurs help understand the various concepts and underpin appropriate policies and practices to advance an ethos of the informed nature of SMEs.

Chapter 2: Entrepreneurship Education and Apprenticeship Training in African SMEs

This chapter aims to review the literature to establish a solid connection to theoretical fundamentals to answer the various research questions. This chapter's prime niche will focus on reviewing academic literature to develop an up-to-date account of entrepreneurial training and education areas, which will provide a logical approach to establish a connection to construct a theoretical framework to measure the extent of its impact on the intentions of SMEs.

The chapter is divided into sub-sections to analyse three critical primary concepts, entrepreneurial training (Alexandria et al., 2014; Lubbe, 2016; Abioye et al., 2017; Odhiambo et al 2021), entrepreneurship education (Mangundjaya, 2015; Matlay, 2018; Murray et al., 2018; Alakaleek, 2019) and apprenticeship training programme (Baloch, Rahim and Manzoor, 2017; Ojala, And Heikkilä, 2011).

Research Question 1: *To what magnitude has this plan by policymakers, educational institutions, global organisations, private institutions and NGOs input towards entrepreneurship training programmes impacted on an entrepreneur's ability and intention to strive for success?'*

A review of these vital concepts will outline various similarities and differential traits to enable the researcher to understand and identify multiple interchangeable gaps and characteristics. This will help develop a conceptual framework to conceptualise the study area in the Sub-Saharan African region.

2.1 Entrepreneurial Education: A Brief Overview

Entrepreneurship is not a new phenomenon, and over the years, it has gained increased interest from researchers. Arguably, the entrepreneurial course was first introduced at Harvard University in 1947, of which 188 business students were enrolled (Lorz, 2011). Many universities worldwide have incorporated entrepreneurship modules and programs into their curriculum for decades along the line. Entrepreneurship interest in recent years is due to the contribution of SMEs to the economy of most countries in terms of innovation, job creation, and diversity of the business sector (Ardichvili, Cardozo and Ray 2003; Rachmawan, Lizar and Mangundjaya 2015; Louise, 2018). Entrepreneurial education (EE) concerns have triggered individuals' behaviours, skills, and attributes to help the creation, sustain, and enhance creativity and innovation (Mangundjaya 2015; Odhiambo et al 2021). The nature of entrepreneurship involves a high realm of uncertainty and complexity, aiming to achieve personal fulfillment and productivity (Louise, 2018). Incorporating Entrepreneurship Education serves as a strategic approach to enhance the quantity and quality of graduates engaging in enterprising endeavors within the economy (Matlay, 2011). However, limited research has been conducted on graduate self-employment and the establishment of new ventures, as universities prioritize various aspects such as skill development, cultural norms, research focus, and knowledge (Matlay, 2011). Conversely, Gibb (2012) and Salem (2014) highlight universities' role in cultivating an environment, culture, practices, and opportunities that foster and support student and graduate entrepreneurship, promoting collaboration among existing institutional activities.

However, many researchers have acknowledged the influential and critical role most educational and training institutions execute in supporting entrepreneurship (Matlay, 2008; NdofirepI & Rambe, 2017). Support from government agencies and other philanthropic organisations, in addition to the role of an educational institution play, is helping to address

the challenges associated with small scale businesses (Boukamcha, 2015). This serves to create a podium to enhance enterprise culture, which will improve the development of small-scale firms (Nafukho and Helen 2010). They further suggested that governmental institutions and other developmental agencies responsible for entrepreneurial initiatives are significant for small businesses because these institutions provide valuable pieces of information and advisory assistance to ensure sustainability.

Furthermore, several literature reviews, articles, and findings from authors, scholars, and researchers' substantial contributions to knowledge acknowledge the importance of entrepreneurial training and education activities among young entrepreneurs and students (Boukamcha, 2015; Matlay, 2018; Daisy, Tanusree and Raiswa 2017; Elikem and Ofori, 2020). However, very limited or no substantial evidence of the complexity of such training for SMEs, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa (Mukata, Ladzani, and Visser, 2018; Louise, 2018). To help the researcher understand comprehensively, the literature review in this chapter will focus primarily on distinguishing between entrepreneurship training and education, categorising various traits of entrepreneurial education, and underpinning and reviewing several policies.

2.2 Dimensions of Entrepreneurship Education

Ideally, entrepreneurial education should be encouraged in higher institutions. This is because (Matlay, 2018) identified two broad generic models of entrepreneurial education, i.e. the magnet and radiant entrepreneurial models.

The magnet and radiant entrepreneurial education models have emerged as approaches to attract and engage students in entrepreneurship courses. The magnet model focuses on drawing students to business schools and offering relevant courses, while the radiant model targets non-business students and provides context-specific entrepreneurship training. This expansion of entrepreneurship education extends beyond traditional business

faculties to disciplines like engineering and pharmacy, equipping professionals with the necessary business knowledge to pursue their ventures. Matlay (2011) highlights the importance of tailoring entrepreneurship education to diverse student interests and providing them with the skills and knowledge of entrepreneurial activities. Ultimately, regardless of the location or setting of the entrepreneurial training program, its objective remains consistent to cultivate aspiring entrepreneurs with a future-oriented mindset (Hayter et al., 2017). Entrepreneurial education has become even more critical in economic issues such as unemployment, which includes unemployed graduates and entrepreneurs who are yet or already in business. There needs to be more research exploring the correlation between entrepreneurial education and the specific requirements of aspiring graduate entrepreneurs (Matlay, 2011). The majority of educational establishments have the potential to foster and promote an entrepreneurial mindset among students, thereby helping them manage their expectations regarding the job market (Murray et al., 2018).

Whether formal or informal, entrepreneurship education and training has the capacity to project a vital role in fostering enterprising students in various settings, including universities (Matlay, 2011; Odhiambo et al 2021), the dynamic nature of the entrepreneurial ecosystem puts immense pressure on educational institutions, particularly universities, to enhance the practical learning experiences for students (Gibb & Haskins, 2014). By incorporating entrepreneurship education, universities can facilitate research collaborations, offer internship opportunities, and support student and staff mobility, bridging the gap between academia and the external environment (Murray et al., 2018). These measures ensure that students are equipped with the skills and knowledge through creativity and innovation to steer the entrepreneurial ecosystem effectively.

The increasing number of educated entrepreneurs has brought formal entrepreneurship to the forefront, particularly in developed countries (Hayter et al., 2017).

This viewpoint highlights the importance of entrepreneurial education in shaping individuals' inclination towards entrepreneurship. This strengthens the claim that educated, and graduate entrepreneurs are more likely to contribute to a nation's economy significantly. As a result of previous studies on entrepreneurship education, there has been a notable transformation in recent years, with the expansion of entrepreneurship programmes in schools and tertiary institutions across the globe (Hayter et al., 2017). The introduction of entrepreneurship programs in the educational curriculum can be traced back to Harvard University in 1947 (Lorz, 2011). In a separate study conducted by Murray et al. (2018), the focus was on how effective entrepreneurship education can foster the development of young entrepreneurs. Although they ascertained the fact that the delivery of teaching approaches in the universities and educational institutions has attracted inadequate attention from scholars, from this point of view, they proposed three vital elements from a theoretical perspective: "Content, delivery and support" to nurture students, new and young vibrant entrepreneurs.

Furthermore, the theoretical framework of Murray et al. (2018) demonstrated a broad sector approach to delivering entrepreneurship education to students to ensure success. Murray et al. (2018) model has primarily focused on alerting students to the awareness of entrepreneurial opportunities and necessary support. However, their framework ignored students' socio-cultural background and factors and how such models will influence their intention, behaviour, feelings, and how they react to entrepreneurship within a specified time, considering the dynamic nature of entrepreneurship.

The spirit of entrepreneurship is dynamic and associated with uncertainties (Nwangwu, 2007; Trends, 2019). Several research findings have identified entrepreneurial training and education as an essential element in understanding entrepreneurs' fundamental needs (Matlay, 2018; Murray et al., 2018). Others view it as a means to develop an intrinsic intent toward job creation (Ajzen, 1991; Shapero & Sokol, 1982; Lorz, 2011; Santoso, 2017).

Table 2.1 Dimensions of Entrepreneurial Education

Classification	Approach	Focus
Entrepreneurship awareness	Experiential/action oriented	Personal development, knowledge,
Entrepreneurship for Start-ups	Self-determined, Repeated practice	Problem into concept, Idea generation development, Competence development
Dynamism of entrepreneurial activity	Flexible session, learning from mistakes	Problem solving, adapting to change

Adapted from Gibb

(2007)

It is better to adopt a conducive approach to understand both the fundamental needs and approaches to develop a stable positive intention for self-employment in this context. This dimension approach to entrepreneurial education can be critically assessed regarding the degree to which individuals desire to start and manage a business. This includes things they intend to do before and after, influencing their attitudes towards thinking, organising, understanding and learning new things. This teaching approach is arguably the core of entrepreneurial learning (Entrepreneurship awareness, Entrepreneurship for start-ups and dynamism for entrepreneurial activity), which can form the basis for the appraisal of the value of the numerous pedagogical methods In other to contribute immensely to recent research, deductions from literature reviews revealed three main categorisations of entrepreneurship programmes taught in schools and other training facilities. These categorisations are;

First and foremost, Entrepreneurship awareness aims to enhance the scope of knowledge surrounding entrepreneurship and individuals adopting a positive attitude to trigger the intent toward self-employment (Short et al., 2010; Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013; Koe & Majid, 2014; Ndofirepi and Rambe 2017; Alakaleek, 2019).

The second category is 'Entrepreneurship for Start-ups'. These categories define entrepreneurial programs that generally enhance or promote individuals who already have an existing idea or need to capitalise on societal problems to become self-employed (Estay, Durrieu, and Akhter, 2013; Daisy, Tanusree and Raiswa, 2017).

The third category focus on the 'dynamic nature of the entrepreneurial activity.' The category primarily focuses on individuals who are already existing entrepreneurs and want to incorporate dynamism in their business operations. These dynamisms can be adopting new skills or adopting new strategies (Bastian, Yusuf, and Amine, 2018; Alexandria, Brent and Alicia, 2018; Fatoki, 2018; Linan, 2004).

According to these categorisations, it can be observed that even though entrepreneurship is taught in schools, especially at the early stages of an individual's life, they are foreseen to enable them to develop aptitude attention towards awareness of creating jobs and build a sense of self-efficacy to cultivate the habit of discovering and solving societal problems (Rachmawan, Lizar, and Mangundjaya 2015). Whiles the other category takes into consideration the uncertain venture of entrepreneurial activity after graduating. As it is difficult to predict the dynamic nature of the economy, it is vital to adapt to change in terms of skills and strategies (Alexandria, Brent, and Alicia, 2018) to achieve success. This can be possible through continual training to adjust to skills demanded to solve societal problems (Linan, 2004).

In a nutshell, this entrepreneurial education and training, either in school or after school, equip individuals to develop an intent to job creation, initiate an idea, accept the risk and failures involved and adapt to change in solving problems through skills enhancement. Little attention is highlighted to the practicality of such education received, especially in entrepreneurial education. This chapter has postulated several differences, characteristics, and similarities between enterprise education, entrepreneurial education, and training.

2.3 Enterprise Education vs Entrepreneurship Education

The term enterprise education and entrepreneurship education cause confusions to educators and researchers since both terms address the same issue (Bridge, 2015). Enterprise Education emanated from the United Kingdom (UK) and has gained immense interest from many educationalists in various higher education worldwide (Liguori *et al.*, 2019). Draycott, Rae, and Vause (2011) argued that policymakers for enterprise education development in England incorporate individual development into educational curricula, including unique skills to understand business financial management and business venture as a whole.

Policymakers and academia arguably used the terms "enterprise and entrepreneurship education" interchangeably (Gibb, 1993; Hytti & O'Gorman, 2004). Hytti and O'Gorman (2004) argued that most countries are promoting enterprise education to create an avenue to nurture promising and young entrepreneurs who will become actual entrepreneurs and possibly increase the propensity for self-employment and other employment opportunities in a country. The underlining confusion has been whether enterprise education is the same as entrepreneurship education. Distinguishing between enterprise education and entrepreneurship studies can be challenging, as argued by Gibb (1993) and Bridge (2015). They highlight the blurred boundaries between these two fields. To shed light on this confusion, Liguori *et al.* (2019) propose a comprehensive definition of enterprise education. According to their suggestion, enterprise education encompasses a wide range of activities

aimed at fostering students' creativity, encouraging innovative ideas and strategic decision-making, and developing their ability to handle risk. However, there has been a blur in distinguishing between enterprise and entrepreneurship education, with both concepts overlapping. Enterprise education is preferably used in work-related learning, action and experimental learning, and entrepreneurial education (Gibb, 1993; Hytti & O'Gorman, 2004; Bridge, 2015).

According to Gibb (1993), enterprise education has often been limited by its association with a narrow business framework, which has resulted in numerous unsuccessful attempts to integrate entrepreneurship education into mainstream curricula. Gibb's perspective emphasizes the importance of enterprise education in providing added value and motivation to aspiring entrepreneurs. Building upon this viewpoint, Belwal, Balushi, and Belwal (2015) suggested that individuals who possess an entrepreneurial spirit are often referred to as "enterprising individuals," highlighting the close relationship between entrepreneurship and the concept of enterprise. Nevertheless, their argument further suggested that enterprise is a very complex concept that can transform individuals into entrepreneurs, adapt and enhance skills, and spot and capitalise on opportunities to invent new ideas.

To ascertain the agreement on the use of both concepts by these researchers, Fayolle et al. (2006) suggested that it can influence students' attitude toward entrepreneurship when the word enterprise is used in higher education to create awareness of other jobs. In contrast, entrepreneurship education is vital in most policymakers' perception because of its essential role acknowledged globally. Ndofirepi and Rambe (2017) suggested that the term entrepreneurship is well recognised for its immense contribution to economic growth as a podium for creating jobs in several countries, especially in most politicians' eyes. The Quality Assurance Agency in the United Kingdom said, "enterprise education is aimed to

produce graduates to develop ideas to solve a societal problem and the ability to act on them." Whiles entrepreneurship education aims at producing graduates to encourage the application of acquired enterprise skills to create and operate either new or existing business ventures with the ultimate goal of building upon opportunities (QAA, 2012). In view of this, it can be argued that enterprise education looks into an immense scope of acquiring knowledge, initiating, and developing skills in both social and business contexts. In contrast, entrepreneurship education focuses on applying the mindset of setting up your venture in an entrepreneurial ecosystem. Both definitions have similar characteristics, making it difficult for scholars, academia, and policymakers to distinguish between both concepts.

2.4 Entrepreneurship Education (EE) vs Entrepreneurship Training (ET)

Entrepreneurship education and training are not done just within schools and universities (Nkirina, 2010) where it is required. Henry, Hill, and Leitch (2005) underpinned some crucial facts that increased several seminars, conferences, and workshops centred around entrepreneurial training and education offered by consultants, NGOs, and trade associations in recent years. Indeed, the entrepreneurship concepts and their undiminished nature have developed several interests from researchers and development practitioners in entrepreneurship education and training over the past decades (Hynes, 1996; Matlay, 2008; Ojala and heikkilä, 2011; Alexandria et al., 2014; Abioye et al., 2017). Although not much literature has focused on the concept of distinguishing between entrepreneurship training and education to understand both concepts vividly, since the area developed an immense interest over the years, it is essential to differentiate between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurship training.

The difference between entrepreneurship education and training is often confusing (Hynes, 1996). Garavan, Costine, and Heraty (1995) argued that the definition of entrepreneurship education involves several activities that enable people to adapt and

develop the knowledge, skills, and technical mindset of solving societal problems from a broad perspective, which allows the opportunity to define the traits, analyse and solve a societal problem. Hynes (1996) supported their stance but further argued that entrepreneurship education could be a formal or informal approach that is not limited or narrow to the field of activities needed. Ten years after Hynes's (1996) definition, Fayolle, Gailly, and Lassas-Clerc (2006) also defined entrepreneurship education as encompassing entrepreneurial attitude and skills to develop specific personal unique characteristics in a gradual duration. These authors perceived entrepreneurship education as an incremental activity to cultivate and develop the knowledge, skills, and mindset of solving a societal problem within specifically structured durations. The nature of entrepreneurship is sophisticated and demands a technical approach to enhance job creation and technical perspectives (Ndofirepi and Rambe 2017). Therefore, entrepreneurship education can be summarised as the technical approach of acquiring knowledge, improving skills and attitude, and attaining a positive mindset towards new venture creation within a structural duration.

In the case of entrepreneurship training, it can be argued as the conscious effort to organise, plan and develop a systematic approach to modify, and acquire knowledge and skills through learning experiences, which is vital to enhance performances in several activities (Hynes, 1996). Ojala and Heikkilä (2011) also viewed entrepreneurship training as providing relevant and pedagogical training for entrepreneurs who have a viable business idea. Their view of entrepreneurial activity was centred around building upon capacity, skills, and technical know-how to improve performance and productivity.

Farashah (2013) also argued that entrepreneurship training underpins the complex nature of noticeable gaps in classroom learning and practical realities. In other to support his findings, Putta (2014) discussed entrepreneurship training as a general purpose to enhance performance through awareness and a positive mindset. Putta (2014) further suggested that

institutions and industry associations should organise entrepreneurship training to familiarise participants with the core characteristics of the operating business, emphasising practically hands-on learning in specific business activities. Putta's (2014) view of entrepreneurship training was similar to Hynes's (1996) earlier research, which perceived entrepreneurship as a short-term learning approach to equip individuals with entrepreneurial interest through practical and hands-on training to acquire and promote their knowledge and skills base capacity to become entrepreneurs.

Table 2.2 Summarised traits of EE and ET

Parameters	EE	ET
Focus	Develop a basic desire for entrepreneurship	Enhance skills and develop a mind-positive mindset towards entrepreneurship
Learning Approach	Application of informative skill developing and inductive strategies	cognitive learning
Nature of training	General basic training	Specialised intensive, structured training
Methods	Teachers' and Lecturers, assumptions	Experience Mentors, Role models, and Highly skilled personals.
Duration	Long Structured Periods	Short periods
Venues	Classroom approach mostly accessed pass/fail approach	Business incubator Centers and off-classroom approach, which is accessed mainly by evaluation
Target group	Secondary and Higher education students	Vulnerable, unemployed, skilled individuals, potentials entrepreneurs, business owners, Secondary and Higher education students

Rewards	Certificates upon Graduation	Performance, output and impact
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Source: Author's deduction adapted from (Alsheikh, 2009; Alexandria et al., 2014)

The future of entrepreneurs will be successful if effective mechanisms are instilled to shape their intentions through a practical approach (Daisy, Tanusree and Raiswa 2017). However, conceptual clarity on the suitable model for entrepreneurship training is needed to ensure business success (Ibrahaim and Soufani 2002). There are no personality characteristics and skills to provide successful entrepreneurs in several entrepreneurial contexts in simple terms. To address this confusion about the appropriate entrepreneurship training, it is vital to underpin the characteristics of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurship training.

Entrepreneurship education is associated with an educator's intervention to instil entrepreneurship qualities and adapt skills to inspire learners to survive in their business operations (Esllyn, Kobus, Christian and Pradeep 2007). Over the years, the traditional teaching methods have been used to transpire entrepreneurship information and knowledge to students (Swanson and Morrison 2010). This teaching approach is mostly classroom-based and has received several criticisms in recent years (Johnson-hunter 2004; Nafukho. and Muyia, 2010; Lubbe, 2016; Chmielewski-Raimondo, Mckeown and Brooks, 2016). These researchers cautioned that contemporary entrepreneurial education had abandoned the cognitive learning approach, where learners are tasked to explore their mental capacity to solve societal problems practically within the business ecosystem. However, Daisy, Tanusree, and Raiswa (2017) classified entrepreneurship education into two broad target groups: 'secondary education students' and 'higher education students.' Their higher education classification included undergraduate and graduate students enrolled on accredited degree programmes that are deemed to be acknowledged upon completion.

To support this distinguished trait of entrepreneurship education, several researchers have mainly focused on students in their case studies when investigating entrepreneurship education (Souitaris, Zerbinati, Al-Laham, 2007; Lorz, 2011; Farashah, 2013; Alakaleek, 2019). The arguments of these scholars have allowed most educational institutions across the globe to develop a more customised and suitable student-centred education curriculum to trigger the interest in entrepreneurship of people and students at the early stage.

On the other hand, entrepreneurship training has been described by Alexandria, Brent, and Alicia (2014) as a specific, dynamic, and goal-oriented approach to acquiring skills and a technical mindset to operate a business. They further argued that entrepreneurship training could be classified based on its target audience. Their arguments supported Daisy, Tanusree, and Raiswa's argument, which perceived entrepreneurship education as more classroom-based to acquire entrepreneurship knowledge. In contrast, entrepreneurship training focuses primarily on knowledge and skills enhancement in business operations. In contrast to entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship training predominantly focuses on capacity building, knowledge enhancement, and managing and operating a business (Alexandria et al., 2014).

Alsheikh's (2009) research findings indicated that Business incubators also provide the necessary training that helps entrepreneurs start, expand, and sustain their businesses. This implies that the nature of entrepreneurship training is perceived to spot specific potential target groups and audiences. Earlier scholars such as Hynes (1996) suggested that entrepreneurial training is most suitable for individuals practising entrepreneurship ventures (managing their own business) who do not have entrepreneurship or are not previously enrolled in formal education on entrepreneurship. Several researchers have supported his argument over the past decades (Kolvereid and Moen, 1997; Ulvenblad, Berggren, and Winborg, 2013; Daisy et al., 2017).

Given the above, some differential traits can be pointed out from the review of entrepreneurship training and education. This implies that potential entrepreneurs develop a positive attitude towards entrepreneurial activities through entrepreneurship education at the early stages of their lives. In contrast, entrepreneurship training helps develop and enhance their skills at various stages of their entrepreneurial activities. Despite considerable attention and values towards entrepreneurship education, some entrepreneurial traits, such as self-confidence, However, the rationale is to emphasise, understand and distinguish between the characteristics of entrepreneurship education and training structured for entrepreneurs.

2.5 Apprenticeship Training Programmes

'Apprenticeship' is considered temporary employment to prepare an individual for an expert profession (Baloch, Rahim, and Manzoor, 2017). The procedures of learning entrepreneurship are evolving around the restrictions placed on traditional classrooms based on the only place to learn and examine are changing (Matlay 2005). The current business environment demands a flexible fundamental approach to enhance entrepreneurial skills. It is deemed vital to create an adjustable podium and redefine the learning approach methods (Putta, 2014). This approach encourages potential entrepreneurs and students to acquire hands-on experience and understanding of their trade or business line in the real world (Baloch, Rahim and Manzoor, 2017; Ojala, And Heikkilä, 2011; Nkirina, 2010; Matley, 2005). However, an apprenticeship as an entry-level for entrepreneurs to acquire the necessary skills is fantastic for potential and promising entrepreneurs to gain a background understanding of their chosen business line (Baloch, Rahim, and Manzoor, 2017). The critical objective of apprenticeship is to expose entrepreneurs to understanding the different perspectives of the business industry. Nkirina (2010) argued that apprenticeship is a planning stage to progressively understand the defining features of how to apply, develop, and apply all the functional aptitudes in the business ecosystem. This indicates that entrepreneurs' past

experiences tend to achieve great success as it prepares them with vital information about the reality of the business.

The nature of educational systems such as vocational educational streams, parallel to academic education in sub-Saharan countries, vocational training through apprenticeship programmes becomes the choice for young and vibrant people when further progress in the formal academic educational system is hindered, either by financial reasons or by their academic performance (Bethlehem, 2020; Baloch, Rahim and Manzoor, 2017). Additionally, most apprenticeship programmes are not a route into formal wage employment in large or public sector enterprises. Instead, traditional apprenticeships are considered pathways to job creation or work in small, informal sector jobs. There are two classes of apprenticeship places: *traditional (informal)* apprenticeship and *modern (formal)* apprenticeship in Africa. Some researchers use the term "traditional apprenticeship training" over the "informal apprenticeship training". Over the years, traditional apprenticeship training programmes have been linked to skills transmission from parents to children, which involves close family members (Putta, 2014). Informal apprenticeship is more unrestricted than traditional apprenticeship, where apprentices sometimes come from external sources rather than family (Baloch, Rahim and Manzoor, 2017). Notwithstanding, a master artisan training informal apprentices might also train their child as a traditional apprentice.

In the late 1990s, the demand for apprenticeship programmes declined due to the economic frustrations in those years (Martin and Bok, 2015). In the 21st century, youth unemployment increased. Still, at the same time, there were significant concerns that low training demand incidence would lead to skill shortages in the future when labour demand would rise again (Martin and Bok, 2015). Therefore, modern apprenticeship training programmes are familiarised in several industry sectors (Putta, 2014; Mukata et al., 2018). These new approaches to apprenticeship training programmes are less associated with the

labour organisation along the production process. Usually, apprentice trainees only have a learning contract but no employment contract, which means there is no avenue to earn wages or stipends. However, they occasionally obtain subsidies and allowances depending on the business policies. These contracts become less cheap for the training firm. Nowadays, the share of modern apprenticeship training programmes is substantial; about 30% of the SMEs offer contemporary apprenticeship training programmes, but there are significant variations among businesses. Informal apprenticeship training refers to the process by which young learners and entrepreneurs acquire the necessary skills needed for a trade or craft in micro, small and medium enterprises. Learning and working along with an experienced craftsman is the core demand in this form of apprenticeship training. Informal apprenticeship training adds value for policymakers and experts to address critical issues by proposing a new approach (Henry, Hill, and Leitch, 2005; Matlay, 2008; Chien-Chi, 2013; Matlay, 2018). The nature of these approaches in the context of Africa views the informal apprenticeship not solely as an elementary practice or exploitation of young people and entrepreneurs as it has often been stigmatised (Abioye et al., 2017; Dzisi and Odoom, 2017; Doran et al. 2018). This training system of the informal economy has grown out of the traditional family and kinship-based apprenticeship, which has the prospect of developing (Doran et al., 2018; Liguori et al., 2019). Their argument goes beyond the neoclassical human capital and labour market concepts which perceive apprenticeship only as a contract between two players or groups.

Evidence from developed countries shows that a successful transition to modern apprenticeship systems is possible in developing countries where the institutional framework can boost incentives and benefits from apprenticeship training, make their work and profession attractive, and by ensuring public funding to finance training programmes for SMEs. Informal apprenticeship has been neglected in recent years regarding national training policies, and this resource guide attempts to shift informal apprenticeship back into the focus

of national priorities for enhancing skills and youth employment (Putta, 2014). In the past decades, some African countries have started to embark on training reforms, including informal apprenticeships. Conscious of these promising developments, the aim is to pave the way for well-informed, informed interventions and policies that will take into account traditional rules and local norms. Since developmental apprenticeship projects are very recent, the resource required to ensure business sustainability remains a "work in progress". Informal apprenticeship training is vital because they promote a set of customs, norms and traditions transmitted in the community and among people of similar trade. This is because they create the right atmosphere for informal apprenticeship to make economic meaning for both the master craftsperson and the trainee (Nübler et al., 2009). Informal apprenticeship training sometimes does not consistently achieve the right results (Doran et al 2018). These have brought about interventions that have tried to establish an entirely modern and formalised apprenticeship training, overlooking the existing traditions and norms (Liguori et al, 2019).

Many of these approaches have not yielded the expected results and have been proven too expensive to expand, cater and accommodate young entrepreneurs' desire to learn in the informal apprenticeship. This has called for formal apprenticeship training, which aims to promote the gradual improvement of an indigenous training system (Doran et al., 2018). Some earlier researchers have called for pinpointing and overcoming the weaknesses associated with the informal apprenticeship, including creating linkages with formal institutions by greater recognition of its contributions as part of the African apprenticeship training system.

2.6 Entrepreneurial Training Programmes in Universities

Training instils any skills and information to enhance students' abilities (Baloch et al., 2017). Training programmes in universities specifically enhance and upgrade people's intellectual capacity for entrepreneurship (Lombardi et al., 2017). This implies that universities' entrepreneurial training programmes are structured to help students understand their entrepreneurial skills and talent. Lombardi et al. (2017) put forward the idea that entrepreneurial training programmes in schools revolve around three primary aspects: converting knowledge into viable startup businesses, providing specialised services and community involvement, and developing curricula focused on entrepreneurship.

Given the above, elaborating on the third focal point justifies the core bases of modern-day entrepreneurial education in universities (Lombardi et al., 2017; Matlay, 2008; Ojala and heikkilä, 2011; Alexandria et al., 2014; Abioye et al., 2017). This is because entrepreneurial activities in the universities are taught through a drafted training curriculum (Lombardi et al., 2017), where teaching activities are conducted in classrooms (Ligurori et al., 2019) with the ultimate aim to support and exchange of knowledge to inspire and promote entrepreneurial activities, especially among students (Matlay, 2018).

Several kinds of research in recent years in the field of entrepreneurship have widely been centred around the impact of entrepreneurship education in universities where learning and training students to become entrepreneurs is vital (Boukamcha, 2015; Matlay, 2018; Lorz, 2011; Dzisi, and Odoom 2017; Dugassa, 2012). The focal point of these researchers has been prioritised on key thematic concepts such as; the impact of entrepreneurial education (Dzisi and Odoom, 2017; Chien-Chi, 2013, Matlay, 2008), entrepreneurial motivation (Solesvik, 2013) and entrepreneurial intention (Lorz, 2011; Dugassa, 2012; Anderson et al., 2018). These concepts have served as the fundamental basis for the recent call for an investigation by scholars in entrepreneurship, mainly centred around students in the

universities and incubatory hubs to enhance entrepreneurial activities in their trade interests (Baloch et al., 2017).

With respect to these arguments, university entrepreneurial training programmes provide students or promising entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and primary information through classroom-based programmes to inspire entrepreneurial motivation among students and develop an intent toward entrepreneurship. The core point of university entrepreneurial training programmes is to create awareness and necessary information about entrepreneurship for students to become entrepreneurs, unlike apprenticeship entrepreneurial training programmes, which establish the bases of skills and knowledge development in reality.

The literature review on how the entrepreneurial education experience of SME owners has an effect on their intention prior to starting their business. Further research on the impact of the intentions of SMEs on business start-ups primarily covers the education and experience of business owners/managers. Most studies have supported entrepreneurial education and training as probably the most vital factor in business success (Teng et al., 2011). Entrepreneurial education is fundamental for business survival (Udayanan, 2019). The intentions of SMEs are perceived as the most critical for business success (Lombardi et al., 2017; Sane, 2020). These critical factors include quality education and personal experiences (Lombardi et al., 2017). Sane (2020) stated that business capital, assets consisting of formal education, acquired knowledge, skills, and core competencies, play an essential role in business survival. (Jones et al., 2018) backed the positive influence of entrepreneurial education on business survival.

Furthermore, Mukata, Ladzani, and Visser (2018) study supported a positive relationship between entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial education level, intention, and business

survival. Scholars highlighted the vital role of business survival as the critical unit of analysis (Lombardi et al., 2017; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). An entrepreneurial education can enhance entrepreneurial capacity to deploy resources efficiently and effectively, thereby maintaining excellent returns (Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). This process requires the need for business owners to understand and seek emerging opportunities for growth and make the right decisions in a time while pursuing profit-maximising decisions.

Entrepreneurial education in the universities is evolving as an increasingly essential element of the most developing nation in innovation systems in Africa (Matlay, 2018; Abioye et al., 2017; Alexandria et al., 2014). Innovation among SMEs in Africa is a result of entrepreneurial and enterprising behaviour (Abioye et al., 2017). Several scholars have linked various patterns of information from various sources, including creativity and innovation, and spotted new business opportunities (Ojala and heikkila; 2011). The implementation of innovation within small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can play a crucial role in differentiating their performance and enhancing their competitive edge in the market among their competitors (Louise, 2018). Both innovation and entrepreneurial knowledge are fundamental elements contributing to the competitive advantage of businesses and nations worldwide (Louise, 2018). The core of innovation has both direct and indirect values that affect SMEs. In the context described, direct value refers to the immediate benefits businesses and producers gain directly from their production. In contrast, indirect value is achieved through the production process, as well as the use of substitute goods and services (Watson & McGowan, 2019). In Africa, large businesses coexist with international and newly established businesses, fostering an environment that promotes innovation (Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). On the other hand, small businesses exhibit lower levels of innovation (Watson & McGowan, 2019). This highlights the vital element of entrepreneurial

education and training and work-related learning within universities, as it enables students and industrial staff to integrate into these entrepreneurial programs.

In the field of entrepreneurial education, collaboration between universities differs based on the demands and technological advancements within mature and emerging industries. This variation is evident in networking approaches and collaboration methods to foster innovation (Lombardi et al., 2017; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). Networking among small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) significantly contributes to their innovative capabilities by exposing them to new ideas, facilitating access to resources, and promoting knowledge transfer. There are three models of innovation which is important for knowledge transfer (Abioye et al., 2017). In the context described, there are three models of innovation. The traditional model involves businesses generating, acquiring, developing, and promoting ideas, often needing the knowledge of the external source from which the knowledge is obtained. The second model is outsourcing innovation, where businesses rely on external sources to develop and implement innovations. Finally, the open innovation model combines internal and external ideas to drive business innovation.

By collaborating and engaging with customers, businesses can reduce their ignorance of customer needs and increase customer confidence, leading to a decreased risk when launching innovations in the market (Davis, 2015). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and small businesses often seek to enhance their reputation by associating with prominent organizations or academic institutions, thereby sharing risks and improving their image (Matlay, 2018).

In the context of entrepreneurial education in universities, innovation encompasses various aspects such as developing new programs, establishing stakeholder relationships, enhancing alumni relations, adopting new research approaches, implementing research

outcomes, and designing new organizational structures and governance processes (Alexandria et al., 2014). Collaborative research between academic researchers and industry players can be valuable for creativity and innovation (Ojala and Heikkila, 2011). Through their entrepreneurial education efforts, universities can offer a cost-effective resource for innovation compared to consultants. However, not all businesses are inclined to collaborate with universities for their innovation needs (Murray et al., 2018).

Entrepreneurship is considered a challenging task. Throughout the past decades, several researchers have specifically addressed the quality of entrepreneurial activities to diverse parameters in the business ecosystem, which includes entrepreneurial training, entrepreneurship education, government policies, finances, marketing dynamics, infrastructure, and cultural differences (Alan Murray et al., 2018; Matlay, 2018; Adenle, 2017; Reeta, 2016). As the population increases, one vital component is the opportunity to ensure economic growth through resilient, independent business structures for people in both quality and quantity manner (Santoso, 2017; Yitbarek et al, 2021). To ensure sustainable economic growth, countries should embrace entrepreneurship activities (Gibb, 1993). Over the years, entrepreneurs have played an essential role in national development, and the various government makes an effort in developing countries to nurture intrinsic young people to become entrepreneurs (Davis, 2015). However, if emerging start-ups are thriving to survive, it is essential to foster entrepreneurial training and education at an early stage (Irissappane and Yasodha 2014). These initiatives can be successfully implemented by promoting entrepreneurship education and training at various stages of business operations (Matlay 2018). SMEs are naturally associated with ambiguities (Majlath, Kelemen-Erdős, and Valocikova, 2019). Because of this, Masadeh (2008) argued that most SMEs often fail because entrepreneurs do not have the required training and skills to promote productivity and ensure sustainability. Even though, entrepreneurs, who have the technical competencies,

do not always have the necessary training to capitalise on their managerial and administrative capabilities required to reduce operational risk (Adenle 2017). Many governments and business owners perceive business incubators and entrepreneurship education as a dynamic training tool to promote SME activities (Elmansori, 2014; Chikandiwa et al., 2020).

2.7 Explorative nature of Apprenticeship training

Many entrepreneurs are linked with informal apprenticeship benefits (Liguori et al., 2019). Doran et al. (2018) argued that some entrepreneurs used the informal apprenticeship approach to exploit and utilise other people in Africa for their selfish means and purposes. Some researchers have also defined the act as victimising and mistreating someone (Baloch, Rahim, and Manzoor, 2017). The informal apprenticeship is often perceived as exploitative in Africa because young and aspiring entrepreneurs work in a workshop for minimal or no compensation and for a considerable time (Liguori et al., 2019). This is because the apprenticeship nature is seen as cheap labour in a business and is considered selfish behaviour by most entrepreneurs. Some researchers have considered the informal apprenticeship approach unfair treatment and abuse of apprentices' labour service (Doran et al. (2018). The arguments above would hold if apprentices joined the workshop merely as workers. However, in the dynamism of the informal apprenticeship, apprentices acquire the necessary skills and learn a trade by providing labour services in exchange for receiving training and skills (Bjursell and Rebecka 2018). Their effort into business productivity compensates for the training cost incurred by the master craftspersons or the actual entrepreneurs.

The apprenticeship duration needs to be proportionate to the time it takes to develop as a competent artisan and must meet the balance of the financial arrangement (Liguori et al., 2019). At the end of the apprenticeship period, the master entrepreneurs must have achieved the training investment; otherwise, they would not be known to enter another apprenticeship

agreement. Informal apprenticeships can also be considered exploitative when entrepreneurs have skills they are committed to training (Doran et al., 2018; Adenle, 2017). Accommodating apprentices for a longer duration without passing the vital skills of the trainee is considered exploitative practice (Bjursell and Rebecka (2018).

Table 2.3 Key weakness of informal apprenticeship

Subjects	Weakness	Reasons	Potential Policy
Quality of apprenticeship training	Lack of dynamism and access to new approaches or technology	Traditional skills transmission does not respond to creativity or change.	-Establish links between larger businesses or formal training institutions to enhance business collaboration. -Provide constant skills upgrade programmes for master and apprentices
Gender of informal or traditional apprenticeship	occupational segregation, which restricts opportunities for both male and female entrepreneurs.	Gender patterns are based on beliefs. Male and female dominance in a specific occupation.	-Encourage most businesses to change recruitment approaches related to apprenticeships, and empower young female entrepreneurs to apply for apprenticeships in male occupations or trades and vice versa.
Child labour	Children below the labour age pursue	-Inadequate enforcement of minimal	-Maintain existing rule by stricter enforcement and raising

	<p>apprenticeship training, and this means that youth are engaged as apprentices below the legal working age.</p>	<p>age law.</p> <p>-The country's inadequate availability of secondary education, higher rate of school drop-out without alternatives.</p>	<p>awareness among businesses.</p> <p>-Invest in pre-vocational training, increased secondary education.</p>
<p>Recognition of contributions and skills by employers</p>	<p>Recognition of skills and effort is limited to a few people</p>	<p>Approaches to apprenticeship are limited because skills recognition is traditionally known to the master artisan's network</p>	<p>Focus on introducing credentials by business associations or formal training centres with credibility and broader outreach</p>

Source: Researcher's deduction

Some researchers have argued that some master entrepreneurs hide the essential skills of apprentices in the workplace by keeping specific critical skills to themselves (Esllyn et al. 2007). These issues prevent trainee apprentices from leaving the workshop as they have not yet acquired all skills relevant to the trade. Measures now in place to avoid exploitative forms of informal apprenticeship are incorporated into the social connection of customers and neighbouring businesses in Africa (Liguori et al., 2019). In this manner, most entrepreneurs are recognised for exploiting their apprentices and endangering their good reputation in the business environment. This has caused likely negatively impacted their customer base, future support from other businesses, and future demand for an apprenticeship. Most researchers and policymakers have raised alarming concerns about addressing policies to counter

exploitative practices that need to strengthen the enforcement of informal apprenticeship contracts. This involves executing monitoring visits and receiving feedback or establishing avenues apprentices or trainees can raise a complaint if they do not receive sufficient training.

The formal apprenticeship approach follows a set of written rules such as training laws, regulations, and policies (Adenle, 2017; Baloch, Rahim, and Manzoor, 2017). These formal rules are executed by formal mechanisms such as the labour court, cooperative bargaining agreements, education institutions, chambers of commerce, and labour inspectors. The formal approach of apprenticeship training programmes is executed through the lenses of institutions and acknowledges that it is embedded in a society's formal and informal institutions (Matlay, 2018). Formal apprenticeship training legislation exists and implements vividly in many African countries. The number of current apprentices learning under formal apprenticeship regulations is minimal (Baloch, Rahim, and Manzoor, 2017).

In several countries, the privatisation of state enterprises in the 1980s and 90s triggered a drastic decline in a formal apprenticeship as large private enterprises considered formal apprenticeship too expensive or felt that training facilities were outmoded in Africa (Adenle, 2017). In Africa, apprentices' demand for formal apprenticeship is low due to strict entry requirements and usually low labour market absorption rates (OECD, 2008; Adams and Johanson, 2004; Atchoarena and Delluc, 2002).

Formal apprenticeship training has attracted considerable interest from academic and political arenas because of its credibility as a panacea for economic drivers across countries (Henry 2013). Formal apprenticeship training has developed a legitimate podium for research interests, highly recognised as higher education programme (Matlay 2018; Eslyn et al. 2007). However, it is not surprising with the persistent increase in research conducted in these areas, government interest, workshops, and symposia are organised to exchange ideas to establish

acceptable practices for policy initiatives for formal apprenticeship in recent times (O'Leary 2017; Storey 2008). Government policies often influence business activities and operations (Elkan, 1988; Adenle, 2017). Formal apprenticeship training with strategic policies is believed to enhance entrepreneurs' intentions to operate and improve their performance in a specific country, especially in developing countries (Colton 1990). However, most sub-Saharan African countries are associated with complicated taxation problems, high political tensions, corruption, and a lack of underlined policies associated with present-day entrepreneurs, which hinders the encouragement of apprenticeships (Hussain and Yaqub, 2010). In view of this, the role of formal apprentice approaches such as mentorship and coaching is a crucial element in a person's life and their vocational development.

Coaching and Mentorship: Coaching is often term as the essential measures to provide the necessary help to individuals, students, SMEs, groups, and organisations through some assistantship activities to achieve success in their endeavours (Jamison, 2018). Baloch, Rahim, and Manzoor (2017) also described coaching as a set of techniques adopted to casually transmit learning skills, support, and other beneficial endeavours relating to a vocation or work from an expert or tutor. In the context of training activities through mentorship programmes, Bjursell and Rebecka (2018) suggested the demand for mentorship and coaching are mostly the same based on the approaches related to problem-oriented scenarios, especially in the workplace. This is because Bjursell and Rebecka's (2018) findings indicated that individuals with mentors could justify the superiority of learning fast in the workplace. The concept of coaching and mentorship has evolved quickly at various workplaces as a justifiable process of learning (Baloch et al., 2018). Mentorship and coaching give entrepreneurs a genuine relationship to be understudied as they are being instilled appropriately in the right directions either by their mentors or coach to visionaries of their business. The essence of mentorship and coaching is essential in modern-day business

and operational activities as they assist entrepreneurs with valuable information, support, and direction (Robinson, Vander-Pal, and Nhat-Hoang, 2017).

Entrepreneurs' involvement in mentorships and coaching training programmes promotes both the 'mentor' and the 'mentee' in terms of maximum job satisfaction to continue learning (Baloch et al., 2018; Robinson et al., 2017). In view of this, the role of mentorship and coaching is a very crucial element in a person's life and their vocational development as well. These provide a podium for both the mentors and mentees to critically understand their business operating activities and adopt measures to mitigate risk emerging. Martin and Bok (2015) suggested that it is vital for entrepreneurs to exhibit traits that show business success, having an emblem of self-identity to look up to and mitigate risk. These emblems of self-identity in this context serve as a medium to attract entrepreneurs, increase innovation, enhance communication and marketing skills, and improve entrepreneurs' performances.

However, despite the vital role mentorship and coaching programmes impact entrepreneurs, they are also associated with potential setbacks. Ehrich, Hansford, and Tennent (2014) researched the impact of mentorship on students in terms of their academic performance, and their findings indicated a negative relationship between these students and their academic mentors by approximately 43 percent. However, Martin and Bok (2015) also argued that mentorships and coaching are time demanding. This is because the right mentors and mentees may not appropriately be matched, leading to an insufficient exchange of knowledge and skills.

2.8 Formal Vs Informal Apprenticeship Training

Over the years, emerging debates have evolved around the appropriate apprenticeship trainings, which has sparked the argument of whether apprenticeship can be taught. Interestingly, several kinds of apprenticeship research have been done (Colette, Frances and Claire, 2005). However, in the 1990s, Gibb (1993) suggested that several attempts have been

made by different governments and organisations worldwide in what is recently termed as 'entrepreneurship education and training' taught in schools and universities. Surprisingly, many research findings have shown a positive relationship between entrepreneurship training and SMEs' performance (Henry, Hill, and Leitch, 2005; Matlay, 2008; Chien-Chi,2013; Matlay, 2018).

In the context of the impact of entrepreneurship education and training, Matlay (2018) observed that entrepreneurship education taught in schools is most likely to change participants' perceptions, attitudes, and behaviour. Matlay (2018) further argued that various entrepreneurship education taught in classrooms contributes to developing generic and specific decision-making skills of promising and future entrepreneurs. However, taught entrepreneurship training could help represent ideas that will eventually stimulate entrepreneurs to deliver creative ideas (Watson and McGowan 2019). Given these, it can be argued that taught entrepreneurship training equips learners with the core knowledge needed to create jobs with much primary focus on developing a positive attitude, perception, and behaviours deemed necessary to achieve success.

Table 2.4 Difference between formal and informal apprenticeship

Elements	Informal	Formal
Training Agreement	Mostly verbal contract between the master artisan and the apprentice's parents or guardians.	A written contract which clearly specifies the conditions and expectations between employer, apprentice and sometimes training centres
Occupational competence	Broad skills that enable mastery of a trade	Broad skills that enable mastery of a trade

Age	Mostly the case, the risk of child labour	Mostly the case, but sometimes age regulations are clearly specified
Place of training	Entirely work-based training complemented by informal training plans.	Training is a workplace-based approach and is followed by courses in training centres through formal curricula or training plans.
Costs of apprenticeship	The master artisan invests time and resources while the apprentice provides labour services or fees	The employer invests time and resources (including apprentice's wage), apprentices provide labour service, government provides financial support.

Source: Inspired by Timmons 1987; Bird 1995; Chien-Chi,2013; Matlay, 2018

Interestingly, some earlier researchers and authors, such as Timmons (1987), believed entrepreneurship could not be ascertained through formal education to some extent. He further argued that entrepreneurial activities could be learned from one's personal experience. However, Bird (1995) later supported the view that entrepreneurship can be nurtured and fostered as a whole. The argument of these earlier authors contradicts the findings of recent research. Despite the disparities in their views, Puta (2014) also believed that entrepreneurship training could transcend from parent to children without formal education or training. With this in mind, when questions are posed to entrepreneurs who did not have any entrepreneurship training on whether entrepreneurship activities can be taught, they may perhaps say "no." such entrepreneurs will probably have the notion that such entrepreneurship cannot be taught but can be transpired through observation from others.

On the other hand, if similar questions are posed to entrepreneurship professors, business consultants, and SMEs undertaking entrepreneurship training, there will probably be a different answer. These disparities demand a review of both taught and untaught

entrepreneurship training in the business ecosystem. Besides, based on the underpinned assumptions, the growth of entrepreneurial education and training concepts at all levels, there seem to be some level equivalence traits (Henry et al., 2015; Matlay, 2018). Yet still, the confusion emanating from whether taught and untaught entrepreneurship is vital for review.

2.9 The need for Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurship Training

Entrepreneurship education and training have been widely acknowledged as valuable tools for enhancing skills and innovation strategies across various business operations (Nkirina, 2010; Anderson, Marques, and Marques, 2018). The importance of entrepreneurship education and business training cannot be underestimated, as they play a crucial role in equipping entrepreneurs with the necessary knowledge and skills to start, expand, and sustain their businesses (Alsheikh, 2009; Swanson & Morrison, 2010). Business incubators, in particular, provide essential training, counselling, and advisory services to support entrepreneurs in their journey. Entrepreneurship training activities have also been found to assist SMEs and young entrepreneurs in capitalizing on opportunities and adopting new strategies (Ardichvili et al., 2003; Yitbarek et al, 2021). Therefore, entrepreneurship education and training are vital components in creating a conducive environment for business success, especially in developing countries where business failures are prevalent.

To enhance businesses' competitive advantage, considerable resources should be directed towards entrepreneurship training and education in many countries. Governments and international organizations have already initiated investments and policies to provide essential training and education for startups and existing SMEs (ILO report, 2015; YALI report, 2010; Trend, 2019). The acceptance and implementation of entrepreneurship concepts and initiatives have been increasing, aiming to stimulate business startups and generate new employment opportunities, particularly for young individuals (Boukamcha, 2015; Liguori et

al., 2019). Addressing unemployment challenges in developing economies requires a focus on entrepreneurship development programs that provide job seekers, including graduates, with the necessary knowledge and skills (Visser, 2018; Ndofirepi & Rambe, 2017). Technical and vocational entrepreneurship training programs can significantly promote entrepreneurial knowledge and skills, thus empowering individuals and fostering economic independence.

Similarly, Lorz (2011) analysed, from a mixed-method study of 272 students chosen from universities, the significant role that entrepreneurship education plays in fostering students' interest in entrepreneurship. According to Lorz (2011), entrepreneurial education and training are instrumental in equipping individuals with the idea regarding business, providing them with the needed perspicuity and skills for entrepreneurship and creating opportunities for job creation. Louise, (2018) deemed that entrepreneurs' decision-making abilities are influenced by training and education. The significant influence of education on students' inclination towards entrepreneurship and its impact on employment generation has been a prominent topic of study for researchers (Abioye et al., 2017; Louise, 2018). Moreover, in order to comprehend the discussion surrounding entrepreneurial education and training, it was essential to examine two key facets of education in relation to entrepreneurship: higher education and the field of entrepreneurial education.

Diverse literature contains numerous theories and perspectives on higher education and entrepreneurial education, which encompasses the involvement of undergraduate students in entrepreneurial growth. The subsequent sections will delve into the significance of higher education and entrepreneurship education in nurturing individuals' intentions towards entrepreneurship. In summary, entrepreneurial education and training have emerged as crucial parameter to foster business growth, promote job creation, and equip individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in the entrepreneurial landscape. Governments,

organizations, and research findings emphasise the vital role of investing in entrepreneurship development to address unemployment challenges and stimulate economic independence.

2.10 socio-economic benefit of entrepreneurship training

Over the years, several countries have gone through substantial budget deficits, and most of these deficits relate to an internal debt due to poor management or a high employment rate (Sheriff and Muffatto 2015). From 2008 to 2009, the world was hit with an economic recession that affected both small and large businesses. There was a rapid fall in oil prices, an increase in unemployment, business failures, increase in government borrowing, and among others (Stankovska, Josimovski, and Edwards 2016). The recession within this period mainly affected the financial sector, directly or indirectly, impacting businesses struggling to survive. This accounted for several business failures leading to a high level of the unemployment rate. For example, between the 2008 to 2009 recession periods, the UK's unemployment rate increased to over 2.6 million. The whole of Europe saw a devastating increase in the unemployment rate of over 20% (JICA, 2009; Chamberlin, 2010). United States of America's budget deficit also increased to 6% of the country's GDP, Africa was not exempted from the crisis, with a declining investment of about 2.6% in 2009 (JICA, 2009).

The recent explosion of the COVID-19 cases at the beginning of the 2020 calendar year across the globe created a hindrance for most SMEs regarding free trade movement since most borders were closed (World bank report 2020). As most developing nations were oppressed by the pandemic, developing areas like Sub-Saharan African countries whose economic activity depends excessively on tourism sector engagement, aviation, production, manufacturing, exportation, and many more are faced with economic dips predicted to impact at the close of the calendar year (Dirk, 2020; United Nation report 2020). This is because most businesses (small or large) are deemed to encounter fundamental inefficiencies in their

daily operational activities (Dirk, 2020). This affected consumers' purchasing power due to the declining demand for goods and services, making businesses vulnerable to operate and produce. Even though businesses with huge reserves will slightly survive, they will temporarily run at a loss or lay off workers.

In the past decades, several recessions have triggered various governments of different countries to embark on different strategic plans to ensure an effective, sustainable economy through diversification (Chamberlin, 2010). The recent economic recession within these periods demands core interest from governments, institutions, and scholars worldwide to devise strategic policies and entrepreneurial training initiatives to ensure most businesses survive (Bethlehem, 2020). In view of this, most governments, researchers, and institutions are compelled to avoid the dreadful outcomes of such issues associated with recessions and pandemics over the years by developing and undertaking strategic measures that aim to curtail such unforeseen circumstances which pose a threat to vibrant and robust economies. This strategic plan demands entrepreneurial training to ensure that most business owners are equipped with the necessary skills and core competence to strive through such periods. With this in mind, Mai and Gan (2007) argued that for businesses to survive, emphasis should be placed on their entrepreneurial training, which is essential to understand the two key thematic areas; the external and internal environmental implications that affect the intentions of entrepreneurs to strive for success. Most institutions and governmental organisations have commissioned and invested immensely to generate an integral measure to promote entrepreneurship in higher institutions and entrepreneurial training centres across the globe (Adenle, 2017). Such policies and initiatives are seen as the backbone of most economies.

2.11 Conclusion

To conclude this editorial review chapter, it is essential to understand entrepreneurship education and training growth. These two concepts, entrepreneurship training and education are a global phenomenon posited well in several academic pieces of literature. Recent research findings highlight critical strategies to improve and develop entrepreneurial training and education programmes. Many scholars have acknowledged the influential role entrepreneurial training plays in transforming entrepreneurs (Watson and McGowan 2019; Matlay 2008).

Apprenticeship training addresses the restrictions placed on classroom learning. This also help exposes entrepreneurs to the practical world to understand their business or trade area. From this chapter, many researchers have argued that coaching is a set of techniques adopted to casually transmit learning skills, support, and other beneficial endeavours relating to a vocation or work from an expert or tutor. Furthermore, coaching and mentorship justify the process of learning quickly at the workplace with valuable information, support, and direction. This makes mentorships and coaching valuable and are sometimes perceived to be time demanding; this is because the right mentors and mentees may not appropriately be matched, leading to an insufficient exchange of knowledge and skills. Another essential element is the incubatory business services; they provide the necessary training, which helps entrepreneurs start, expand, and sustain their businesses, while entrepreneurship education triggers individuals' interest in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial training, education, coaching, and mentorships taught and untaught entrepreneurial training influence the intentions of SMEs.

This has called for in-depth studies on other components of training to understand the impact on job creation. Many journal reviews on training and education regarding

entrepreneurship are subjected to three key elements; i) training and job creation, ii) training and intention iii) training and sustainability.

To understand entrepreneurial training and apprenticeship programmes, it is vital to understand such training's essential role in entrepreneurs' intentions. Furthermore, Enterprise education is preferably used in areas related to the business realm, such as work-related learning, action, experimental learning, and entrepreneurial education. Enterprise education covers an immense scope of acquiring knowledge, initiating, and developing social and business skills. Whiles entrepreneurship education focuses on applying the mindset of setting up a venture in an entrepreneurial ecosystem.

The literature review in this chapter also revealed that university entrepreneurial training programmes provide students or promising entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and primary information through classroom-based learning to inspire entrepreneurial motivation among students and to develop an intent toward entrepreneurship. Also, deduction from literature reviews reveals that university entrepreneurial educations are summarised into three main categories: Entrepreneurial Awareness, Entrepreneurship for Start-ups, and the dynamic nature of Entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship education plays a crucial role in cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset among students, helping them align their expectations with the realities of the business world and fostering job creation (Watson & McGowan, 2019). It encompasses both formal and informal approaches, including structured educational processes and real-world experiences, which contribute significantly to the development of entrepreneurial skills and attitudes in students within and beyond the university setting (Matlay, 2011). Academic research in this context can take various forms, such as collaborative research, contractual engagements, consulting, and informal activities like networking and advisory roles with

industry professionals (Sane, 2020). Universities are driven by the entrepreneurial environment to enhance the overall student experience, leading to the implementation of programs like research exchanges and internships that facilitate mobility and collaboration between academia and the external business landscape (Sane, 2020; Liguori et al., 2019; Alan Murray et al., 2018; Matlay, 2018; Lombardi et al., 2017). An entrepreneurial university also supports the international mobility of students and staff (Gibb et al., 2014).

It is essential to understand how entrepreneurial education and training impact entrepreneurs' intentions to understand apprenticeship training programmes and their impact on entrepreneurs. Since the scope of apprentice organisation takes a different scope from entrepreneurship training and education, from this chapter, it is not surprising how most research findings justify that individuals with just entrepreneurship training or education are more likely to have a positive intention toward job creation. Several types of research have neglected the vital role of apprenticeship training in entrepreneurs' intentions. The next chapter will further give a vivid understanding of multiple issues in entrepreneurial training that affect SMEs' entrepreneurial intention in Africa precisely Ghana and Kenya.

Chapter 3: SMEs Activities In Africa

This chapter aims to provide an explanation of different entrepreneurship concepts and delve into the various issues related to entrepreneurial training that impact the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs. As discussed in the first chapter, there is limited research available on the effects of entrepreneurial training on SMEs. Only a few researchers have attempted to explore the different aspects of entrepreneurial training and its influence on the perceptions and intentions of actual entrepreneurs operating businesses in Sub-Saharan African countries (Davis,2015; Louise, 2018; Adenle, 2017; Amato et., al 2018). This lack of research makes it challenging to fully comprehend the nature of entrepreneurial intentions within the African context. This makes it extremely difficult to understand the nature of entrepreneurial intentions on African soil. To understand this gap, this thesis will focus on understanding the vital roles of entrepreneurial training on the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in Ghana and Kenya.

It is crucial to acknowledge that SMEs play a significant role in the economies of developing countries (Adenle, 2017; Owusu, 2014; Boso et al., 2018). These small and medium-sized enterprises are often the backbone of economic development, providing employment opportunities and contributing to economic growth. However, at the heart of every SME, the entrepreneur drives its direction and determines its success or failure. Some researchers have argued that the nature of SMEs activity is complicated, which demands that institutions incorporate entrepreneurial training programs to bridge the gap between the needs of SMEs and the entrepreneurial training (Kiggundu, 2002; Hunter and Lean, 2018; Jurie and Botha, 2010), notably highlight on how their intentions influence their activities. Several institutions, universities, and technical schools in Africa are continually developing entrepreneurship models to equip students with the necessary skills for entrepreneurialism (Sheriff and Muffatto, 2015), and other institutions have promoted apprenticeship

programmes as an essential needs for promising and young entrepreneurs (Baloch, Rahim, and Manzoor, 2017).

3.1 Nature of SMEs In Sub-Saharan Africa

The promotion of SME activities in Sub-Saharan African regions promotes economic growth. It transforms the crucial role in the development of entrepreneurial education and training programmes since the early years of independence in the 1950s. The vital role of international organisations and institutions such as the United Nations, World Bank, and African Development Bank in the Saharan African region, especially in the field of entrepreneurship and technical training, cannot be overlooked (World Bank report 2019; World Employment Social Outlook, 2019; United Nation report 2020; African Development Bank, 2016). These institutions and government organisations in these regions have commissioned necessary measures to promote entrepreneurship in higher institutions and entrepreneurial training centres across (Adenle, 2017).

There are no clear definitions for SMEs as it varies from country to country. It is usually based on some parameters, thus either the size of the economy, policies, and regulations existing in the specified country (Safura, 2017). SMEs' significant contribution to global economies can not be overlooked (Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Pearl, 2018). The nature of Entrepreneurship is perceived as an escape route (Amoah and Amoah, 2018) and a means to reduce the persistent unemployment rate in Sub-Saharan African countries (Shonubi and Taiwo, 2013; Majlath, 2019). Some steps have been initiated to enhance, promote, and integrate technology and innovations across the region to encourage SMEs and entrepreneurialism (Boso, Debrah, and Amankwah-Amoah, 2018).

Engagement in SMEs is described as the prominent way to create jobs and reduce the unemployment rate across the globe (Alakaleek, 2019; Corbett, 2007), source of income and revenue (Dankwa, 2018; Khalifa 2019) and economic development (Adenle, 2017; Putta

2014). However, Sthembiso, Nkwinika, and Mashau (2019) argued that entrepreneurial activity might not necessarily solve persistent unemployment issues, even though it can reduce unemployment. But entrepreneurial education and training among potential students and entrepreneurs at various stages within the business environment remain pivotal to promoting job creation through appropriate financial and regulatory interventions (Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Alakaleek, 2019).

The pride of SME activities has been tagged as an efficient role in creating jobs and the catalyst for global economic growth engines (Cant and Wiid, 2016). The 2018 world Bank report indicated that the significant role of SMEs' contributions could not be overlooked as it contributes over 90% of the Sub-Saharan region's private business and more than 50% of employment and GDP. Most countries often perceive SMEs as the core for innovation, economic growth, and job creation opportunities. For instance, in South Africa, SMEs contribute about 57% to GDP and account for over 90% of the business, with over 60 % employment of the country's labour force in the region (Cant and Wiid, 2016). SMEs in Ghana cannot be underestimated as well, as the sector employs about 85% of the manufacturing labour force across the country in both rural and urban settlements (Amoah and Amoah, 2018).

Over the past decades, most Sub-Saharan African countries have adopted diverse strategies to boost the entrepreneurial skills of SMEs (Nafukho and Muyia 2009). Many countries viewed the promotion of SMEs and entrepreneurial activities as an essential catalyst to promote growth with strategic policies. Entrepreneurs and SMEs have played a key vital role in addressing the most unemployment crisis in most developing countries (Hruby, 2019). However, the role of SMEs' contribution to economic growth in developing countries cannot be underrated, and several setbacks affect undiscovered abilities to capitalise upon their full potential to achieve great satisfaction. Some researchers have argued that SMEs ' activities

are hampered by numerous factors that hinder their operational capacity. These hindrances evolve around management, skills and innovation, technology, legislation, and marketing (Quartey and Abor, 2010; Nafukho and Muya, 2015; Souitaris, Zerbinati, and Al-Laham, 2007). These constraints demotivate people's interest in SMEs. Yet still, a substantial number of studies seek to investigate the impact of entrepreneurial training and education on students in some selected African countries as case studies (Yabashaija and Katono, 2011; Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Shonubi and Taiwo, 2013; O'leary 2017) with limited interest on actual or real entrepreneurs in the region (Davis,2015; Louise, 2018).

SMEs' nature turns to attract highly motivated entrepreneurs, yet their desire is limited to competing with more prominent firms in their industry. However, most advisory support needed by SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa is relatively high, and such consulting firms are not equipped with strategic managerial solutions (Lorz, 2011). Kayanula and Quartey (2000) argued that SMEs are trained by several institutions and different advisory services either at a cost or already paid by the government. Yet, SMEs' ability to compete or sustain is a huge skill gap. These setbacks are based on some critical factors because most entrepreneurs do not have a clear idea of their business idea (Rachmawan, Lizar and Mangundjaya 2015), cannot afford training costs, or see no vital need to upgrade skills (Cooney 2012).

3.2 SMES and Economic growth

Henry, Hill, and Leitch (2017) argued that the acknowledged accolades attributed to entrepreneurial activity are more than a trend. It provides a platform for technological innovation and changes in our natural and business environment. Indeed, it is not surprising that most institutions and policymakers acknowledge the significant impact of entrepreneurship on economies of different countries (Nwangwu, 2007; Safura, 2017). They attribute the awareness of entrepreneurship to job creation and the versatile nature of SMEs (Henry et al., 2005) and how entrepreneurship programs taught in schools create the

awareness to create jobs (Murray et al., 2018). The outlook of several research findings for the past decades agrees that significant health impacts entrepreneurship to the economy (Minniti and Levesque, 2008; Rachmawan, Lizar, and Mangundjaya, 2015; Doran, McCarthy, and O'Connor, 2018). Entrepreneurship gained global attention for its immense contribution to economic coupled with social development.

Entrepreneurship on the scoreboard is known for its diversity in nature, associated with a wide range of traits of individuals from different backgrounds (Byrne et al., 2016). Entrepreneurship has attracted global attention and is still being scrutinised in research because of its job creation traits that contribute to the national development of different economies (Doran et al., 2018). In view of this, Job creation measures the level of entrepreneurial activity in the economy (Safura, 2017). Several findings from diverse research indicate that social influencers such as family, childhood experience, role models (Rachmawan et al., 2015; Lorz, 2011) and demographic characteristics such as marital status, educational levels, assets, and ethnicity (Doran et al., 2018) has the tendency to negatively or positively trigger the choice for self-employment.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in utilizing resources, particularly raw materials that may generate little foreign earnings for a country, preventing wastage (Amoah & Amoah, 2018). The definitions of SMEs vary among countries, organizations, and researchers based on factors such as size, assets, sales, and operational purpose (Hosseini, Banihashemi, Chileshe, 2016; Piperopoulos, 2016). In developing countries, SMEs constitute approximately 90 percent of all businesses operating in rural and urban areas (Amoah & Amoah, 2018).

The 2018 world Bank report indicated that SMEs contribute to over 90% of private businesses in Sub-Saharan Africa and contribute to more than 50% of employment and GDP

in most African countries. Most SMEs are often perceived as the core for innovation, economic growth, and job creation opportunity by most countries. Several criteria can be used to define SMEs' characteristics in most developing countries (Fishers and Reuber, 2000). Over the years, SMEs is believed to be the engine of most developing economies. In recent years, the concept of entrepreneurship as the key to developing most countries is always attracting scholars' interest and policymakers across the globe (Spencer and Gomez, 2004). Besides the crucial role SMEs play in addressing unemployment issues in Africa, Government institutions and NGOs developed an interest in entrepreneurship in recent years (Sánchez-Escobedo et al., 2011).

Entrepreneurship is widely acknowledged as a crucial catalyst for economic growth in developing countries. SMEs play a vital and prominent role in job creation, improving living standards, and increasing income levels, especially in African nations (Seth & Alfred, 2018). The International Monetary Fund's 2019 report highlights the rapid economic growth of countries like Ethiopia, Rwanda, Ghana, and Kenya in Sub-Saharan Africa. For instance, the international trade centre's 2016 report shows that SMEs in Ghana, primarily individual business owners, account for approximately 85% of businesses and contribute around 70% to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Similarly, the Kenya Central Bank's 2017 report reveals that SMEs make up 98% of all businesses in Kenya.

These statistics underscore the significant presence and contribution of SMEs to the economies of these nations. Policymakers and stakeholders need to recognise the vital role of SMEs in fostering economic development and implement supportive measures to nurture their growth and sustainability. Furthermore, a report by the Kenya Central Bank in 2017 also revealed 98% of all businesses are SMEs. Over the past decade, the Kenyan government invested tremendously in female entrepreneurial training with the idea that such an initiative would encourage the most vibrant female participants to create their own businesses

(Nafukho and Helen 2010). The Government of Ghana perceives SMEs' role as the drivers of the economy (Bamfo, Asiedu-Appiah, and Oppong-Boakye, 2015). The African Centre for Economic Transformation 2012 perceived Kenya as one of the fastest and best-performing countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. Rwanda's economy is a mostly informal business and predominately dominated by self-employed SMEs in both trade and Agriculture (Malunda and Musana 2012).

Individuals or Self-employed business categories often own most SMEs. This group consists of a more significant portion of the those employed in most developing countries that comprise family members who do not receive wages but are actively involved in the business's day-to-day activities (Owusu-ansah, 2012). SMEs in most sub-Saharan African countries are more labour intensive and demand a low capital cost to operate than large firms (Kinya et al., 2018). Over the years, most governments and NGOs have encouraged entrepreneurship training programs to develop a positive attitude among SMEs to become self-reliant (Nafukho and Muya 2009). Most governments have realised that the Contribution of SMEs that had been in operating for decades have some growth potential, which demands a particular focus on training and business advisory services.

3.3 Challenges SMEs Failures in Sub-Saharan Africa

Establishing a business in Africa comes with uncertainties and ambiguity, such as infrastructure, policies, inadequate training and disasters (Majlath, Kelemen-Erdős, and Valocikova, 2019). However, not all business management students have the intrinsic desire to develop a positive intention towards self-employment. This is because studies conducted by Shonubi and Taiwo (2013) on Nigerian graduate students suggest that self-employed graduates with no formal education in management module(s) background develop a positive intention to successfully manage their business and thrive through difficult periods. Owusu-Ansah, (2012) also investigated how entrepreneurial training in tertiary institutions in Ghana

over the past decades was influencing the entrepreneurial intention to create jobs and employment. Their study revealed entrepreneurial training and education influence the intentions of students to create jobs.

Sustaining business in business in African countries poses a significant challenge to many entrepreneurs concerning the ability to utilise the available resources (Chinomona et al., 2020).

Most formal sectors in Sub-Saharan African countries cannot accommodate the graduate and unemployed active labour force's high growth across various countries (Brahima, 2019; Adenle, 2017; Freddy, 2019). Most people are compelled to engage in self-employment ventures to make a living (Amoah and Amoah 2018). Most individuals who engage in entrepreneurial activities do not have the intrinsic desire to engage in job creation ventures but are compelled to because of the calamity of not being employed in the cooperate world after graduating (Owusu-Ansah, 2012). The persistent collapse of business in sub-Saharan Africa is of great concern to many governments; this has encouraged most of them to promote entrepreneurial training to help curb these issues to promote business sustainability (Nwangwu, 2007; Jones et., al 2018). However, David (2015) suggested that if a business collapses, it does not necessarily mean the business is entirely out of operation but may be linked to the continuous loss in income or reduction in productivity (Ucbasaran, Westhead, and Wright, 2009; Short et al. 2010). Some other authors have attributed SMEs' failure in Africa to vastly on lack of entrepreneurial training (Mukata, Ladzani, and Visser 2018; Nafukho and Helen 2010). Jones et al. (2018) suggest that most SMEs are prone to fail within three to 5 years of business operation. This is because most business owners do not have the required managerial skills (Chinomona et al., 2020; Davis, 2015), needed entrepreneurial training and education knowledge (Yabashaija and Katono, 2011; Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Shonubi and Taiwo, 2013; O'leary 2017), and positive entrepreneurial

intentions and capacities (Mang'unyi et al. 2018; Chinomona et al., 2020) to ensure their business is thriving and sustainable.

3.4 Training Initiatives in Sub-Saharan Africa

Africa is one of the fastest-growing economies globally, yet it is coupled with significant unemployment challenges (Adenle, 2017). Indigenous African entrepreneurs can improve vastly in productivity and managerial capacity to expand territories (Shonubi and Taiwo, 2013). Several inefficiencies have often stimulated the argument for entrepreneurship education and training on the African soil over the years. This is because several governments have hugely invested in entrepreneurship training activities, especially in most sub-Saharan African countries, to address the rising unemployment rate (world youth report, 2018). A distinction between research on entrepreneurial training conducted in the context of sub-Saharan African countries has mainly focused on the general principles (Nafukho and Helen, 2010), strategies and theoretical approach to create jobs (Abioye et al., 2017) and parameters of small business failures (Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Makwembere and Pooe, 2020).

Some researchers have attributed African entrepreneurs' gradual success to personal traits such as demographic traits, behavioural patterns, core competencies, and social status (Adenle, 2017; Nkirina, 2010; Nafukho and Helen, 2010). However, other research studies also analysed the relevance based on diverse environmental factors such as institutions, political, economic, and financial structural capacities of the entrepreneurialism in the business ecosystem (Kiggundu, 2002; Kuada, 2015; Makwembere and Pooe, 2020). Furthermore, entrepreneurship training and education are essential, but most individuals tend to overlook the importance of such training offered on business development (Adenle 2017; Chikandiwa et al., 2020).

In recent years, sub-Saharan African countries have seen several public engagements from different entrepreneurship training initiatives across the world. For example, in 2010,

the United States President Barack Obama's commissioned the Youth African Leadership Initiative (YALI). The training initiative was structured to spur business and entrepreneurship growth through a comprehensive six-week training package for young entrepreneurs (YALI report, 2010). Since 2014, over 4400 entrepreneurial leaders within Sub-Saharan African regions from the ages of 25 to 35 have immensely benefited from the training (YALI, 2019). The YALI has established proven records of enhancing innovation and skills in various participating countries in Sub-Saharan African regions (Adenle, 2017). Some researchers have argued that the promotion of such entrepreneurship training has helped address the persistent unemployment rate's critical issues on African soil (Kiggundu, 2002; Kuada, 2015; Adenle, 2017; Makwembere and Pooe, 2020). Given this, most Sub-Saharan African entrepreneurs will have the podium to hone the skills and edge to support developmental progress in the region. Furthermore, the International Labour Organisation (ILO) reports that attempts have been initiated to help provide specific technical training for entrepreneurs across Sub-Saharan African countries over the decades (ILO, 2015). Over the years, ILO has partnered with the world bank, African Development Bank (ADB), and United Nations (UN) to structure training projects to address issues relating to employment networks in the business environment (Trends, 2019). These training initiatives were designed to provide entrepreneurs with business advisory services, capacity building through apprenticeship schemes, business development services, and opportunities to create jobs (ILO, 2019).

Also, the Mastercard foundation, over the years, has initiated several measures to curb youth unemployment in Sub-Saharan Africa (Reeta, 2016). Reeta further explained that even for individuals who have access to formal employment, the majority struggle to make a decent life. In 2015, the Mastercard foundation underpinned a five years initiative, "Economic Opportunity for Youth," in collaboration with various governments and organisations in Sub-Saharan to provide a holistic approach to address three critical issues in

the business ecosystems: 1. "training, skills development, and education," 2. "opportunities that exist in the market" and 3. "financial services and education" (MasterCard foundation report 2015). These five-year initiatives were designed to enhance necessary skills, encourage experiential learning, link market opportunities, and promote the ability to manage finances in the region.

Locally, various respective countries have structural entrepreneurship training programme initiatives (Sheriff and Muffatto, 2015). In the 2019 Ghanaian national budget report, 7000 entrepreneurs were trained under the National Entrepreneurship Innovation Plan (NEIP), and 1350 SMEs were assisted in restructuring and developing business plans with financial support in 2018 (Ofori-Atta 2019: Amoako & Agyapong, 2020). The project initiatives by the Ghanaian governments were expected to create 2700 direct jobs for people. Furthermore, In the 2018/2019 financial year, Rwanda initiated National Employment Programme (NEP), which was aimed to enhance and create jobs for over 4700 entrepreneurs (Budget report 2018). To attain this target, several measures such as Hands-on skills development, Skills upgrading for artisans, and standards and compliance capacity development programs were designed to encourage people into entrepreneurship, facilitated by different institutions and apprenticeships opportunities (Ndagijimana, 2019).

Furthermore, in 2019, the International Trade Center (ITC) report indicated a reform in the Kenyan national constitution dedicated to a section for SMEs and youth employment. Several instrumental policies, such as the 'National Youth Empowerment Strategy,' 'National Employment Policy and Strategy for Kenya' and 'Kenya's Youth Development Policy', were initiated to help spur SMEs and Youth entrepreneurship in Kenya (International Trade Center 2019). Over the years, the Kenyan government has supported 497 037 entrepreneurs from 2012 to 2017 through an established national Enterprise fund.

3.5 Effectiveness of Training initiatives

However, despite the comprehensive entrepreneurship support offered to start-ups and SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa, several diverse arguments exist on these training programs' effectiveness. A study by Mukata, Ladzani, and Visser (2018) assessed the effectiveness of entrepreneurship training offered to SME service providers in Namibia and revealed that the constant rate of business failures after entrepreneurship training depends on the experience and quality of training received. Regardless, most recent Sub-Saharan African countries have healthy policy initiatives on entrepreneurship. However, these entrepreneurship training initiatives' ultimate goals should align with the needs of various governments and individual countries (Adenle, 2017; Makwembere, and Pooe, 2020).

Furthermore, Sub-Saharan Countries must responsively act, primarily through policies to support technical, vocational, and business incubators in various regions and communities (Nkirina, 2010; Abor and Quartey, 2010; Kuada, 2015). Given these, successful entrepreneurship initiatives can be successful if different facilitators and coordinators of respective programmes understand the nature of the local indigenes' entrepreneurial activities that are supported by government policies and consortium partners to achieve success. The nature of entrepreneurial activities is complex and associated with ambiguity, as discussed in the previous chapters. The core importance of entrepreneurship training within the ecosystem has been pivotal for policy formulation and other initiatives to enhance business activities.

As a priority for most countries, several governments have adopted an insightful trend to installing strategic policies pertain to entrepreneurial activities with flexible approaches to enhance intention for entrepreneurs as there is scarcity in this research area (Sheriff and Muffatto 2015), especially in developing countries. Subjective evidence suggests that there are different kinds of policies and initiatives with regard to entrepreneurial training in

institutions and organisations across the globe (Sheriff, 2005; Adenle, 2017). The above policy initiatives in table 2 serve as an intermediary to understand the commercialised policies employed for the studies' geographical area.

Recently, most businesses are faced with challenges that have called for the innovation strategies and models to change (Stankovska, Josimovski and Edwards 2016) and adopt an ecosystem model that encompasses all the critical stakeholders in the entrepreneurial ecosystem, and this includes; government, students, business owners, institutions, business incubators, business associations among others (Murray et al., 2018; Sheriff and Muffatto 2015; African Development Bank, 2016).

Most policies usually focus on single end-users of entrepreneurial training rather than the broader perspectives of the end-users of entrepreneurial training in the ecosystem. However, in the past decades, that has been a shift in vital interest in entrepreneurial training subjected to innovation systems within the ecosystems in the 1990s towards training involving critical users of the entrepreneurial training to enrich their knowledge base through an academic and public debate (Sheriff and Muffatto 2015; Baah, et al., 2020). Comparably, this has staged the national discussion for a keen interest in entrepreneurship as a discipline of compliance as a significant catalyst for sustainable growth in the ecosystem rather than innovation training.

3.6 Patterns of SMEs in Africa

The advent of different paradigms in the business ecosystem can be grouped in clusters in sub-Saharan Africa. Over the years, there has been an explosive growth of different kinds of literature in this field (Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Baah, et al., 2020). The crustal groupings of SMEs in specific regions in the Sub-Saharan relates to the core business

operational activities associated with the territory (Louise, 2018; Sheriff and Muffatto, 2015; Baah, et al., 2020). This grouping can either be similar business activities (Ejesi & Ejem, 2021) or geographical segmentation of the particular region's business activities. These segmentations or grouping triangulate business activities to specific communities or countries. This enhances specialisation and social development. For example, from a broader perspective, Kenya is world known for their wildlife reserves which attract a lot of tourists to the country, and Ivory Coast is also known for Cocoa production, Ethiopia as a country is known for it prudent aviation sector and among others. In the context of smaller communities' places like 'Nnewi- Nigeria', 'And Abbosey Okai- Ghana, is known for auto spare parts. Town-Town in Rwanda is also known for the gorgeous sale of fabric across the streets (African Development Bank, 2016; ICT 2019; Sheriff and Muffatto 2015).

3.6.1 Ghana

Ghana, located in the western part of Africa, has an estimated population of about 30 million people across the region (world bank data, 2020; ILO, 2020). The annual GDP increased from 6.3 percent in 2018 to 6.5 percent in 2019, respectively (IMF data, 2020). The estimated unemployment rate also increased in 2019 by about 4.3 percent compared to 2018 of about 4.1 percent (world bank data, 2020). The world bank data further indicates that the population below the poverty line is about 23.4 percent. Several reports from the world bank, International Monetary Fund, African Development Bank, and budget reports in Ghana explicate the effect of the country's unemployment crisis and living conditions (Abor and Quartey, 2010; Amoah and Amoah 2018; Owusu-Ansah 2012).

Ghana's economic growth rate has been projected as one of the fastest-growing economies by international organisations, which projects that the country is associated with a prospective future (world bank report 2018). The government and other organisations have

prioritised an essential quota to SMEs for their contribution through enhancement and supportive approach in the country in the past decades. This is because the SME sector employs about 85 per cent of the active labour force in urban and rural areas (Amoah and Amoah, 2018). In 2019, the sector contributed about 71 per cent to the GDP (Ofori-Atta, 2019). These statistical indicators from local and international reports suggest that the Ghanaian economy depends massively on SMEs' growth (Pearl 2018; Ejesi & Ejem, 2021). This projects a significant contribution of SMEs to the country's socio-economic development.

Over the years, the country has seen an upsurge of interest by policymakers, investors, and business owners to instigate a strategic approach to ensure sustainability. SME businesses in Ghana are mostly family-owned businesses that transfer from one generation to the other (Pearl, 2018). The crucial role of SMEs play in Ghana is essential, yet the sector is associated with uncertainty, which leads to the collapse of most businesses in the country (Dankwa, 2018). Several policies have been initiated by both local and international organisations such as the Ministry of Trade and Industry, MasterCard Foundation, World Bank, and African Development Bank (ADB) to provide both 'financial support' and 'training and skills development initiatives (ILO report 2015; Trends, 2019). Table 4.1 indicates training initiatives instigated to support both young, potential, and existing entrepreneurs. To address the unemployment crisis, it is therefore essential to train students, young entrepreneurs, and existing SMEs to have positive intentions towards adapting to the dynamic nature of business activities in Ghana (Dzisi and Odoom, 2017) since the nature of entrepreneurship activity is associated with ambiguity (Kiggundu, 2002). This has triggered the attention to dynamic measures to ensure strategic interventions to protect SMEs' competitive and desirable contribution (Boso, Debrah, and Amankwah-Amoah, 2018; Abor and Quartey, 2010).

SMEs' activities in Ghana seem favourable compared to other Sub-Saharan African countries because of the stable political environment over the years (Sheriff and Muffatto 2015). According to international communities and observers, Ghana can boast of peaceful and successful general elections for the past years (Mbaku, 2016; Amoako & Agyapong, 2020). The nature of SMEs in Ghana is classified as a one-person business where the owner performs all the managerial roles from financing, production, marketing, and distribution (Owusu-ansah, 2012). This role of managers seems a burden but sometimes affects the business. This is because Robinson et al. (2017) argued that the general control of all activities within the business operating environment has a venom effect on the business.

After Ghana gained independence in 1957, the country deployed on operating on large scale industry which was mainly centered on the exportation of finish and semi-finished goods (Abor, and Quartey, 2010) and import substitutions with limited no specific policies to protect and enhance SMEs (Sheriff and Muffatto, 2015). However, over the recent past decades, the focus of present policies within the country seeks to promote entrepreneurial and SME activities.

Several entrepreneurial training programs have been initiated to promote economic growth (Amoah and Amoah, 2018). These training initiatives were fully designed to align the needs of entrepreneurs to trade and consumer requirements (Sheriff and Muffatto 2015) with the hope of promoting an entrepreneurial environment and the private sector. Several educational policies have been initiated with priorities emphasis on vocational and technical training to alleviate students' intrinsic desire to develop an entrepreneurial intention towards self-employment after graduating. The Ghanaian educational sector has taken adequate steps to promote entrepreneurship programs by creating awareness to encourage self-employment after graduating (Adarkwa, 2010).

The budgetary report makes provision for SMEs and business training projects in the country for the past decades. This provision is set to promote individual entrepreneurialism to create jobs, reduce the unemployment rate, and also ensure the gap created by the universities in terms of provision of practical and employment skills is bridged.

Additionally, the country has seen an explosion of interest from international organisations and other philanthropists such as MasterCard foundation and the World Bank with dynamic and immense investment in Ghana to promote the activities of SMEs by providing them with access to business advisory services and financial opportunities in the country (Adenle, 2017; Reeta 2006; MasterCard foundation report 2015). These opportunities are mandated to provide practical application of skills development.

To achieve this, it is essential to understand how the entrepreneurship education and training initiatives instigated by the government of Ghana and other local international organisations influence the intentions of these entrepreneurs.

Table 3.1 Ghana Entrepreneurship Support, Policies Initiatives

PROGRAM	Function
<i>The National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programme (NEIP)</i>	'NEIP focuses on providing business development services; start-up incubators and funding for young businesses to enable them grow and become successful'
<i>Ghana Investment and Promotion Center (GIPC)</i>	GIPC provides a hub for international and local investors to link together by providing tax exemptions on goods and accurate information about doing business in Ghana.
<i>Exibank Ghana</i>	Exibank aligns with government's agenda for Industrialisation and provide support for the private sector with initiatives. Exibank

	finance ensure employment creation, value addition through production efficiency and foreign exchange revenue potential for SMEs who needs financial support.
<i>National Board for Small Scale Industry (NBSSI)</i>	NBSSI was established in 1981 to provide supportive Programs to micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) and start-ups businesses in Ghana.
<i>Regional Appropriate Technology Industrial Service (GRATIS)-Grantis foundation</i>	Grantis foundation was established in 1987, to ensure SMEs acquire the necessary technological support from the European Union and the Canadian International Development Agency to promote small-scale industrialisation in the country.
<i>Young African Leader Initiative</i>	Promote business and entrepreneurship, leadership skills and managerial skills
<i>Youth Inclusive Entrepreneurial Development initiative for Employment (YIEDIE)</i>	YIEDIE is a 5year (2015-2020) project designed to create economic opportunities in Ghana's construction sector for economically disadvantaged youth, implemented by Global Communities in partnership with Mastercard Foundation.

Source; MasterCard foundation reports; government business development reports 2019- (Ghana)

The nature of entrepreneurship existing in Ghana determines the policy initiatives. This is because Schumpeter (1934) suggested that a critical understanding of the entrepreneur's contributions to the economy will determine the kind of policies to ensure economic growth. Legislators are tasked to formulate policies to ensure SMEs are equipped with a favorable environment to operate within the ecosystem.

3.6.2 Kenya

In Kenya, SMEs, including micro-enterprises, employs about 81.1% of the workforce and contribute 5.6% to GDP (ILO, 2020). The country was perceived to be one of the fastest developing nations in the Sub-Saharan region until 2014, and the world bank classified the country as a low-income country. According to the world bank projection indicators, Kenyan's population is estimated to be 52.5 million in 2019. The population has doubled over

the past 30 years. Despite the population growth, GDP for the nation decreased from 6.3% in 2018 to 5.3% in 2019. Musambayi (2018) argued that the major challenges associated with Kenya's economy are the persistent unemployment rate, poor business performance, and declining level of entrepreneurial activities, which hinder the growth rate.

With respect to vision 2030, Kenya projects to achieve a middle-income country. Mwai (2019) argued that Kenya's road map to vision 2030 was subjected to three key parameters, thus "Economic", "Social", and "Political" strategies. Mwai's (2019) views on the massive investment in these parameters were to make Kenya's economy globally competitive and improve the quality of life of its citizen. The Kenyan government's paradigmatic approach was subjected to improving the key areas such as health, water, sanitation education, entrepreneurial training, and a favourable working environment to promote stable economic growth. Most SMEs in Kenya are faced with financial challenges (Nafukho and Helen 2010; Ezeanya, and Egbunike, 2020), endangering their ability to survive. Banks charge an excessive rate of about 20% interest rate, making it critical for SMEs to borrow (Mawi, 2019). Banks seem reluctant to reduce charges on loans borrowed from people and other businesses. In response to this, the Kenyan government pegged the interest charges to the national prime rate to reduce the rate not above 4% set by the government (Mawi, 2019). This legislation was a drastic approach to promote a conducive business environment to alleviate the interest burden on business owners and repayment stress on individuals and firms.

SMEs in Kenya are perceived as the panacea to the country's persistent unemployment rate (Nafukho and Helen 2010). The Kenyan government has invested massively in entrepreneurial training and education in the past decades (Kinya, Wanjau, and Omondi, 2018). This is because the government of Kenya has initiated strategic measures to incorporate Integrated entrepreneurship and other business modules in the education

curriculum to enable innate talented individuals to spot opportunities and successfully execute them.

Table 3.2 Kenya's Entrepreneurship Support, Policies Initiatives

PROGRAM	Function
<i>The Youth Enterprise Development Fund</i>	Entrepreneurship training and resources, Funding opportunities for start-ups, Job Matching, Mentoring for Kenyan youth to participate national development.
<i>Young African Leader Initiative (YALI)</i>	Promote business and entrepreneurship, leadership skills and managerial skills
<i>Stawisha SME Mashinani</i>	An initiative by the Kenyan government to provide affordable credit to MSMEs, Provide business advisory services and grants to SMEs especially in the agriculture, food and textile industries.
<i>Young Africa Works</i>	A MasterCard foundation initiative to promote young entrepreneurs to create jobs, enhance digital entrepreneurship in Kenya, provide business advisory services for young people, and provide capital opportunities, mentorship, and business development services, predominantly in the agriculture, manufacturing, housing, and health care
<i>Youth Business International</i>	Support for young entrepreneurs within 18 – 35 years to start, grow and sustain their businesses through a viable business idea

Source; MasterCard foundation reports; government business development reports 2019- (Kenya)

It is important to note that entrepreneurial activities encompass all business ecosystem activities, which include policy initiatives and how the economy is managed but not only the entrepreneurs only. The Kenyan government is tasked with an important role in encouraging

entrepreneurial spirit through vocational and technical education. The government of Kenya, for example, invested in females through vocational and technical training to address the persistent increase in the female unemployment rate to engage in self-employment across the country (Nafukho and Helen 2010). The policy initiatives regarding SMEs need to address and identify all loopholes to trigger SMEs' intentions. This will create both internal and external conducive environments for small businesses.

3.7 Conclusion

Unlike other regions, the sub-Saharan African region is the largest region, with a total active labour force of 47% compared to its population (ILO, 2020). The current statistics indicate the unemployment rate and a decline in economic growth (World Bank data, 2020). One of the major concerns for most developing nations is creating jobs for the soaring youthful lads. Most Sub-Saharan countries like Ghana, Kenya, and Rwanda frequently have several SMEs that fail within the first five years of business operation and have a high unemployment rate (Jones et al. 2018). Some researchers have argued that business failures do not mean a business is out of business (Davis, 2015). In response to this argument, Ucbasaran et al. (2009) and Short et al. (2010) attribute it to a decline in profits resulting from a reduction in entrepreneurial intentions to operate a business. Considering the number of graduates for tertiary institutions with business and entrepreneurship backgrounds annually, it is difficult to understand the persistent unemployment rate even though the Sub-Saharan African countries are endowed with diverse business opportunities which have not to be tapped.

In other to address this issue, entrepreneurship education and training are fundamental to understanding both SMEs' nature and measures to mitigate risk. This can only be achieved when all the various stakeholders contribute to a quota understanding of actual entrepreneurs'

right entrepreneurial training or education. As discussed earlier, most SMEs are often family-owned businesses, and the family members perform the operational activities. Most of these individuals have access to formal or no formal entrepreneurship training, and most of this training are transpire from one generation to the other.

Most governments across the Sub-Saharan African region have initiated several policies to promote entrepreneurship. The next chapter underpin the nature of entrepreneurial intention and factors that influence the intentions of SMEs. Given the significance of entrepreneurship, researchers have shown considerable interest in exploring the concept of entrepreneurial intention. Various authors have contended that entrepreneurial intentions are influenced by multiple factors, some of which are within an individual's control, while others are beyond their control, in the pursuit of establishing and operating a business venture.

Chapter 4: Entrepreneurship Intention of SMEs

Numerous research findings suggest that entrepreneurial training and education can influence the intention of entrepreneurs. The ultimate questions are; How long can their intentions last? Do the intentions of entrepreneurs decrease or increase? What triggers the intentions of entrepreneurs? Most researchers' emphasis on entrepreneurial intentions is mostly focused on individual ability to start their own business. Most of their research sample frame is subjected to students rather than SMEs or individuals who are already in a business (Santoso, 2017; Yabashaija and Katono, 2011).

Different parameters are involved in the formation of entrepreneurship intention. Some of these factors are as a result of both internal and external behavioural traits of an individual (Ajzen 1991), personal experiences (Morris 1998), and others are also as a result of the trigger of events (Shapero, A. and Sokol 1982; Lorz, 2011). Some authors believe that entrepreneurial intentions are influenced by a series of traits such as demographic, psychological, Skills, and environmental influence (Lorz 2011; Marvin, Pentang and Flora 2014).

In light of this, the nature of entrepreneurship has called for great interest by researchers to investigate the concepts of entrepreneurial intention. Some authors have argued that entrepreneurship intentions are triggered by many factors which individuals have control of or beyond the control of an individual to establish and run a business venture (Shane and Khurana, 2003; and Sha, 2003).

4.1 Introduction

In the late 1990s, there was an explosion of different kinds of research on intention models and conceptual frameworks, thereby confirming various themes of its applicability in the business ecosystem (Mitton,1989; Cant, 1996; Ajzen 1991; Shapero, 1982). However, despite different alternative models of intentions, there is some evidence of its adaptability in

the entrepreneurial ecosystem (Liñán and Fayolle, 2015; Ezeanya, and Egbunike, 2020). The nature of entrepreneurship is complicated, which demands potential entrepreneurs' interest to adopt positive intentions (Koe and Majid, 2014). Some researchers argued that intentions represent an individual's motivation to exhibit a conscious effort to execute a plan or take a bold decision (Millman, Matlay, and Wang-chan, 2010). Meta-analyses from diverse research indicate a strong bond between intention and people's behaviour (Santoso, 2017; Lorz, 2011). Owusu (2014) highlighted that developing nations, such as those in Africa, may hold a wealth of undiscovered entrepreneurship opportunities. However, it is not merely identifying these opportunities but also the commitment of entrepreneurs to continue their businesses that will shape the future economic landscape. Thus, this study aims to shed light on the factors influencing the intentions of African SME entrepreneurs to persist in their ventures, ultimately contributing to sustainable economic growth. From the diverse literature reviewed, entrepreneurship intention (EI) can be categorised into two broad thematic parameters. The first parameter can be associated with social-psychological attributes of an individual's behaviour (Mitton,1989; Ajzen, 1991). This considers the general fundamental and mental process of an individual to respond to a particular attitude or belief. Examples can be seen in Mitton's (1989) research works, which argued that people with entrepreneurial intentions are associated with psychological attributes such as commitment, managerial capacity, and action to take a risk. Over the past decades, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) by Ajzen (1991) has widely been used as the basis of experimenting or investigating social-psychological traits of an entrepreneur's intention in general.

Furthermore, the second thematic parameter of intention can be linked to a specific area of entrepreneurship. These can be seen in the works of (Shapero and Sokol 1982; Bird 1988). Shapero and Sokol (1982) introduced a systematic model that provided a logical explanation of the critical processes that foster the intent to establish a new venture.

However, the amalgamation of both themes gives a generous contribution to the understanding of entrepreneurship intentions. Entrepreneurship intentions have been defined over the years as people's state of mind to create and undertake a business venture (Lorz, 2011; Santoso, 2017). The uncertain nature of entrepreneurship requires the interest of researchers to investigate the intentions of entrepreneurs. Over the decades, the majority of empirical studies conducted generally has focused on the motivation of entrepreneurs ability to ensure business growth at various stages of their business operation (Kauanui, Thomas, Rubens, and Sherman 2010; Davidsson, Achtenhagen and Naldi; 2010; Estay, Durrieu, and Akhter 2013; Davis 2015).

However, there is limited or partial neglect of empirical research on entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial intention towards business growth (Nabi Holden 2008; Lorz, 2011; Santoso, 2017). Since the terms are mostly used interchangeably in most works of literature reviewed, it is essential to distinguish between entrepreneurship motivation and entrepreneurship intentions in this chapter.

4.2 Nature of Entrepreneurship Intention

The word intention in nature refers to an individual's primary motivation to make a conscious effort to execute a plan (Liñán and Fayolle, 2015). From Liñán and Fayolle's definition, it can be deduced that individuals need the motivation to have intent. The nature of entrepreneurship intent means an individual's mindset to start a new business venture (Shook and Bratianu, 2008). Entrepreneurial intentions play a crucial role in understanding the critical parameters of entrepreneurial concepts concerning a business's growth. In the late 1990s, Cant (1996) perceived the people's entrepreneurial intentions as the intrinsic motives to create jobs.

According to Fayolle, Gailly, and Lassas-Clerc (2006), entrepreneurial intention refers to the planning efforts that drive an individual's inclination to establish a business.

Similarly, Wurthmann (2014) describes entrepreneurial intention as the conscious decision of a motivated individual to initiate a new venture. These scholars highlight that entrepreneurial intention is a pivotal starting point for individuals who are motivated and willing to embark on entrepreneurial endeavours. It becomes apparent that the level of motivation significantly influences an individual's intention to start their own business. In essence, entrepreneurial intentions are shaped by various situational factors that may be under an individual's control or beyond their influence. This implies that either existence or absence of motivation dramatically impacts the likelihood of having a positive intention to initiate an entrepreneurial venture. Recognizing the importance of motivation in fostering entrepreneurial intentions can provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders involved in entrepreneurship development programs. By understanding the factors that influence motivation, such as personal aspirations, environmental factors, and support networks, efforts can be directed towards fostering an entrepreneurial mindset and cultivating an environment conducive to entrepreneurial success. Undebatable, most of the literature reviewed postulate entrepreneurial intention as a person's motive to undertake a conscious and strategic business plan.

4.2.1 Relationship between Entrepreneurial Motivation and Intention

In order to establish a link that triggers an individual's intent to act in a specific way towards starting their business and operating their business, it is crucial to understand the various motivation factors that trigger their intent. In order to establish a connection between an individual's entrepreneurial motivation and intention to start and operate a business, it is crucial to examine the various factors that influence their motives. Scholars have conducted extensive research on these factors, including personal attributes such as age, education level, gender, and cultural background (Lorz, 2011; Hui-Chen et al., 2014; Estay et al., 2013; Davis, 2015; Ezeanya & Egbunike, 2020). Different authors have proposed numerous models

to investigate the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation and intention, as well as how these motives can be used to predict the attitudes and behaviours of entrepreneurs.

The link between entrepreneurial motivation and intention is a complex and dynamic process. Individuals with different personal characteristics and backgrounds may be driven by unique motives to engage in entrepreneurial activities. For instance, research suggests that age can influence entrepreneurial motivation, with younger individuals being more inclined towards entrepreneurial pursuits due to their desire for independence and personal fulfilment (Lorz, 2011). Similarly, education level has been found to impact entrepreneurial motivation, as higher levels of education can provide individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills to recognize business opportunities and overcome challenges (Estay et al., 2013).

Gender also plays a role in entrepreneurial motivation, with studies indicating that women entrepreneurs often have different motives compared to their male counterparts. For instance, women may be motivated by factors such as work-life balance, flexibility, and the desire to make a positive social impact (Hui-Chen et al., 2014). Cultural influences further shape entrepreneurial motivation, as cultural values and norms can impact individuals' perception of entrepreneurship as a viable career choice (Davis, 2015).

The various models developed by scholars aim to understand the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation and intention. These models consider factors such as personal characteristics, environmental influences, and psychological processes to explain how motivation translates into entrepreneurial intentions. By identifying and understanding the motives that drive individuals towards entrepreneurship, policymakers, educators, and practitioners can design targeted interventions and support systems to foster entrepreneurial intentions and encourage entrepreneurial behaviour.

The relationship between entrepreneurial motivation and intention is multifaceted and influenced by a range of personal, cultural, and environmental factors. By examining these factors and utilizing the insights provided by different models, stakeholders can gain a deeper understanding of the motivational drivers behind entrepreneurship. This knowledge can inform the development of strategies and initiatives that promote entrepreneurial intentions and facilitate the growth and success of entrepreneurs in various contexts. Many researchers have used different explanatory models to establish the link between motivation and intention. However, the focus on the relationship between entrepreneurship motivation and intention is a broad topic that cannot be explored in a single study. The study area will strictly be limited to justifying the core relationship between these constants to justify the findings.

4.2.1.1 Cognitive approach

Firstly, some researchers have used cognitive models to examine entrepreneurs' thinking behaviour (Amato et al., 2018; Boukamcha 2015). Other researchers have also adapted the cognitive style to understand why people behave in a particular way (Adomako et al., 2016). Some researchers may ask why it is vital to consider the practical approach when establishing the link between entrepreneurs' motivation and intentions in this context. This is because the cognitive style has been acknowledged as a practical approach to explaining the motivating factors behind people's behaviour and preferences (Adomako et al., 2016; Amato et al., 2018). Abdallah, Halima, and Ibtissem (2019) suggested that to understand individuals' intention, and Consideration should be established to elaborate on the core values that directly influence a person's understanding of information and power to make decisions.

Hence, to understand various predictive variables of entrepreneurial intent, critical attention should be considered to understand the motivating factors of entrepreneurs that optimise their judgment and decisions to initiate and execute a plan. Solesvik (2013) conducted a study to investigate students' intention and profile with the desire to become

entrepreneurs. The study was conducted on students from three different universities in Ukraine. Their finding indicated that personality traits of an individual such as level of education have a great possibility of developing an intent of student towards establishing their business venture in the city.

4.2.1.2 Process Approach Model

The second parameter is the process model. This model considers the motivating factors that influence an individual's intentions due to expected rewards in wages or income and opportunities to satisfy personal needs (Chandra, 2017; Su, Wu, and Zhou, 2019). Sullivan and Meek (2012) argued that this approach deals with entrepreneurs' motivations and expectancy factors to develop a particular intention. The process model by Sullivan and Meek (2012) was categorised into stages, which further established that the process model of an entrepreneur examines the various factors that motivate an entrepreneur to choose a particular career path. The ambiguous nature of entrepreneurship (Amoah and Amoah 2018; Barnard and Luiz 2018; Hyder and Lussier 2016) suggests that an individual's intent to start a business deserves a positive intention to succeed (Koe and Majid, 2014).

In respect to these conditions attached to an entrepreneur's life, Sullivan and Meek (2012) argued that most people dislike the role exhibited by managers and have the intrinsic belief that they can perform better than their judgments. Such judgments motivate the intent of an individual to pursue an entrepreneurship venture. Su, Wu, and Zhou (2019) categorised entrepreneurs' process model approach into four phases; 'Before start-up Stage,' 'Start-up stage,' 'Early growth stage,' and 'Late growth.' They argued that at every stage of the process model of entrepreneurs, they are motivated by factors that influence people's intent. However, they neglected the uncertainties that may emanate during the entrepreneurs' process models at various stages. The emphasis was assumed as linear relation of the entrepreneurs' life without considering any unforeseen circumstances which may not trigger their intent.

4.2.2 How motivation affect Entrepreneurial intention of SMEs

In the past decades, there has been an explosion of several factors contributing to entrepreneurial activities' success in several different contexts. With the desire to survive most start-up and existing businesses, entrepreneurs are compelled to devise a strategic approach to having a desirable intention to achieve success (Hynes 1996; Ajzen, 1991; Ankli and Palliam, 2012; Kamanzi, 2019). SMEs' activities are perceived as the core demand for most nations to ensure economic growth (Santoso, 2017; Ezeanya, and Egbunike, 2020). Business sustainability is the core heart of most entrepreneurs (Hussain and Yaqub, 2010; Ezeanya, and Egbunike, 2020). This makes the demand for motivation a catalyst for the required intention to execute a plan by entrepreneurs. Shirol (2014) argued that motivation is an internal feeling which triggers an individual to react in a particular way. This implies that entrepreneurs cannot execute plans, decisions, tasks, or strategies without motivation.

In earlier research findings of Steller and Eliot (1985) suggested that despite motivation encouraging individuals to behave in a manner in terms of personal belongings and needs, with respect to the workplace, motivation incorporates external and internal stimuli. Their argument further postulated that initiate an intention or complete a task, motivation plays a crucial role, which is sometimes centred around inducement. Their opinion seems broad and comprehensively failed to illustrate the various critique and gaps found in recent literature.

Given this, Ankli & Palliam (2012) also argued that before the motivations of individuals are sparked, there should be some expected desires or inducement to encourage them to have an intention to 'respond to an action,' 'develop an intrinsic aspiration to learn' and 'strength to perform better at the workplace.' Expected returns or value for investment by entrepreneurs has shown a very high fundamental to enhance the intentions of entrepreneurs to achieve specific, measurable targets.

4.3 Entrepreneurial Intention Models

The nature of entrepreneurial intention reveals the state of mind, which encourages individuals to create jobs for themselves rather than focusing on traditional salary-based jobs (Dugassa, 2012). The nature of entrepreneurship is a complex and thematic understanding of the entrepreneur's intention to vital predict behaviour. Anderson et al. (2018) suggested that entrepreneurs' intention is very vital to predict their behaviour. On the other hand, other researchers believe the contrary (Dugassa, 2012; Krueger, Reilly, and Casrund, 2000). In support of this argument, Krueger et al. (2000) argued that an individual's decision to become an entrepreneur is probably deemed voluntary and not deliberate. However, several researchers specialising in intention-based studies believed that most of the model's explanatory variables could predict entrepreneurs' behaviours from a diverse perspective in a different context (Ajzen,1991; Shapero, 1982; Lorz 2011; Davis, 2015). Given this, it can be argued that entrepreneurship intention is fundamental to understanding entrepreneurs' overall behaviour. To understand how SMEs or entrepreneurs' intentions, it is vital to highlight some widely accepted intention models to examine their impacts on business activities.

Previous studies have analysed behavioural intention models to act as a theoretical framework to understand Entrepreneurship intention. Entrepreneurship Event Model (EEM) (Shapero,1982) and Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen,1991) are the two key models that have served as the basis of studying behavioural and intentions of entrepreneurs over the years. These two models, propounded by these authors, seem the most comprehensive and empirically thoroughly tested models to understand entrepreneurship intentions.

The intention model of entrepreneurship was first introduced by Shapero (1982), who examined how individuals' perceptions of entrepreneurship influence their intention to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Bird (1995) expanded on this model by raising concerns

about the inconsistency between entrepreneurial intentions and actual entrepreneurial behaviour. If intention is considered an independent variable capable of predicting behaviour, it becomes puzzling why some individuals fail to translate their entrepreneurial intentions into actual action. This disconnect between intention and behaviour has been a subject of interest and investigation among scholars, who seek to understand the underlying factors contributing to this difference. By exploring the difficulties of intention and its relationship to behaviour, researchers can gain valuable insights into the barriers and challenges that hinder the transformation of entrepreneurial intentions into tangible outcomes. Such understanding can inform the development of strategies and interventions to bridge the intention-behaviour gap and enhance the likelihood of entrepreneurial intentions being successfully translated into real-world entrepreneurial actions.

The TPB examines these factors that influence an individual behavioural trait (Ajzen (1991). The theory assumes that individuals' actions are conscious action to predict their intention to react in a particular way. Besides (Ajzen 2005) argued that the theory of planned behaviour consists of three key indicators, which are Attitude Towards Behaviour (ATB), Subjective Norm (SN), Perceived Behaviour Control (PBC).

Figure 1. Theory of Planned Behaviour - Ajzen (1991)

Ajzen (1991) TPB was classified into three key intention dimensional parameters: Attitude Towards Behaviour (ATB) which "refers to the strength of individual behaviour to achieve a particular purpose," Subjective Norm (SN), the second parameter also refers to "the social pressures from family, mentors, friends and other social influencers which trigger an individual to exhibit a particular behaviour" and finally, the third parameter Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) refers to the self-evaluation or self-efficacy of their core-competence to undertake a task.

According to Ajzen's (1991) theory of behavioural intention, entrepreneurial intention can be categorised into three main themes: Personal Experience, Social Influencers, and Self-efficacy, particularly within the context of business ecosystems (Edi et al., 2019; Al-Swidi et al., 2014; Markman et al., 2005). However, researchers generally agree that the more robust an individual's Attitude Towards Behavior (ATB), Subjective Norms (SN), and Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC), the stronger their behavioural intention to engage in entrepreneurship (Ajzen, 1991; Al-Swidi et al., 2014; Rachmawan et al., 2015). The theory of planned behaviour by Ajzen (1991) is subjected to a reason action theory (Eid et al., 2019), which considers both individuals' personal and social traits. From Ajzen's (1991) model above, intentions are influenced by an ATB, which refers to how individuals respond to a particular behaviour to achieve a particular purpose. Understanding the strength of ATB in a business environment, Azjen's argument will be analysed on the power of entrepreneurs' attitudes to stay favorable to a particular behaviour in this study. These were subjected to SMEs' encounters or experiences to exhibit some specific trait to display specific behaviour.

Undoubtedly, in recent global crises, it is vital to know the entrepreneurial strength of existing entrepreneurs' attitudes regarding whether they can be sustainable considering these persistent changes of the business condition affecting business activities, especially among small and medium enterprises (Edi et al., 2019). In the case of subjective norm, Azjen's illustration specifically projected the influence of pressure from families, mentors, and colleagues' impacts on individuals' intention. This is because Krueger et al. (2000) suggested that persistent interactions from friends and family who are already entrepreneurs can influence an individual's intentions to act like them. Al-Swidi, Mohammed, Haroon, and Noor (2014), called these pressures from family, friends, mentors, and colleagues, among others, as Social Influencers (SI). These SI are very important in nurturing and grooming individuals' intentions to become entrepreneurs to exhibit entrepreneurs' essential traits (Dugassa, 2012; Ezeanya, and Egbunike, 2020).

In respect to perceived behavioural control, Ajzen (1991) referred to an individual's core competence. Azjen argument was based on the degree of applying potential abilities to act or behave in a particular manner. Markman et al. (2005) suggested that starting up a new business is a challenging process that demands individual core competencies and self-efficacy. Markman et al.'s (2005) arguments were based on the fact that applying such self-efficacy in business differs actual entrepreneurs from non-entrepreneurs. This indicates that SMEs or entrepreneurs have a higher tendency to persevere and self-efficacy and overcome various obstacles and setbacks to have a positive intention towards striving for growth.

However, after critically evaluating the theory of planned behaviour by Azjen (1991), a mathematical equation can be generated from the various themes of the theory.

$\uparrow ATB + \uparrow SN + \uparrow PBC = \uparrow EI$ – this implies the higher the ATB, SN, and PBC of individuals' behaviour, the tendency they are likely to develop an increase in entrepreneurial intention.

Other researchers have also supported the motion that the TPB can be used to predict entrepreneurs' behaviour (Ajzen 1991, Lorz 2011; Davis, 2015; Solesvik, 2013).

Under the theory of planned behaviour, the three-key concepts specify different simplified beliefs that form the study's salience to critically understand the vital role of the intention concepts on SMEs. These salient beliefs include; the personal experience (PE), Social influencers (SI), and Self-efficacy of entrepreneurs (Edi et al., 2019; Al-Swidi et al., 2014; Markman et al., 2005). The amalgamation of these salient beliefs in the context of the business environment proposes a new different mathematical equation to understand existing entrepreneurs' or SMEs' intentions.

$\uparrow PE + \uparrow SI + \uparrow SE = \uparrow I$.- This implies that the higher the Personal Experience (PE), Social influencers (SI) (family, mentors, role models, consultants, friends), and Self-Efficacy SE (core competence and ability) of an entrepreneur or SME, the greater their entrepreneurial intention EI to strive for sustainability. Given that a new mathematical equation can be formulated.

Therefore, some critical questions can be derived from the context of SMEs operating their business.

Firstly, how does Personal experience influence the intention of SMEs?

How does Self-efficacy and core competencies affect the behavioural intention of SMEs?

How can people's mutual and social relationships directly or indirectly related to SMEs affect them to perform or respond to a particular behaviour?

Furthermore, are the core competencies and ability of SMEs the best option to act in a particular manner?

4.3.1 Personal Experience (PE)

There has been an increase in debates in recent years surrounding whether SMEs should experience their business area in the form of apprenticeship, an internship in their society, or the real-world before commencing their actual business activity (Andreas, Rhodri, and Stephanie, 2006). The general concepts of personal experience are important because it exposes entrepreneurs to a unique insight to understand customers, practically analyse the market, and viably utilise and allocate scarce resources that can influence the business operating activities (Gabrielsson, and Politis, 2012). This earlier insight gained at the early stages of an entrepreneur's life triggers their intention to develop better and innovative ideas for the market and as well serve customers by responding to their basic needs and capitalising on opportunities. Mai and Gu (2012) argued that SMEs' personal experience enables them to identify future entrepreneurial opportunities and gain access to relevant information about their business area. These unique experiences of entrepreneurs help them expand their network base, allowing them to apply basic techniques before and during their business operation (Ulvenblad et al., 2013). Mai and Gu (2012) conducted a study on successful businesses, and their outcome revealed that previous experiences and encounters of entrepreneurs play a crucial role in the way they behave.

Recent studies often suggest a positive influence of entrepreneurs' personal experience on their new ventures (Mai and Gu, 2012; Lorz 2011; Vaillant and Lafuente, 2019), with limited research on its negative impact. For example, suppose an individual quit from his daily job they never enjoyed to set the same kind of venture. In that case, this means they may be likely to have low intrinsic motivation considering the risk associated with entrepreneurship. Alongside, the entrepreneurial experience from his/her past job could be difficult for them to apply their ability comprehensively considering the risk of capital

associated with starting a new business. With respect to this, their previous experience may tend to impact their business inversely.

Therefore, entrepreneurs' personal experiences and past experiences affect their cognitive way of thinking in a new business adventure. Vaillant and Lafuente (2019) pinpointed that a new variation in experience explains the rationale behind why entrepreneurs differ from one another. The justification for applying entrepreneurs' cognitive decisions differs from entrepreneurs who lack personal experience (Amato et al., 2018). Successful entrepreneurs are able to exploit, identify opportunities, and utilise their core competencies (Chinomona et al., 2020). To support this, Ojeifo et al., (2021) suggested that if an entrepreneur identifies opportunities, apply their abilities to increase the core capacity to manage entrepreneurial risk based on the past or previous entrepreneurial experiences, and they have promoted growth.

4.3.2 Social Influencer (SI)

The nature of entrepreneurship is complicated, understood differently from different people's perspectives (Rachmawan, Lizar, and Mangundjaya, 2015; O'leary, 2017; Ojala and Heikkilä, 2011). There has been some behavior trait that transcends to entrepreneurs either from friends or family (Putta, 2014). The nature of entrepreneurial activities seems unstructured, complicated, and demands different adaptations (Rachmawan et al., 2015). This implies there is no laid down procedures to learn entrepreneurship. However, the study conducted in the late 1900s by Autio et al. (1997) indicated entrepreneurship education and training directly impact students who are willing to become entrepreneurs and equip them with the necessary information and skills to achieve success. Matlay (2018) also suggested that entrepreneurship education triggers students' interest to engage in entrepreneurial activities. These authors' views suggest that education and training can influence individuals'

decisions, either from a tutor or teacher. This implies entrepreneurs are likely to behave like their tutors and, as such, adapt some of their acquired knowledge into their business.

There is no specific approach to influencing the behavior of entrepreneurs (Owusu-Ansah, 2012). Several studies have also pin-point that family traits such as a relationship with parents who are entrepreneurs and family income have a positive correlation with the entrepreneurs (Lorz, 2011, and Rachmawan et al., 2015). Davis (2015) claimed that families are perceived to be a sense of independence and the first point of nurturing entrepreneurs to have entrepreneurial confidence and control. Studies conducted by Rachmanwan et al. (2015) postulated a positive relationship between some of the variables; 'Family,' 'childhood experience,' 'role model', as well as 'previous job experience' on intentions of entrepreneurs.

4.3.3 Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy has been described as a critical determinant of entrepreneurial intention (Udayanan, 2019). Edi et al. (2019) suggested that self-efficacy defines the intrinsic belief of an individual's core competence to complete a task. Self-efficacy becomes a key asset when individuals are challenged with a difficult situation and can mitigate them, and also when an individual wants to establish a business (Udayanan, 2019). Many academia' have researched thoroughly into various parameters needed to enhance entrepreneurial capacity and intentions (Chinomona et al., 2020; Krueger et al., 2000; Anderson et al., 2018; Chandra, 2017). Most findings from different kinds of literature indicate that the stronger the entrepreneurial intentions and self-efficacy, the stronger the attempt to start a business (Lorz, 2011; Udayanan, 2019).

Caldwell and Hayes (2016) conducted a study to find the relationship between self-efficacy and self-awareness of entrepreneurial leaders to understand their core competence and abilities. The outcomes also revealed that to achieve great success, entrepreneurs with significant self-efficacy have the potential to achieve great success than

those without. Self-efficacy describes an individual's core capabilities to strive towards success (Kasouf, Morrish, and Miles, 2015). Kasouf, Morrish and Miles (2015) conducted a study to examine how entrepreneurial actions impact business development. Their findings indicated that two cognitive results (explanatory style and self-efficacy) positively link with entrepreneurial intentions. They further proposed a framework that will help understand how self-efficacy influences entrepreneurial intentions and a guide to aid policymakers in promoting entrepreneurial success. However, it is not surprising that innovative entrepreneurs can exhibit a high level of competencies (Markman et al., 2005).

Despite diverse research's positive contributions to the impact of self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention, it is also associated with some contrary findings. Wang, Chang, Yao, and Liang (2016) conducted a study to analyse the impact of personality traits and self-efficacy on entrepreneurs' intentions. Their findings revealed that self-efficacy partially affects entrepreneurs' intentions. These may be as a result of the control variables used. Furthermore, Zarefard and Cho (2018) also conducted a study to investigate the impact of core competence and innovation on entrepreneurs' performance and output. Their findings also suggested a negative relationship between self-efficacy and innovation of entrepreneurs.

From the review, to understand entrepreneurs' self-efficacy, key variables that throw lights on the entrepreneurial capabilities and core competencies should be examined to understand the intentions of SMEs. For this reason, researchers should focus on core competencies that promote the development of entrepreneurial capacities that will foster entrepreneurial skills and knowledge. For a business to succeed, entrepreneurial training programmes should focus on how to build core competencies of entrepreneurs to develop a core attitude toward entrepreneurialism.

4.4 Entrepreneurial capacities (EC) and intentions

The word 'entrepreneurial capacities' define entrepreneurs' talent and core competencies in any business operating venture (Chinomona et al., 2020). The talents and abilities of entrepreneurs are vital in analysing the thematic stages of operating businesses. These stages include starting, nurturing, competing, and sustaining businesses in the ecosystem (Baloch et al., 2017; Jayeoba, 2015). Entrepreneurs' core competencies are labelled as the skills, techniques, attitudes, and knowledge combined to ensure efficiency at the various workplaces (Chinomona et al., 2020). Mai and Gan (2007) suggested that entrepreneurial capacities can be categorised into two segments: 'entrepreneurial intention' and 'entrepreneurial opportunities.' The entrepreneurial intention in this context refers to the intrinsic motivation that enhances the intention of promising entrepreneurs to create a business venture. Their argument in this context did not highlight how these capabilities can sustain their intention of entrepreneurs. This is because Anderson et al. (2018) suggested that the nature of entrepreneurial activities is complex. A thematic understanding of their intention is essential when predicting how they behave in the long run to sustain their business. Entrepreneurial capabilities are important in diverse ways to spur the intention of both potential and existing entrepreneurs. In the context of entrepreneurial opportunities, Mai and Gan (2007) attributed it deeply to the various external and internal environmental implications that affect entrepreneurs' intentions. Corbett (2007) identified these internal and external implications are social and economic factors that affect business operation activities. These factors include blocked promotion at the workplace, recession, fired from work, divorced or married. Shapero (1982) highlighted these factors that enable entrepreneurs to develop a capacity to establish an intention towards entrepreneurship. Shapero categorised these social and economic factors into three categories; 1. 'Negative displacement/push factors,' 2. 'Between factors' and 3. Pull or positive factors.

Figure 2. Key impact on entrepreneur's intention

Shapero and sokol (1982) categorised these life-changing events, which may enhance individuals' capacity to develop an intent as an explanatory model to explain both internal and external issues affecting entrepreneurs' intentions. This was similar to the descriptions by Mai and Gan (2007). They also argued that these influencing factors could be attributed to the moulding and shaping of entrepreneurs' intentions before or within their business venture operation.

From the illustration, it can be pinpointed from figure two above; a scenario can be seen from the negative factors as postulated that economic recessions affecting SMEs activities due to coronavirus have led to the collapse or brought most businesses to a standstill (World Bank review, 2020). This may discourage potential entrepreneurs' intentions to engage in self-employment, and existing entrepreneurs may not have the zeal to continue their business operations. In another scenario, an entrepreneur can be encouraged by their colleague entrepreneurs or advice from mentors or partners to have a positive mindset towards entrepreneurship.

4.5 Conceptual framework

Based on the review above, the purpose of this research is to highlight the impact of entrepreneurship training with respect to the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa (Ghana and Kenya). The literature indicated that entrepreneurial capacity is influenced by entrepreneurial opportunities which trigger entrepreneurs' intentions since opportunities and capabilities are relatively scarce for most entrepreneurs to have efficient zeal to strive for success. This is because, Chinomona et al. (2020) argued that to acquire the capacity to develop an intention for entrepreneurship, business ventures must incorporate the necessary skills and core competencies to strive for success and remain competitive in the business environment.

The conceptual framework of entrepreneurial intentions encompasses various factors influencing individuals' inclination to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Among these factors, social influence, personal experience, and self-efficacy have been identified as critical determinants (Ajzen, 1991; Bandura, 1997; Krueger et al., 2000).

Figure 3 Triadic Influence Framework for entrepreneurial intention for SMEs Adapted from Ajzen (1991) and Shapero (1982) framework.

The proposed theoretical framework, called the "Triadic Influence Framework," integrates the influential factors of social influencers, personal experience, and self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intentions. This framework acknowledges the impact of external social factors, such as mentors, role models, and networks (Lorz, 2011), and the significance of personal experiences and past entrepreneurial endeavours (Davis, 2015) in shaping entrepreneurial intentions.

From the framework above,

Personal Experience;

Personal experience (PE) is being used to represent all the actual business-related variables, insights, and encounters by entrepreneurs either before or within the business operation (Ulvenblad et al., 2013; Vaillant & Lafuente, 2019).

Personal experience plays a crucial role in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. Individuals with prior exposure to entrepreneurship, either through family business involvement or entrepreneurial activities, are more likely to develop positive attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship (Krueger et al., 2000). Such firsthand experiences provide insights into entrepreneurship's challenges, rewards, and opportunities, influencing individuals' perceptions of feasibility and desirability. For example, employees may seem promising in a scenario where an entrepreneur wants to start his/her own business with family and friends. He then trusts and believes in them for the business's survival because you know the kind of person they are. What might trigger or go wrong? However, no matter how strong the relationship with loved ones sometimes poses a significant challenge working together in a professional setting. This is because O'leary (2017) suggested that business is deemed to grow and people are needed to expand; however, family and friends' presence can create chaos or political instability in the business's operational activities. On the other hand,

entrepreneurs' experiences from internship training or programmes can encourage SMEs to exhibit the right intention to make the right decisions in their business operational activities (Gabrielsson & Politis, 2012).

Social Influencer

In the case of social influencers (SI), earlier individuals close to the entrepreneurs have the capacity to influence their decisions. Several studies have indicated a positive relationship between family, role models, teachers/lecturers, and friends, influencing entrepreneurs' decisions (Lorz, 2011; Rachmanwan, 2015).

Social influence refers to the impact of external factors, such as family, friends, mentors, and role models, on an individual's entrepreneurial intentions (Ajzen, 1991). Different research findings suggest that business-interest individuals are more likely to pursue entrepreneurship if they perceive positive support and encouragement from their social networks (Krueger et al., 2000). Conversely, negative social influences or lack of support may dampen entrepreneurial intentions. These social influencers have a direct observable concept to ensure the individual personal characteristics to behave in a particular way through motivation (Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013). Furthermore, the trigger motivation from social influencers can impact the visual learning abilities of people. For example, an entrepreneur's role model, with whom they have personally had direct or indirect contact, might create some expectation level to achieve success through efficient motivations transpired either directly or indirectly (Estay, Durrieu, Akhter 2013).

Self-Efficacy

Nevertheless, in this scenario, self-efficacy refers to the entrepreneurs believing and exhibiting their core competencies to promote a positive intention to strive towards success (Kasouf, Morrish, and Miles 2015).

Self-efficacy, a concept introduced by Bandura (1997), refers to an individual's belief in their capability to perform entrepreneurial tasks and overcome obstacles. Higher levels of self-efficacy are associated with more excellent entrepreneurial intentions (Krueger et al., 2000). Individuals with a strong sense of self-efficacy perceive themselves as capable of effectively managing the uncertainties and demands of entrepreneurial endeavours, thus fostering their intentions to pursue entrepreneurship. This natural ability of entrepreneurs impacts their intention to exhibit a high level of managerial behavioural elements such as organising, controlling, planning, coordinating, etc. (Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013). The ultimate rationale of these three key concepts (PE, SI, SE) links entrepreneurial capacity (which depends on core competence) to influence SMEs' intentions, which psychologically influence SMEs' behaviour during their actual business operation. However, the researcher argued that the simplified deduction from Ajzen (1991) and Shapero (1982) would help understand the various conscious process of sub-section variables of understanding SMEs' intentions. This will help understand the multiple components of SMEs' intentions and initiate vital policies to aid the operational activities in the business ecosystem.

In the conceptual framework, these three factors, social influence, personal experience, and self-efficacy, interact and shape individuals' entrepreneurial intentions. Positive social influences, coupled with personal experiences demonstrating feasibility and desirability, enhance self-efficacy beliefs and increase the likelihood of individuals translating their intentions into entrepreneurial actions.

Understanding the interplay of these factors is crucial for policymakers, educators, and practitioners aiming to foster entrepreneurship. By leveraging social networks, providing exposure to entrepreneurial experiences, and nurturing individuals' self-efficacy beliefs, interventions can be designed to promote entrepreneurial intentions and facilitate the conversion of intentions into entrepreneurial actions.

Research question one : What impact have entrepreneurship training programmes had on entrepreneurs' capacity and determination in light of efforts by policymakers, educational institutions, global organisations, private entities, and NGOs?

Over the past decades, several African governments and institutions have acknowledged the vital role entrepreneurship plays in the economy. Most educational institutions have undertaken drastic measures to review the universities' education curricula (Draycott et al., 2011). For example, Amato et al. (2018) introduced a conceptual framework that best fits students who desire to be entrepreneurs and existing entrepreneurs. Since both concepts overlap, there needs to be more clarity in distinguishing between enterprise and entrepreneurship education.

Universities in sub-Saharan African countries need to provide practical entrepreneurial training so that promising entrepreneurs can adhere to enhancing entrepreneurial skills. Entrepreneurship in nature plays an influential role in generating job opportunities and reducing the persistent increase in the unemployment rate in Saharan Africa (Adenle, 2017; Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013). This answers the question as to why many governments and other international organisations have deployed several investments into Sub-Saharan African countries. These are measures to combat unemployment, poverty, and low living standards (Amoah & Amoah, 2018).

Despite a considerable number of investments and educational reform adjustments to promote entrepreneurship in universities, there are many unemployed or jobless people after graduating (Owusu-Ansah, 2012). This raises the alarming concern of whether such training is insufficient for such students to create jobs. Most graduates of business and entrepreneurship modules have yet to have continual intentions to engage in self-employment

ventures. Several data show that a considerable number of graduates from entrepreneurial training are about searching for jobs instead of creating jobs (Temoor et al., 2018). This situation has prompted most researchers to investigate the right training approach to educate entrepreneurs to engage in SME activities and educate upcoming entrepreneurs by providing the right skills to ensure entrepreneurial success. From chapter 2.2.1, Bridge (2015) and Gibb (1993) suggested that enterprise education is preferably used in work-related learning, which involves action, experimental learning, and entrepreneurship education. This implies that entrepreneurship education is a subset of enterprise education. Enterprise education looks into an immense scope of acquiring knowledge, initiating, and developing skills in social and business contexts (QAA, 2012).

To further understand the impact of entrepreneurship training on SMEs' intentions, it is appropriate to understand the crucial role apprentice programmes have on SMEs' intentions. Baloch et al. (2017) perceived apprenticeship as an essential tool to encourage potential entrepreneurs and students to acquire hands-on experience and understand their trade or business line in the real world. These gears people towards entrepreneurship to develop an intention towards entrepreneurship. Nkirina (2010) argued that apprenticeship training addresses the restrictions placed on classroom leanings, and this exposes potential entrepreneurs to understanding their trade area in a practical manner. For SMEs to have positive intentions towards their trade area, Jamison (2018) believed that coaching and mentorship justify the process of learning quickly at the workplace with valuable information, support, and direction. This explains Bjursell and Rebecka's (2018) claims that coaching is a set of techniques adopted to casually transmit learning skills, support, and other beneficial endeavours relating to a vocation or work from an expert or tutor. This provides vocational development for entrepreneurs to develop their Intrinsic desire towards being self-employed. Mentorships and coaching have been described by some researchers to be time-

consuming and a waste of time because the right mentors and mentees may need to be appropriately matched, leading to an insufficient exchange of knowledge and skills (Martin & Bok, 2015). Despite their crucial role, it is also affiliated with some setbacks.

From the above, *entrepreneurship training, entrepreneurial education, and apprenticeship programmes have the capacity to influence the intentions of SMEs*. If this rationale holds, the myth behind its influence on SMEs to have positive intent demands investigation to justify the reality of such an assumption in Sub-Saharan Africa. This because the statistical data from the world bank and other reports indicates a high unemployment rate and high dependency on the government for jobs (world youth report, 2018). This throws doubt behind why several governments have hugely invested in entrepreneurship training activities on youth and SMEs, especially in most sub-Saharan African.

Research question two : RQ2: How can the persistent rise in business failures among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Africa be interpreted in the context of efforts to enhance entrepreneurial capabilities through educational reforms and training initiatives?

In Africa, entrepreneurship education focuses on applying the mindset of setting up your venture in an entrepreneurial ecosystem (NdofirepI and Rambe 2017). University entrepreneurial training programmes provide students or promising entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and primary information through classroom-based programmes, inspire entrepreneurial motivation among students, and develop an intention towards entrepreneurship in a practical way (Putta, 2014). To understand the core of underpinned myth, it's vital to investigate SMEs' intention in the Sub-Saharan region. By judging SMEs' intentions in Sub-Saharan Africa, some earlier scholars have propounded theories that predict

individuals' intentions and behaviours (Shapero and Sokol 1982; Ajzen 1991). The examination of entrepreneurial intention has become a subject of global interest in recent decades, prompting numerous scholars to explore various models and propose different theories to elucidate the concept (Liñán & Fayolle, 2015; Shapero & Sokol, 1982; Ajzen, 1991). Among these theories, the theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) has been particularly prominent and widely utilized. The theory of planned behaviour focuses on identifying factors that influence an individual's intention, including Attitude Towards Behavior (ATB), Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC), and Subjective Norms (SN). Some other researchers also simplified and classified these factors into three different parameters that can be easily be understood in a business context; Personal experience, Social Influencers, and Self-efficacy (Edi et al., 2019; Al-Swidi et al., 2014; Markman et al., 2005).

Research question three : 'What factors influence SMEs' desire to develop the intentions to undertake entrepreneurial training initiatives?'

In Africa, there has been a drastic increase in population which creates a problem of unemployment. Many individuals rely massively on the government for employment in developing countries (Rachmanwan et al., 2015; Amato et., al 2018). This makes entrepreneurial training necessary to promote the concept of entrepreneurship intention, which highlights job creation. Recently entrepreneurial training has become an avenue for promoting sustainable economic development. In the business context, personal experience represents the business insight acquired either before or with their business operation (Andreas et al., 2006). As Mai and Gu (2012) described earlier in 5.3.1, they suggested that personal experience positively and negatively influences individuals' intentions. This aligns with ATB propounded in Ajzen's (1991) model, which defines the strength of an individual's behaviour to achieve a particular purpose. This implies that entrepreneurs' intentions depend

on their previous experience. These experiences may be either positive or negative (Chinomona et al., 2020). In a different context, social influencer best replaces SN in Ajzen (1991) in the planned behaviour model theory. Rachmanwan et al. (2015) described social influencers as family, friends, co-workers, teachers, and tutors. Their argument was based on the fact that these individuals play a crucial role in influencing SMEs' intentions. Whereas PBC also replaces self-efficacy in a real business context.

Even though the Ajzen model is widely used by most researchers when investigating individuals' intentions, it is also associated with some limitations. For example, a generalisation of the model varies from different cultures and scenarios. Ajzen suggested that the importance of ATB, SN, and PBC are different among individuals' behaviour. To address the concerns of entrepreneurs' intentions in various countries that bring instability to SMEs, multiple governments need to pay critical attention to SMEs and promote SMEs' business.

4.6 Conclusion

Certain motivating factors influence SMEs' intentions. This encompasses the thinking behaviour of the entrepreneur and expected rewards in the long or short term (wages or income, opportunities to satisfy personal needs). From this chapter, it is believed that a cognitive style is a practical approach to explaining the motivating factors behind people's behaviour and intentions through the individual's personal traits. Furthermore, the process model approach highlights the motivating factors that influence an individual's intentions as a result of expected rewards in the form of wages or income and opportunities to satisfy personal needs.

In addition, the Personal experience of entrepreneurs has a positive or negative impact on their intention SMEs. Personal experience can be used to represent all the real business-related insights and encounters by entrepreneurs either before or within the business

operation. Social influencers such as family, friends, co-workers, and teachers/tutors are one of the core influences of the intentions of SMEs. Entrepreneurs' self-efficacy is influenced by their intentions to create jobs and maintain a stable intent. Self-efficacy defines the intrinsic belief of an individual's core competence to complete a task. Personal experience, Social influencers, and Self-efficacy can only influence entrepreneurial intention with entrepreneurial capacity. Entrepreneurial capacity triggers the ability to identify entrepreneurial opportunities or entrepreneurial intentions.

Numerous research studies have emphasized the positive correlation between entrepreneurial training and intentions, but several factors have affected the outcomes. These include the sample size and the selection of dependent and independent variables. Many studies have predominantly focused on students, neglecting established entrepreneurs, contributing to variations in the final results. Acknowledging the limitations that have influenced previous findings, this thesis aims to investigate the impact of entrepreneurial training through methodologically robust studies. Specifically, this study will examine how entrepreneurial training influences the intentions of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), with a particular focus on the relationship between intention and self-employment. Additionally, this thesis will explore the role of entrepreneurial trigger events as key research components within this research study.

Chapter 5: Methodological Review

This chapter explicitly explains how the research will be executed by explaining various research concepts from research philosophies, population and sample size, how the data was collected and analysed, the rationale behind various variables and themes adopted for the study. This chapter outlines the various key aspects of data collection and analysis for this study. This section begins with a detailed description of previous studies, participant sampling strategy, Pilot studies, and rationale for the interview's approach to collecting data.

The methodological approach then goes into this study's specific data collection methods and instrumentation. The following section outlines the expected data analysis collected through these instruments. A section on credibility and reliability then lays out the various ways this methodological approach is structured to collect accurate and suitable data, and the ethics section layouts how this study prioritises the treatment of the participants selection. Finally, the last section discusses the delimitations that bound this study as well as the study's limitations. In an attempt to address the impact of entrepreneurial training, as discussed in chapter 2, most studies indicate that most of the research had methodological constraints. These constraints range from not categorising the core concept of the study into suitable themes, the sample size, duration of the entrepreneurial training, and the target population.

5.1 Previous studies

Most research on entrepreneurial intentions in Sub-Saharan Africa focuses on some aspects of the end-users of entrepreneurial training. For example, most studies conducted in the past two decades are mostly centred around students (Nafukho & Helen, 2010; Yabashaija & Katono, 2011; Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013; O'Leary, 2017). Students are just one aspect of the end-users of entrepreneurial training. There has been colossal neglect or little research on some core aspects of the 'end users' such as actual

entrepreneurs or SMEs. This aspect includes SMEs, researchers, and institutions (Amato et., al 2018). This is because these critical stakeholders who are perceived to be the 'end users' of EET have the potential influence to transpire, encourage and transform their intentions as entrepreneurs. In other to achieve this, an appropriate methodological approach should be selected.

In a longitudinal study conducted by Lorz (2011), the impact of entrepreneurial education on individuals' entrepreneurial intentions was examined over 18 months. The study employed a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative components. The quantitative segment utilized a quasi-experimental research design known as the 'ex-ante/ex-post study, control group,' involving a sample size of 272 completely matched participants.

The study employed the theory of planned behaviour as the theoretical framework to assess students' intentions towards entrepreneurship, following similar approaches taken by Murray et al. (2018) and Alexandria et al. (2014) in their studies. Regression models were employed to analyze the data. Although the findings did not show a significant impact of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention, they indicated the importance of entrepreneurial education in triggering individuals' intentions.

Interestingly, the findings suggested that individuals who became self-employed at the end of their entrepreneurship programs had higher entrepreneurial intentions at the start of the program compared to those who did not become self-employed. While the direct relationship between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention was not found to be statistically significant, the study emphasized the crucial role of entrepreneurial education as a catalyst for fostering individuals' intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities.

The study highlights the significance of entrepreneurial education in influencing individuals' entrepreneurial intentions. It provides insights into the complex dynamics between entrepreneurial education, self-employment outcomes, and the initial intentions of individuals. These findings provided the importance of incorporating effective entrepreneurial education programs that impart knowledge and skills and inspire and motivate individuals to pursue entrepreneurship. Such initiatives can play a vital role in nurturing the entrepreneurial ecosystem and fostering an entrepreneurial culture.

Furthermore, Murray et al. (2018) argued that understanding the end-users of entrepreneurial education provide the conceptual understanding of the "behaviour, emotions, perspectives and experiences" of the core value within the educational establishments. However, their research focuses primarily on students as the fundamental concept of their study area. With respect to their findings, it emerges that critical attention should be examined to identify key personalities for the successful implementation of entrepreneurial training or education to achieve the best practice of entrepreneurial training and education.

Similarly, Alexandria et al. (2014) incorporated a different dimension by conducting a study to understand how entrepreneurial training and education impact the intentions of students and actual entrepreneurs. Their study proposed a conceptual framework which aids in understanding entrepreneurship programs taught in schools. They adopted a study approach consisting of a heterogeneous program divided into entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention. The study consisted of a purposive sample size which comprises students (secondary and post-secondary) and actual entrepreneurs. Their argument for such an approach was that the dimension of entrepreneurial education and training demands have different target groups.

Akinso (2018) explored several strategies small businesses in Nigeria adopt to survive for the first five (5) years of operating a company. Jones et al. (2018) argued that most businesses in Africa fail between three to 5 years of operation. Akinso (2018) adopted a qualitative methodological approach to investigate the rationale with 'what' and 'why' questions. The study was centred around a research design where multiple case studies of entrepreneurs in the 'soybeans processing sector were analysed. Furthermore, Bryman (2015) suggest that the best way to examine and understand the motivation behind a phenomenon is simply by asking 'what' and 'why' questions. This approach was essential for the study as it helped the researcher to identify and investigate human behaviour with limited emphasis on numeric data, as posited by (Bryman, 2015). It is crucial to shift research focus on entrepreneurial intentions in Sub-Saharan Africa away from being exclusively centred on students and towards a more comprehensive examination of actual entrepreneurs or SMEs. While previous studies have predominantly concentrated on students' entrepreneurial intentions (Nafukho & Helen, 2010; Yabashaija & Katono, 2011; Owusu-Ansah, 2012; Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013; O'Leary, 2017), this narrow perspective fails to address the holistic ecosystem of entrepreneurship. Real-world entrepreneurs and SMEs represent entrepreneurial training programs' ultimate beneficiaries and implementers. Neglecting their perspectives and experiences overlooks critical insights into the challenges, motivations, and decision-making processes of those actively engaged in entrepreneurship. By shifting the conversation towards actual entrepreneurs and SMEs, research can provide more practical and actionable insights to inform policies, interventions, and support mechanisms that directly impact the success and sustainability of businesses in Sub-Saharan Africa. This shift is essential for a more comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape and for crafting effective strategies to foster regional entrepreneurship.

To address the intended research question, a step-by-step methodological approach was adopted to understand the study area. exploratory study will be employed to understand and address the various alarming research questions in Chapter 1.4.0. consist of a qualitative method to bridge the gaps identified in the literature. The study's geographical area consists of two countries (Ghana and Kenya) with other policies and strategies initiated to support SME activities in the sub-Saharan region, with Scotland as the area for the pilot studies.

5.2 Research Population

This research undertaking is an exploratory study aimed at examining the diverse factors that impact the intentions of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The study was conducted in two African countries, Ghana and Kenya. In the methodology section of this research, the data collection approach emphasises that entrepreneurs are the main point of contact. By focusing on entrepreneurs as the central subjects of our study, This approach aimed to gain deeper insights into their intentions, actions, and the influence of entrepreneurial education and training on their decision-making processes.

In the western part of Africa, Ghana is home to an approximate population of 30 million individuals within the region (World Bank data, 2020; ILO, 2020). In terms of economic growth, Ghana experienced an increase in its annual GDP from 6.3 percent in 2018 to 6.5 percent in 2019 (IMF data, 2020).

In Kenya, SMEs, including micro-enterprises, employ a significant portion of the workforce, accounting for approximately 81.1% of employment, contributing 5.6% to the country's GDP (ILO, 2020). Until 2014, Kenya was regarded as one of the fastest-developing nations in the Sub-Saharan region. However, it should be noted that the World Bank currently classifies the country as a low-income nation.

This study aims to shed light on the unique dynamics by investigating the specific contexts of sub-Saharan Africa; Ghana and Kenya. It influences that shape the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in these respective countries.

5.2.1 Sample Frame

The sample of the study consist of 22 entrepreneurs (owners/managers) from diverse business (manufacturing, service and tourism industry). However, the pilot studies was done in scotland. the approach of traveling to Ghana and Kenya, which were the main countries for the subsequent studies, was affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. This logistical challenge made it more practical to conduct initial research in Scotland, which was more accessible at the time.

Table 5.1 Demographic of participant from Ghana

SAMPLES	DEMOGRAPHICS					
GHANA	Gender	Nature of business	Educational Level	Previous work experience	Years of Business operation	Number of employees
GH-1001	Male	Service	Degree	No	9	22
GH-1002	Male	Manufacturing	Degree	Yes	6	17
GH-1003	Female	Service	Degree	Yes	3	15
GH-1004	Male	Service	Degree	No	3	11
GH-1005	Male	Manufacturing	Degree	Yes	4	25
GH-1006	Female	Service	Degree	Yes	8	20
GH-1007	Female	Service	Masters	Yes	10	31
GH-1008	Female	Service	Masters	Yes	9	35
GH-1009	Male	Service	Degree	Yes	5	22
GH-1010	Female	Manufacturing	Masters	Yes	15	45
GH-1011	Male	Manufacturing	Degree	Yes	6	18

Source: (Data collection, 2022)

Table 5.2 Demographic of participant from Kenya

SAMPLES	DEMOGRAPHICS					
	Gender	Nature of business	Educational Level	Previous work experience	Years of Business operation	Number of employees
KY-1001	Female	Service	Masters	Yes	4	20
KY-1002	Female	Service	Degree	Yes	3	32
KY-1003	Male	Tourism	Degree	Yes	7	35
KY-1004	Female	Manufacturing	Degree	Yes	4	11
KY-1005	Male	Tourism	Masters	No	3	10
KY-1006	Male	Service	Degree	Yes	8	41
KY-1007	Female	Manufacturing	Degree	Yes	9	36
KY-1008	Female	Service	Degree	Yes	14	23
KY-1009	Female	Tourism	Degree	Yes	5	22
KY-1010	Female	Service	Degree	Yes	9	20
KY-1011	Male	Manufacturing	Degree	Yes	11	45

Source: (Data collection, 2022)

The rationale for selection of each participant for the study only required to have established and operating your business for at least three years and above. This is because Jones et al. (2018) argued that most businesses in Africa fail between three to 5 years of operation. The study consisted of 10 male's ad 12 females in both countries. The sample of selection was snowball sampling. Understand the outcome of the study was based on SMEs (owners/ managers) willingness to participate in the explorations of the impact of entrepreneurial training on intentions of SMEs. The is no direct relations which impacted or affected the outcome of the study. The perception of SMEs and their experiences has the tendency to influence the intentions and underpin measures to their survival. The purpose of

this research examines how entrepreneurial training and education influence SMEs intentions.

SMEs manager and owners we contacted through an approved consent form to participate in the study, which adopted a snowball sampling approach. Aggarwal, (2011) and Elikem and Ofori, (2020) suggested that definite subjects and traits for inclusion for the purpose of the study ensure the results of the study are appropriate. Snowball sampling involved an appropriate approach that business owners or SMEs (owners or managers) who the necessary experience ranging of a minimum of three (3) to five (5) years at topmost or managerial level (Jones et al. 2018; Saunders et al., 2016; Collis and Hussey, 2014; Elikem and Ofori, 2020).

Key Criteria Inclusion

1. Geographically, Ghana and Kenya are two countries located in different regions of Africa. Ghana is in the western part of Africa, while Kenya is in the eastern part of the continent.
2. To participate in this study, businesses in Ghana and Kenya must have existed for a minimum period of three years or more. This requirement ensures that the selected businesses have a certain level of establishment and longevity.
3. The study focuses on managers and business owners as the target participants. These individuals play a crucial role in shaping the direction and decision-making within their respective businesses. By including managers and business owners, the study aims to capture their perspectives and insights into the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions in SMEs.
4. SMEs category;

Kenya

- I. Size- Small (0-49), Medium (50-99) and Large (100+) employees.

II. Turnover- Small (\$5,000 to \$50,000), Medium (\$ 50,000 to \$8 million) and Large (\$8 million)

Ghana

I. Size- Small (0-29), Medium (30-99) and Large (100+) employees

II. Assets- firms cannot be classified as SMEs if their Fixed assets exceed 10 million Ghanaian cedis (£1.25 million)

5. Must be a registered business and on the government business register

Snowball sampling allows the selection through referrals who might best understand the influence of entrepreneurial training on SMEs survival. Snowball sampling has been considered as a vital sample approach of non-probability sampling adopted for this research study.

5.3 Methodological Approach

The research will follow a systematic approach to address the various gaps identified in the literature review. Various gaps identified will aid to bridge and provide a critical understanding of the study area. An exploratory qualitative methodological approach was employed for the studies. This approach was adapted to explore new insights and trend into a relatively new area of research. This will help understand the rationale behind with ‘how’ and ‘why’ research questions to address the aim of the study. This will help address methodological errors in early research and provide a variable approach to enhance future errors and shortcomings in earlier research.

Table 5.3 Methodological Approach

<i>Approach</i>	Exploratory qualitative	<i>Explore new insights and trend into a relatively new area of research. The result</i>
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of exploration findings helps the researcher not to base on assumption or generalization (Elikem and Ofori, 2020)

<i>Philosophy</i>	Interpretivism	Interpretive standpoint. This is because the research rationale obtained information relating to the judgments, attitudes, and behaviours individuals have about entrepreneurial training towards SMEs' intentions (Tessier, 2012; Saunders et al. 2012)
<i>Strategy</i>	Qualitative	Phenomenological research involves the researcher's active participation in conducting interviews with respondents, using probing questions to gain a deeper understanding of their thought processes and the development of their ideas. The primary aim of this thesis is to gather information regarding individuals' judgments, attitudes, and behaviours, focusing on exploring their subjective experiences and perceptions (Elikem and Ofori, 2020).
<i>Method(s)</i>	(Interview guide-Primary data) and (Journal reviews, website, archives	Each data collected was linked to both the research questions and the conceptual framework. The interview guide instrument

	– Secondary data)	is directly from the gap, knowledge and influence identified in the literature review
<i>Sample & Technique</i>	Snowball sampling	22 SMEs (owners/managers) from diverse business (manufacturing, service and tourism industry).
<i>Analytical Approach</i>	Thematic methods	Inductive thematic analysis was adopted to identify themes strongly connected to the data rather than existing research (Clarke et al., 2015).

5.3.1 Research Philosophy

Numerous academics have recognized the importance of establishing the philosophical framework underlying a research project, as it helps clarify its main objectives and purpose (Quinlan, 2011; Fielding, 2012). Two philosophical perspectives can be adopted when conducting a research project: positivism and interpretivism.

Positivism is associated with the traditional research approaches where beliefs are critically understood in reality's objectives where truths are determined through empiric observations and scientific evidence (Babbie, 2016). In the works of Collis and Hussey (2014), they argued that positivists adopt a realist ontological approach about the nature of reality which the accepted truth is deduced through a quantitative methodological approach. As suggested by Bryman (2016), this standpoint point of positivism involves observation of experiments and fact-gathering through scientific methods. In reality, a scientific approach like the selections process, measuring variables and analysing data may differ from the hypothesis only if the researcher is unbiased (Vanderstoep and Johnston, 2009; Dube and Naidoo 2020). Based on the argument, the positivist knowledge regarding reality can be rationalised by

justifying and verifying through mathematical evidence and hypothesis as supported by (Vanderstoep and Johnston, 2009; Collis and Hussey 2014; Dube and Naidoo 2020).

On the contrary, the interpretive perspective appreciates subjectivity and upholds the ontological belief that there are different adaptations of reality and truth in the social world (Daymon and Holloway, 2011; Tessier, 2012). These imply that every individual has their unique version of the reality of the social world. According to Saunders et al. (2012), these different versions of unique interpretations can be found through individuals' personal experience and beliefs. Furthermore, in support of this argument, Bryman (2016) highlighted that interpretivism phenomenology concerns the understanding of how individuals make sense of the reality of the world around them. Given these arguments, Hammond, and Wellington (2013), viewed that the interpretive looks at internal traits that influence the thinking and actions of humans regarding social activity in the real world.

Based on the two philosophical perspectives, this research adopts a phenomenological approach and embraces an interpretive standpoint. The rationale behind this choice is to gather insights into individuals' perceptions, attitudes, and behaviours regarding entrepreneurial training and its impact on SMEs' intentions.

As discussed in chapter one and chapter four, the selected countries have different policies, culture and business operation environment. It is vital to adopt a exploratory approach to understand the various background. This is because Bryman (2007) suggested a cross-sectional system gathers information from a pool of different participants possessed with other demographic traits or variables. The result of exploration findings helps the researcher not to base on assumption or generalisation. However, it provides a podium for the researcher to project the study's actual findings on facts and figures based on specifically adapted thematic variables employed for the research or analysis. Bryman (2007) suggested that a

cross-sectional study eliminate assumption and reinstate reality based on factual data based on used variables in the study area during a specific period. The researcher adopted a cross-sectional exploratory approach for the study because the study will elaborate more to generate an insight into the research area to understand the study area at a specific time critically. As Davis (2015) described, many barriers such as fear of business failure/collapse, marketing, experience, and inadequate ways to mitigate risk influence SMEs' intention, especially in their early business operation stages. This discourages most promising entrepreneurs from venturing into entrepreneurial and Small and Medium Enterprises. This issue demands an interpretive approach to understand the research area.

Bryman (2016) reflects on Taylor's (1975) perspective, which highlights that interpretivism aims to comprehend individuals' actions by considering their own perspectives and gaining a profound understanding of their behaviour within their natural environment. Consequently, since there are multiple subjective realities within the research subject, each entrepreneur will express their own unique perceptions, knowledge, and beliefs, thereby enriching the understanding of the research topic.

5.3.2 Qualitative

This study's research design was qualitative, which aligns with the interpretivism research paradigm approach of earlier researchers (Saunders et al., 2016; Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). Qualitative research designs are characterised by their association with an interpretive philosophy and their emphasis on understanding and interpreting phenomena in-depth, enhancing the findings' validity (Davis, 2015).

This thesis disparity to quantitative research focuses on testing and generalising findings from a specific context to a larger population. In contrast, qualitative research approaches offer a more nuanced and contextualised understanding of the research topic (Bryman, 2015). The aim of theory development drove this study's adoption of a qualitative

research design. The researchers sought to explore and develop a comprehensive theoretical perspective on entrepreneurship models that goes beyond the existing knowledge available in the literature (Saunders et al., 2016; Collis & Hussey, 2014).

By employing a qualitative research design, the study aimed to capture the richness and complexity of entrepreneurial phenomena and gain a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences and perspectives. This approach allowed for a natural and emergent research design, facilitating the exploration of new and unexplored dimensions of entrepreneurship (Saunders et al., 2016; Collis & Hussey, 2014).

The qualitative research design adopted in this study provides a podium and the opportunity to delve into the complexities of entrepreneurial training and its influence on entrepreneurial intentions. It allows for a holistic exploration of the subject matter, considering the social, cultural, and personal factors that shape individuals' perceptions and motivations in the entrepreneurial context. Through in-depth interviews, observations, and thematic analysis, the study aimed to generate rich and nuanced insights that contribute to developing motivation factors, intention theory, and factors that trigger entrepreneurial training and expand our understanding of the intricate dynamics of entrepreneurship in the African context. Moreover, Safura (2017) notes that a qualitative research design is most suitable when prior knowledge is scarce. This viewpoint is supported by other researchers (Daymon & Holloway, 2011; Tessier, 2012; Saunders et al., 2016). This indicates that a qualitative research design is essential for exploratory investigations, as it allows flexibility in addressing unexpected issues and unstructured problems that may arise due to limited insights. Therefore, a qualitative-exploratory research design was employed to explore the underlying concepts and themes relevant to developing a novel theory on the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in Ghana and Kenya. Given the lack of recent literature on SMEs'

intentions in these countries, a realistic and inductive exploration was undertaken to investigate these notions.

5.3.3 Quality evaluation of the research

Assessing the quality of the study area is crucial to ensure consistent and accurate results. According to Wilson (2014), two primary aspects that can impact the quality of a study are validity and reliability. Therefore, it is essential to consider validity and reliability when researching to ensure that it effectively measures what it aims to measure.

Walliman (2016) defines validity as the extent to which research findings accurately represent the phenomenon being studied. Building upon the work of Filmer (1998), who identified three key types of validity, Walliman highlights the following:

Measurement validity: This refers to the degree to which the measures used in the study effectively capture the concepts they are intended to assess.

Internal validity: It pertains to the strength of causal relationships established within the study, indicating the extent to which the observed effects can be attributed to the variables under investigation.

External validity: This type of validity addresses the generalizability of study results to other populations and settings, assessing whether the findings can be applied beyond the specific context in which the research was conducted.

In summary, Walliman emphasises the importance of ensuring that measures are valid, causal relationships are robust, and the findings have relevance beyond the immediate study population and environment.

Bryman (2016) further identifies ecological validity, which questions whether research findings relate to people's everyday natural social settings.

Validity in qualitative research, although often associated with quantitative studies, can also be assessed in qualitative inquiries by focusing on the credibility and truthfulness of the findings (Maxwell, 2013). In qualitative research, validity is determined by the richness and quality of the data collected rather than the sheer quantity, highlighting the significance of capturing participants' perspectives accurately to represent the phenomena being studied. To enhance validity, researchers often employ triangulation techniques. One approach is to compare and contrast the perspectives of different participants, recognising that each individual brings a unique interpretation of the topic that can uncover patterns or discrepancies. Another form of triangulation involves comparing the collected data with established theoretical frameworks proposed by reputable scholars, which assists in interpreting the subject matter.

As discussed by Crowther and Lancaster (2008), reliability refers to the consistency or repeatability of data collected across different instances. It is the ability to produce consistent results, as highlighted by Lorz (2011). Walliman (2016), building on Bryman's (2012) work, identified three critical components of reliability: stability (consistency over time), internal reliability (homogeneity of measures), and interobserver consistency (consistency among multiple observers in recording observations or interpreting data). These definitions primarily pertain to quantitative research and measuring reliability and replicability in qualitative research presents additional challenges due to its subjective nature. To maintain rigorous standards, the researcher in this study adopted a meticulous approach by referring to studies published in highly reputable journals.

Reliability is closely associated with dependability in qualitative research, which involves adopting an auditing approach to maintain comprehensive documentation of all aspects of the research process (Bryman & Bell, 2015). To enhance dependability, this study utilizes audio recordings and transcriptions of the interviews, ensuring a systematic, precise, and coherent analysis (Fern, 2001). However, since this is a phenomenological study, the researcher actively engages with the respondents during the interviews, potentially introducing subjectivity and affecting the reliability of the data. To mitigate this risk, the presence of multiple observers can help counterbalance the impact of the interviewer's subjectivity on the analysis (Babbie, 2016).

5.4 Pilot Study

The pilot study was conducted to identify potential problem and deficiencies in the research methodology prior to its implementation in the main studies.

Table 6.2 (Pilot) Rationale of geographical and research context

<i>Country</i>	Population (2020) million	SMEs Business %	SMEs employment contribution	Definitions of SMEs
(Pilot) Scotland	5.46	99.3 %	86.9%	1. Size-Small (0-49), Medium (50-249) and large (250+) employees 2. Annual Turnover- Small (£ 8.2 Million), Medium (£ 41 Million)
Ghana	31.07	92%	71%	1. Size- Small (0-29), Medium (30-99) and Large (100+) employees 2. Assets- firms cannot be classified as SMEs if their Fixed assets exceed 10 million Ghanaian cedis (£1.25 million)
Kenya	53.77	95%	81.1%	1. Size- Small (0-49), Medium (50-99) and Large (100+) employees.

2. Turnover- Small (\$5,000 to \$50,000), Medium (\$ 50,000 to \$8 million) and Large (\$8 million)

Source: (*Business in Scotland, 2018; World Bank data 2020; Budget Reports 2019-Ghana, Kenya*)

The table above provides an overview of countries selected for the studies. These countries have a unique and slightly similar trait regarding SMEs. Findings and outcomes obtained from the diverse methods have the potential power to address the identified problem in question.

The reason for choosing these countries involves several parameters.

First and foremost, Scotland (Edinburgh and Glasgow) was selected for the pilot studies because the objective of this research is to devise an appropriate methodological approach that will be universal accepted to predict SMEs intention in connection to entrepreneurial training. The researcher deemed it vital to test the methodological approach on a different experimental geographical area since selected countries have strategic policies to promote SMEs activities.

Research Objectives;

- ▶ Devise and construct an appropriate exploratory methodological approach to analyse whether entrepreneurial training predicts SMEs' behaviour.
- ▶ Collect and analyse various factors that influence SMEs' stability of entrepreneurial intention after entrepreneurial training
- ▶ To comment and conclude on the key events that trigger entrepreneurship training initiatives and displaying key contributions.

This approach is essential because this allows the researcher to investigate and understand the cause, effect and relationships that exist between different thematic variables in different

locations. Fielding (2012) suggested that different experimental groups with similar traits such as age, sex, location, level of education, culture allows the researcher to understand and compare the effect and relationship of the underlined variables. *Secondly*, the selected countries for the pilot and primary studies have SMEs contribution to over 90% of businesses in the respective countries. *Thirdly*, from the table above, SMEs contribute over 70% to total employment in respective countries. *Fourth*, There are slightly similar classification of SMEs of respective countries **Scotland** (Small 0-49, Medium 50-249), **Ghana** (Small 0-29, Medium 30-99) and **Kenya** (Small 0-49, Medium 50-99).

Scotland was chosen as the location for the pilot studies due to several reasons:

1. It has a rich history of entrepreneurship.
2. The presence of African-owned businesses.
3. The logistical considerations related to the COVID-19 pandemic with massive travel restrictions across the globe.
4. Scotland and Africa have strong connections through initiatives to tackle poverty, food security, and education.

These factors provide a solid foundation for researching entrepreneurship and related topics in both regions.

Pilot Studies Process

The pilot studies process consists of three systematic stages; Feasibility of the study; Recruitment of participant and Data analysis.

Figure 4: Pilot studies process

Sample Description

The study area began with pilot studies in Scotland, consisting of **eight (8) Small and Medium Enterprises in Edinburgh and Glasgow**. In total, four (4) SMEs from Edinburgh and three (4) from Glasgow. This approach informs the researcher of the best methodological approach to adapting to the primary studies (Ghana and Kenya). The Pilot studies presented a small sample size of 8 SMEs. Furthermore, the majority of entrepreneurs interviewed for the pilot studies were owners of African-owned businesses in cities like Glasgow and Edinburgh. This connection between African entrepreneurs and Scotland adds depth to the research context and allows for a diverse range of perspectives. However, a total of 20 emails was sent to SMEs listed on the business registry in two major cities in Scotland (Edinburgh-10 and Glasgow-10). Snowball non-probability technique, which involves obtaining participant through referrals, was adapted (Bryman, 2007; Jackson, 2012). This approach allows easy access to collect data swiftly and less cost-effective (Tessier, 2012). However, many scholars have criticised this approach of Snowball non-probability sampling, which argues that the

findings' authenticity may be at risk because they do not represent the entire population because the researcher tends to demonstrate selection bias regarding the subject area (Bryman and Bell, 2015). However, the researcher's approach to this sampling method looks to acquire deep understanding and insight through exploratory research, which (Lorz 2011) adapted this sampling approach reliable for exploratory study. However, the recent coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has massively affected human life and mounted high pressure on the business environment, which has inversely impacted business many businesses worldwide. The researcher deems it necessary that this sampling was appropriate to reach out to participant. Furthermore In terms of the link between Scotland and Africa, there are several notable connections. Scotland has a history of forming alliances with African countries to promote entrepreneurship and address key issues related to sustainable development goals. For instance, Scotland's Social Enterprise Academy established a partnership with selected Sub-Saharan African countries to promote social enterprises among young entrepreneurs (Allan, 2017). This collaboration was aimed at addressing poverty, a shared concern in both Scotland and Africa, as SMEs in both regions play a significant role in employment and business activity.

Data collection

The data collection approach employed in this study involved conducting in-depth interviews with SME owners and managers. This approach was chosen to gather detailed insights into the participants' attitudes, behaviours, and intentions regarding the subject area. By utilizing in-depth interviews, the researcher aimed to provide a platform for entrepreneurs to express their perspectives and experiences within their respective trade areas in the real world. Previous research by Granot et al. (2012) emphasizes that in-depth interviews are particularly suited for exploring participant experiences and interpreting their understanding of those experiences.

Through these interviews, the researcher sought to understand the participants' viewpoints comprehensively, allowing for a deep exploration of their thoughts, motivations, and challenges. The in-depth interview method offers the flexibility to delve into specific topics, probe for detailed responses, and uncover nuanced insights that may not be captured through other data collection methods. It allows participants to share their unique perspectives and contribute valuable firsthand knowledge to the study.

By utilizing the in-depth interview approach, the researcher aimed to generate rich qualitative data to shed light on the intricacies of entrepreneurial experiences and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the influences on SMEs' attitudes, behaviours, and intentions in the selected African countries.

Data Analysis

Entrepreneurial Education/Training

Entrepreneurship training can be argued as the conscious effort to organise, plan and develop a systematic approach to modify, acquire knowledge and skills through learning experiences, which is vital to enhance performances in several activities (Hynes 1996). Ojala and Heikkilä (2011) also viewed entrepreneurship training as providing relevant and pedagogical training for entrepreneurs who have a viable business idea. The Participants view of entrepreneurial training was centred around building upon capacity, skills, and technical know-how to improve performance and productivity.

The concept of entrepreneurial training as defined across the interviews to participant as some participants were in a dilemma about whether they influence entrepreneurs' intention.

“... had entrepreneurial training before I commenced my business ... had the opportunity to undertake training that involves risk assessment, understanding people, and how people react to different situations from different backgrounds” (G1, 2021).

“...starting my business required entrepreneurial training to ensure my business run smoothly.” -(E4, 2021).

“...periodic training is important ...to ensure business success” (G4, 2021)

All participant acknowledged entrepreneurial training as an essential aspect of an individual's intention to establish and a run business because such training tends to offer crucial support and skill to promote growth as described by (Murray et al., 2018). Furthermore, G1, 2021 and E4, 2021 statement explicates the importance of entrepreneurial training towards their entrepreneur's intention. This confirms the principal role of entrepreneurship education and business training cannot be underestimated. From chapter 3.3, Alsheikh's (2009) research findings indicated that business training services provide the necessary training that helps entrepreneurs start, expand and sustain their business while entrepreneurship education triggers individuals' interest in entrepreneurship (Swanson and Morrison, 2010).

However, these entrepreneurs G1, 2021 and E4, 2020 indicated that such training helped them to understand some basic parameters surrounding everyday business endeavours such as risk assessment, customer service, operational activities and under situations and employees from different background. G4 also suggested the periodic training create awareness to ensure business success. This is because constant entrepreneurial training awareness aims to enhance the scope of knowledge surrounding entrepreneurship and individuals adopting a positive attitude to trigger the intent to self-employment. Participants view about view of entrepreneurial training supports the earlier research findings of (Short et al., 2010; Shonubi and Taiwo, 2013; Koe and Majid 2014; Ndofirepi and Rambe 2017; Alakaleek, 2019).

However, some participant debunked the fact that entrepreneurial training is the key approach to attain positive intention towards entrepreneurship.

“...I successful operate my business without any entrepreneurial training” (G2, 2021).

“... I knew basic skills on how the business is managed ... from my previous job ... I didn't need any training” (E2, 2021).

“...without entrepreneurial training most business in my industry can survive” (G3, 2021).

These participants acknowledge the importance of entrepreneurship, but however, believes that their business will be successful without entrepreneurial training. They believe *entrepreneurial training taught in schools is not the primary trigger to influence their intentions*. This confirms Gibb (1993) viewed that enterprise training is streamline from a restrictive business context, which is perceive as the prime factor behind several failed attempts to mainstream entrepreneurship education.

Nevertheless, the advantage of entrepreneurial training from schools and universities, as indicated in the literature review, the analysed data's findings do not fully support the underlined perception. This is because some of the respondents criticised the nature of entrepreneurial education argued that *“...difficult to see some sort of practical entrepreneurial training from the universities...because I never had that practical opportunity” (E2,2021)*. Even though (E2,2021) had the opportunity to entrepreneurial education, the respondent expresses that universities do not have the avenue to expose students to learn practically. Furthermore, *“... I never had any mentor because universities do not provide an avenue for a business mentor.” (E4,2021)*. This confirms Henry et al. (2015) that confusions emanating from whether taught and untaught entrepreneurship are demands review.

6.2 Apprenticeship Training

Another participant mention that ... *"from my experience, I will recommend to anybody to have some apprenticeship training before they start their business"* (E4, 2021). From Baloch et al. (2017) research works they suggested that apprenticeship at an entry-level for entrepreneurs is an important measure to acquire necessary skills which is fantastic for potential and promising entrepreneurs to gain a background understanding of their chosen business line. Furthermore, another participant suggests that *"...apprenticeship training serves as a bonus to a business because it makes managing their business easier to operate"* (G1,2021). This statement makes apprenticeship training a unique avenue to manage a business practice. This statement supports Lorz (2011) argument, which described apprenticeship training as procedures of learning entrepreneurial activities in the real world without the restrictions placed on traditional classrooms based on the only place to learn and examine.

In light of the above, another participant mentioned that **"apprenticeship gives real exposure to the business of interest...at early stages"** (E2,2021; G4,2021). This statement implies that apprenticeship experience is a fantastic opportunity to empower entrepreneurs at the initial stage of their career path. In support of this argument, Nkirina (2010) indicated that apprenticeship is a planning stage to progressively understand the defining features of how to apply, develop, and apply all the functional aptitude in the business ecosystem. This views by these participants shows how important apprenticeship training is important. ***This Promote the rationale behind why the UK government continues increase apprentices' wages over the years as a strategic measure to lure and promote young and upcoming entrepreneurs into apprenticeship training.***

2.3 Personal Experience

Personal experience was identified as a theme as some respondents concur that it serves as an important element in relation in start a business.

“... I decided to start my own business because of a past experience in my previous job... benefit I was getting from my previous jobs; it was not appropriate enough”. (G1, 2021).

“... My parent had a similar business when I was young... I acquire the skills from the them and I was eager to continue from where they left” (G3, 2021)

“... not appreciated and I was not getting what I wanted so I quit and started my own business...got to the time I was to be promoted at work, it was given to some else”. (E2, 2021).

“My decision to become an entrepreneur was as result of a bad experience. I was working tirelessly, putting in a lot of work and was not getting recognition for what I was entitled to and not also being acknowledged”. (E4, 2021).

These entrepreneurs attributed personal experience as their primary source of motivation to start their business. Personal experience plays a crucial and significant role in the intention of entrepreneurs to start their business. Entrepreneurs' personal experiences and past experiences affect their cognitive way of thinking in a new business adventure. Statements from G3, 2021 and E2, 2021 suggest the trigger point for personal experience can be a positive or negative. This is because Vaillant and Lafuente (2019) pinpointed that a new variation in experience explains the rationale behind why entrepreneurs differ from one another. The justification for applying entrepreneurs' cognitive decisions differs from entrepreneurs who lack personal experience. This further explains the thematic deduction from the data; G1, E2, E4 attributed the motive of starting their business to a negative or destructive experience from their previous jobs. *Each participant has a different experience before starting their business*

and these were mostly negative parameters. These negative parameters relate to **lack of benefit, promotion, recognition, and acknowledgement.**

However, G3, 2021 attribute it to a positive initial event from their parent (family business). G3, 2021 initial exposure to the trade area triggers the intention to start their business. In support of this, Mai and Gu (2012) argued that earlier insight gained at the early stages of an entrepreneur's life triggers their intention to develop better and innovative ideas for the market and serve customers by responding to their basic needs and capitalising on opportunities. In view of this, participant experience both negative and positive tends to influence the intention of entrepreneurs as indicated from their statements above. These unique experiences of entrepreneurs help them expand their network base, allowing them to apply basic techniques and avoid their dislike before and during their business operation as also seen the works of earlier researchers (Mai and Gu, 2012; Ulvenblad et al., 2013).

2.4 Family and Friends support

The views shared by the participants below prove that family and friends support are very essential element in business activities. Their ideas also support the remarks made by Shonubi, and Taiwo (2013) suggested that family and friend have a direct observable concept to ensure the individual personal characteristics to behave in a particular way through motivation.

“...My friends and family have been influential in my business.... In-terms of patronising my service” (G1,2021).

“Family are friends are very important very in my business... they provide me with emotional support” (E3,2021).

“...in-terms of emotional support that are always there for me” (G4,2021).

“... support from family is fantastic... they always provide with necessary support” (E2, 2021).

All underline statement above by participant implies that most businesses need a lot of close support to succeed, whether financial, operational or emotional. Puta (2014) as cited in the literature review indicated that the most vital sources of support for many entrepreneurs are their friends and family members' network from research outcome. Furthermore, statement from (G1,2021) suggests that close relations are social creatures, and many entrepreneurs face the business world's rigours either alone or with a small staff of dedicated employees. Observation from (G1,2021, G4,2021, E2, 2021, E3,2021) responses indicated that friends and family provide that support system that can help business owners overcome stress, balance work ethics, and importantly keep up with a sense of perspective even amid the pressure and responsibility of starting and maintaining a successful business in an often-unfeeling marketplace.

2.5 Government support

Since public policies strongly influence most businesses, it is crucial to understand how policies and governmental decisions affect businesses.

“... financial support has been made available for small business struggling to survive” (G1,2021).

“... brexist, has hugely affected my business... most of my client are from EU” (E3, 2021).

“...grants for business and furlough schemes has been beneficial especially within this pandemic” (G4, 2021.)

These participants views suggest that government policies can affect business both positively and negatively. There are diverse ways that companies view and relate to government

policies and initiatives. Participants were much more focused on the impact of such policies on their business rather than their intention. (G1, 2021) and (G4, 2021) expressed how grants schemes made available are impacting their business, while (E3, 2021) views were on how Brexit has affected its customer base. Assuming all (E3, 2021) clients are EU based, the intention of (E3,2021) will decrease. This indicates why some entrepreneur's intentions are negatively influenced by some policies. However, some negative parameters came up from the interviews; *"...Government should provide the necessary support to promising entrepreneurs" (E2, 2021); "...EU client in terms of selling products to them and some tax levies recently" (E3, 2021); "...High taxes" (G2, 2021).*

To foster economic growth, government policies are designed to support individual firms and entrepreneurs through local and regional government bodies and agencies. The objective of these policies, as highlighted by Lorz (2011), is to assist new and small businesses in acquiring the necessary skills, identifying opportunities, and accessing resources. A robust business infrastructure, which includes access to private sector support services like accountants, financiers, and patent agents, is also vital for entrepreneurs. Government interventions often aim to complement these personal services by focusing on areas where market failures occur, as discussed by Boukamcha (2015). However, the findings from the interviews conducted in this study do not entirely align with this argument. Specifically, local and regional policies seek to improve access to guidance, training, finance, technology, markets, physical infrastructure, and an understanding of and adaptation to local characteristics. These policies aim to address entrepreneurs' challenges in these areas and create an enabling environment for their growth and success.

Table 6.3 Summary of key Findings

The table below indicates all the thematic findings from the from the pilot studies.

<p>Entrepreneurial Training/Education</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Not the main trigger to influence the intentions of entrepreneurs ▶ Universities helps understand basic parameters surrounding everyday business endeavours theoretically. ▶ Periodic and constant entrepreneurial training create awareness which triggers intentions of entrepreneurs ▶ Entrepreneurial training/Education in schools do not promote practical experience.
<p>Apprenticeship Training</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Unique Avenue to manage a business practically ▶ Real exposure to business
<p>Personal Experience</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Primary source of motivation to start their business ▶ Negative or destructive experience from their previous jobs key influence on entrepreneurial intention. ▶ Negative experiences (lack of benefit, promotion, recognition, and acknowledgement) at previous jobs are the main trigger point for business start-ups ▶ Positive experiences which influence entrepreneurial intentions are from enhance skills and family business.
<p>Family and Friends</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Vital sources of emotional, operational and financial support to keep entrepreneur's focus ▶ Wider client and customer base through networking ▶ Provide support system that overcome stress, balance work ethics and keep up with other personal duties
<p>Government support</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Government initiatives such as grants, taxes and business policies affect the intention of entrepreneurs

The pilot studies revealed that government initiatives such as grants, taxes and business policies affect entrepreneurs' intention.

Scotland has got a rich heritage of entrepreneurs, inventors and creative individuals. From inventing television, the telephone, among others (Herman, 2001). The Scots have a rich past achievement of entrepreneurs with innovative ideas over the years. For this entrepreneurial spirit to continue to prevail in Scottish history, the government should continue to make grants available for promising and needy business. Tax-free allowances should be given to new businesses to serve as a relief structure to upcoming entrepreneurs to maintain a positive entrepreneurial intention. Business policies are very crucial to many entrepreneurs. Findings from the literature reveal that the impact of Brexit has affected most business with strong links with other European countries in terms of networking, client and customer base. Government should also make policies that will constantly promote apprenticeship among upcoming and promising entrepreneurs. A lucrative package should be assigned to apprenticeship training because it reveals that apprenticeship exposes entrepreneurs to the real world.

In a report by Times Higher Education 2020, Scotland maintains a strong network, ten (10) in the global top 600 universities and are mainly focused on business across all sectors. However, the pilot studies' findings reveal that most entrepreneurs acknowledge the vital role entrepreneurial education and training plays in their business. They believe entrepreneurial training and education provide basic skills theoretical but do not entirely guarantee a positive entrepreneurial intention. The study's findings also suggested that entrepreneurial training/education in schools does not promote practical experience in the real world. This has to serve as a wake-up call to most higher institutions to incorporate a practical approach

to learning entrepreneurial educations in the business world. To achieve this, universities should align with actual SMEs with compulsory modules to assign each student to a particular trade area as an internship. This will enable a student to learn to apply the theoretical aspect taught in class. Furthermore, apprenticeship training should also be encouraging through higher education.

The pilot study further indicated that family and friends provide the best emotional and financial support to ensure positive intention even though some participants acknowledged that their family and friends do not understand their business's nature yet still provided the necessary support when needed.

In 2018, Scotland has an estimated 345915 private businesses operating across the country. SMEs account for about 99.3% of all sector business in Scotland. About (98.2%) were small (0 to 49 employees), 3,925 representing 1.1% were medium-sized (50 to 249 employees) and 2,380 representing 0.7% were large (250 or more employees). SMEs account for about 1.2 million jobs in Scotland. From the data, the crucial tie between entrepreneurs, family, friends and community should be strengthened. The social bonds serve as lifeline support to most businesses. Apart from these supports, in the 21st century, these social ties and bonds between these entrepreneurs and their social influencers (Friends, family and community) serve a networking, customer and client base. This will help business owners overcome stress, balance work ethics, and importantly keep up with a sense of perspective even amid the pressure and responsibility of starting and maintaining a successful business in an often-unfeeling marketplace.

5.4.1 Main Studies Consideration

The methodological approach employed in this pilot study aimed to address limitations identified in previous research. However, the study faced several challenges, primarily due to the COVID-19 pandemic, making it difficult to reach many SMEs. Face-to-face interactions

were impossible, and participants preferred phone interviews over visual ones. The researcher tried to avoid biases in data interpretation, emphasising clarity and transparency. Fisher (2011) emphasized the importance of this approach, as it allows for critique and examination of the research findings.

Transcribing and categorising the data proved to be time-consuming. The pilot study involved eight participants, which the author believed was sufficient to provide initial insights. The findings indicated the positive impact of entrepreneurial training on entrepreneurial intention and job creation. However, the study needed to differentiate between SMEs with and without entrepreneurship education/training backgrounds who had already established their businesses. Therefore, the main study will include specific questions to explore the effects of entrepreneurial training on both groups.

The outcomes and findings of the pilot study offer substantial and persuasive evidence. However, generalizing the results based on only eight participants may be limited. The preliminary study will investigate a larger sample size within a specified time frame. The main study will also define business acumen and terminology to ensure participant understanding and accurate responses. Furthermore, the main study will consider the duration of participants' businesses and how it influences their intentions to overcome challenges during difficult periods. This approach will highlight a comprehensive understanding of the long-term effects of entrepreneurial training on entrepreneurial intention across the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

In summary, the pilot study encountered challenges related to the COVID-19 pandemic and participant preferences for phone interviews. Despite these limitations, the findings highlighted the positive impact of entrepreneurial training on entrepreneurial intention. The main study will address the limitations of the pilot study by examining a larger sample size,

differentiating between participants with and without entrepreneurial training backgrounds, and considering the duration of participants' businesses.

5.5 Protocols

The research question is focused on understanding various trigger events that induce existing and upcoming SMEs to adopt positive or negative traits that influence their intentions. The goal is to understand the gap existing in literature, clear the perception factors for recent business failures, and highlight SMEs' motivation factors and how they navigate through the external environmental factors surrounding their business ecosystem

5.5.1 Data Collection Procedure

This section explicit how data was collected for analysis. The researcher started by reviewing literature for key words and contextual phrase, this helped to identify key areas to draft interview questions. In the methodology section of this research, the data collection approach emphasises that entrepreneurs are the main point of contact. By focusing on entrepreneurs as the central subjects of our study, This approach aimed to gain deeper insights into their intentions, actions, and the influence of entrepreneurial education and training on their decision-making processes. This was later followed by interviews. Each of the interview questions was connected to the key themes identified in the conceptual framework with is also connected to the research questions. Each data collected was linked to both the research questions and the conceptual framework. The interview guide instrument is directly from the gap, knowledge and influence identified in literature review of this study. The researcher used approaches of previous studies to acquire the baseline of understanding the strength of the interview guide and method of data collection. This helped to better understand the responses of data obtain from participant and further probe if deem appropriate and reasonable.

5.5.2 Interviews

Interviews are deemed to serve as a vital role in acquiring data with the goal of obtaining a detailed and deeper understanding of entrepreneurial intention and behavior (Saunders et al., 2016; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). The goal was to conduct interviews with 30 participants. Due to the nature of the study a total of 22 participant was completed. A period of one hour was scheduled for each participant. All data was collected to zoom conference due to travel restrictions and requirement in both participating countries (Ghana and Kenya) respectively.

All interviews lasted approximately one hour and was conducted by the researcher. A semi-structured interview was deployed which allowed the researcher to explore other key areas to address the aim of the study (Saunders et al., 2016). The researcher asked further questions on areas which needed clarity or further understanding in situations where participant were willing to give detailed information. A pilot studies was conducted in Scotland with SMEs who are already in business to test the interview questions to the view to make edits advancing to the main studies. This approach was to obtain a rich data from the main study areas. The interview protocol consisted of 18 questions which covers Background and Experience, Entrepreneurial Education and training, Personal Experience, Small business support and Government. The interview guide can be found in Appendix A.

5.5.3 Data Analysis

The researcher began the data analysis during the interview process. At the end of every interview section, the researcher read notes and underpinned key analytical memos to identify themes, key observation and overall view of the data. In this approach, the researcher had an idea to logically link the data obtain to address the research questions. At the end of every interview, the researcher the interview recording is listened several times and transcribed. After transcription is done, coding begins. Coding was done manually through an

Atlas.ti software which helped the researcher organise and track code across the transcripts. The researcher adopted open coding by using concepts from the theoretical framework as well as empirical codes from the primary data. In the second stage of the coding process, the researcher grouped codes into analytical codes. In the final stage of the coding process, the researcher identified the directions and themes of the analysis using the concept of the conceptual framework. This led to the findings in chapter 7.

There are several dimensions to be adapted to analyse qualitative data. These methods include ethnographic, thematic, content, biographical or conversational analysis (Tessier, 2012; Wilkinson, 2016). For this study, the researcher adopted thematic methods for its analysis. This approach includes detecting categories, also known as themes, from the data, which directly or indirectly impact the participant (Tessier,2012). The research approach underpinned contextualism, where participant shares their experience, understand the subject area and interpret how the broader social context impacts those meanings to which thematic analysis is used to unravel such realities available in the real world as described by (Braun and Clarke. 2006; Bryman, 2007).

Figure 5 Systematic thematic analysis

The thematic approach can be seen in diverse forms; inductive and deductive. Inductive thematic analysis involves identifying themes that emerge directly from the data, without being influenced by existing research. On the other hand, deductive thematic analysis involves defining themes based on existing theoretical concepts and specific research questions, allowing for a more structured and analytical approach to the research process (Clarke et al., 2015).

The research area adopted an inductive approach because the researcher used themes generated from the participant response to describe the phenomena. Braun and Clarke (2006) suggested that inductive thematic analysis stays close to the meanings understood from the original data. Because of this, existing theories and concepts can not influence the outcome of the analysis of the structure of the analysis. However, theoretical concepts are adapted to support the data collected by identifying similarities and differences, strengthening the reality presented by the participant.

5.5.4 Viability and Reliability

While validity is primarily associated with quantitative research (Bryman, 2016), it is also applicable to qualitative research when considering the credibility and truthfulness of the findings (Maxwell, 2013). Validity is commonly associated with quantitative research, but it also holds relevance in qualitative research, particularly concerning the credibility and truthfulness of the findings (Maxwell, 2013). In qualitative research, validity is established by the depth and quality of the collected data, prioritizing the significance of respondents as critical variables that shape the depiction of the phenomena being examined. However, in this phenomenological study, the researcher's involvement during the interviews, including probing questions for clarification, introduces a potential threat to the data's reliability. To address this concern, multiple viewers can help mitigate any subjectivity the interviewer introduces during the analysis process (Babbie, 2016). By incorporating diverse perspectives, the study can enhance the reliability of the findings and ensure a more comprehensive and

accurate portrayal of the phenomenon under study. To enhance the validity of the research data, triangulation is employed, which entails analyzing and comparing the perspectives expressed by the various participants engaged in the study. Each individual brings a relevant and distinct interpretation of the topic, which can reveal patterns or contradictions. Moreover, theory triangulation is utilized to compare the collected data with theoretical frameworks proposed by reputable scholars, aiding in the interpretation of the subject matter.

5.5.5 Ethics

The key fundamental of ethical process in research is seeking informed consent (Bryman, 2016). The researcher seeks the consent of all participants after reading and signing both the participant and consent forms. The forms explained to participant the purpose and aim for the research and their participation was entirely voluntary and had the power to withdraw anytime they feel uncomfortable or do not want to participate. The participant and consent forms were approved by the UWS ethical committee. Appendix B and C contains both the consent and participant forms respectively. All data collected for this study was deemed anonymous and kept strictly confidential. To adhere to confidentiality, I created pennames for each interview participant, and did not attach their real names or jobs to any quotations that I used.

Chapter 6: Findings

This chapter reports the key findings from the interviews conducted. The study was purely a qualitative study where data was collected from 22 SMEs from Ghana and Kenya. Data were coded and analysed to identify the knowledge, rationale, and motivations of entrepreneurial training on SMEs' intentions that influence their behaviour. The interview data were systematically analysed to identify key themes. This chapter presents results from themes related to the research questions in chapter one. The main research questions that guided the purpose of the interview guide are as follows.

- 1. RQ1: *What impact have entrepreneurship training programmes had on entrepreneurs' capacity and determination in light of efforts by policymakers, educational institutions, global organisations, private entities, and NGOs?***
- 2. RQ2: *How can the persistent rise in business failures among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Africa be interpreted in the context of efforts to enhance entrepreneurial capabilities through educational reforms and training initiatives?***
- 3. RQ3: *'What factors influence SMEs' desire to develop the intentions to undertake entrepreneurial training initiatives?'***

6.1 Startup Motivation

This chapter aims to analyse and appreciate various trigger events or situations influencing entrepreneurs' intentions to start a business. The reflection of participants in Ghana and Kenya SMEs was categorised into three major vital elements: cognitive factors, self-efficacy and entrepreneurial capacity. Three key categories of startup motivation emerged during the coding and the thematic categories process. Many individuals decide to set up their businesses for various reasons, with previous research findings indicating that startup rationale affects the motives for starting a business (Kolvereid & Isaksen, 2006; Kassouf et al., 2015). Other researchers have argued that the motives for starting a business are vital to understanding and predicting the business's entrepreneurial performance (Naicker &

Nsengimana, 2022). The motivation to start a business may also influence the entrepreneurs' behaviour, precisely how they identify and spot opportunities and intend to grow and manage their business in the post-launch phase.

Entrepreneurs' self-efficacy is a vital motivational construct influencing choices, ambition, psychological reactions, action, coping and endurance (Edi et al., 2019; Al-Swidi et al., 2014). As evident in the literature review in chapter 5.3.3, self-efficacy defines an individual's core capabilities to persevere towards success. This is because the findings of Kassouf et al. (2015) revealed that entrepreneurs with significant self-efficacy have the potential to achieve great success than those without. In other to address the answer to the research question '*What factors influence SMEs' desire to develop the intentions to undertake entrepreneurial training initiatives*', it is vital to understand that self-efficacy defines the intrinsic belief of an individual's core competence to complete a task or to achieve a goal and adopt a particular intention as stated in chapter 5.3.3 and 5.6. A relevant and insightful example from the data collected revealed that

"My business started six years ago. The motivation was solely based on passion. I started dealing in leather products, from wallets, belts, footwear, and leather bags. I found it a way to make extra income. That was how I started my own business. A little bit of remodelling and customisation came into play. That is how my business has been evolved over the years. The business is growing, and the production aspect is meeting demand."
(Respondent, GH1002).

This response from GH-1002 is an intriguing example in so many ways. The business was started based on "**passion**" and "**opportunities**". This is because his motivation was "passion", as he dealt with the leather product as an "opportunity" to make extra cash. First and foremost, the business was started about six (6) years ago. The business has been thriving

through an intrinsic desire from the owner called passion. As stated in (chapter 1.1.6), Most businesses in Africa fail between three to 5 years of operation (Jones et al., 2018). Passion makes individuals believe in themselves, which triggers them to identify opportunities. Respondent GH1002's ability to spot opportunities to make extra income was massively influenced by the creative remodelling and customisation.

Another participant response from KY-1009 and GH-1001,

"My skills and passion are the core that really pushed towards my business. I was able to, manage to the business without the training, but of course, with time, I used to read books I used to talk to my other entrepreneurs and also attend seminars and training that other organisations organised, and it really helped." (Respondent KY-1009)

"The rate of unemployed graduates triggered me to start my own business. I decided to create something for myself in order not to depend on or join many unemployed graduates already in the system" (Respondent, GH-1001).

Response from GH001 established that his motivation was triggered by **fear of being unemployed**. GH001 response, "I decided to create something for myself", indicates that after graduating from school, GH001 wanted to use **skills** acquired to create a job rather than join the pool of unemployed graduates.

Furthermore, response from GH1004,

"When I finished university, I worked really hard for a highly reputable company; I felt I was not appreciated and was not getting what I wanted. I picked up shifts and covered for other colleagues because we needed more staff. When it got to the time I was to be promoted, it was given to someone else. The person was employed two weeks before the promotion, but he was given the promotion. This really motivated me to start my own business." (Respondent, GH-1004).

Reflections on response from GH1004 took a different twist, *"I felt I was not appreciated and was not getting what I wanted..."* lack of recognition was the main motivation for GH1004 to start his own business. Reflection from GH-1004 can be seen as a negative trigger to start a business. This source of motivation to start a business was similar to that of Respondent KY-1002.... *"I work and was not getting recognition for the innovative idea was giving to the company and not also being acknowledged."* (Respondent, KY-1002)

Finally, Reflection on

"Personal skills have had a huge impact on my business. I have encountered several challenges that demotivated me as an entrepreneur. Sometimes dealing with angry customers or clients and want to get rid of them, but you cannot get rid of them because you need money for your business." (Respondent KY1003).

Participant response indicates that personal skills, zeal, desire, passion, fear, ambition and motivation. Some entrepreneurs consider startup motivations subjective, with much emphasis on personal truth intrinsic values and beliefs of the individual.

6.2 Entrepreneurial Education and training

Souitaris et al. (2007) established that entrepreneurial training and education have the most substantial impact on entrepreneurial intention. The literature review (see Chapter 5.5) indicates a conceptual framework establishing the linkage between factors influencing entrepreneurs' intentions that may lead to a specific action. These thematic influences include *Personal experience, Social influencer, self-Efficacy and entrepreneurial capacity* (see figure 5.5). From the literature, an argument from Edi et al. (2019) indicated that persistent changes in business operations affect the entrepreneurial strength of existing entrepreneurs' intentions toward business.

However, data collected from respondents have diverse opinions on what may trigger them to take or undertake entrepreneurial training while operating their businesses. An interesting example is that of Respondent GH-1001.

"Most of my failures and early mistake as an entrepreneur were as a result of no entrepreneurial training. Because there were a lot of errors I made in my business at the beginning. It really impacted my business heavily." (Respondent GH-1001).

This respondent suggested that because he/she had no background of entrepreneurial training, there were so many errors made at the early stages of their business. In view of this, Truman (2021) also suggested that entrepreneurial training is the pivot for SMEs to overcome the challenges at the early stages of their business. This implies that an entrepreneur will be triggered to have some training to **"prevent mistakes and errors."**

Similarly, Respondent KY-1008 supported the subject of how important entrepreneurial training can be; ... *"I feel entrepreneurial training is important or justifiable guarantee or success in a business typically in the traditional way to combat business failures. Especially in the early stages of a business". Respondent KY-1008*

This shows the importance of entrepreneurial training. Both Respondent GH-1001 and KY-1008 believes entrepreneurial training is a vital way to **"acquire skills"** to **"mitigate the risk"** of challenges or failure at the early stage of every business. This indicates the vital role entrepreneurial training possesses at the early stage of every business to prevent **"failure"** or **"collapse of the business"**.

However, KY-1009 was of the view that.... *"I manage my business without the training, but of course, with time, I used to read books I, used to talk to my other entrepreneurs and also attend seminars and trainings that other organisations organised, and it really helped."* Respondent KY-1009. KY-1009 has a different dimension of entrepreneurial training. Even

though KY-1009 did not start the business with any form of entrepreneurial training they learnt on the process. They spoke to other entrepreneurs in the form of " **networking**" and went for training seminars and reading to "**acquire knowledge**". And also, KY-1001 "*Yes because with entrepreneurial training, you get to understand the latest trends and issues related to your business and how to deal with them*". (Respondent KY-1001). This means entrepreneurial training is a vital means for an individual to "**understand the latest trend**" and how to approach and deal with them. This can also imply that entrepreneurs are willing to be "**dynamic**" and "**adapt to change**" and address the demands of people/customers/consumers.

In other to understand the desire for an individual to undertake entrepreneurial training, Respondent GH-1002 was of the view that "*Even though after school, I enrolled into some design thinking modules with CEBS.*" (Respondent GH-1002). This indicates how individuals undertake entrepreneurial training for different reasons. GH-1002 was of the view that after school, He/she went further to enrol on design thinking modules to acquire more "**ideas**" and become "**creative**".

These respondents view entrepreneurial education and training as providing the necessary skills and also serving as a source of understanding the latest trends and news. Furthermore, feedback from respondents also suggested that training helps prevent mistakes and errors in their business, especially during the early stages of the business.

6.3 Entrepreneurial Education and Training (University)

As stated earlier in the literature review section 2.1, entrepreneurial education triggers individuals' behaviours, skills, and attributes to help the creation, sustain, and enhance creativity and innovation (Mangundjaya, 2015). Matlay (2018) argued differently that a variety of entrepreneurship education taught in classrooms contributes to developing both

generic and specific decision-making skills of promising and future entrepreneurs. Timmons (1987) suggested that entrepreneurial activities could be learned from one's personal experience. Putta (2014) also suggested that entrepreneurship can be nurtured and fostered, which is to transcend from parent to children without formal education or training.

However, a perfect example is that of GH-1001... *"Most universities do train people to become entrepreneurs. But the issue has got to do with a student graduating and not using their skills"*- (Respondent GH-1001). The participant believed that entrepreneurial education from the university is important and trains individuals to become entrepreneurs. But the respondent argued that the major issue is graduating and not using the skills acquired.

However, KY-1001 also had a different opinion *"....the universities have got the requisite skills to equip individuals with the required training. Yes because you get to understand the latest trends and issues related to your business and how to deal with them"*. Similarly, Murray et al. (2018), believed that entrepreneurship education has the capacity to provide support for students and staff by bridging the gap between the external environment and academia KY -1001's view indicated that entrepreneurial education and training in the university are important in providing and individual with the necessary skills and also serve as source of understanding latest trends and news.

KY-1009 believed that university entrepreneurial training helped sharpen their skills... *"through the academia of journey in the university, such business programmes I studied study add and sharpen my skills"* Respondent (KY-1009)

"I feel universities should put up modules that adapt to current circumstances. I feel they have the capacity, they have the resources, but it is a matter of changing the scope to adapt to current approach existing in our daily lives" (Participant GH-1005)

"The educational system only encourages people to employment rather than entrepreneurship. People are scared of going out there to try and do businesses" (Participant KY-1008).

Most participants admitted that university entrepreneurial training is essential to developing individual skills in establishing and running a business because such training tends to offer crucial support and skill to promote growth, as described by (Murray et al., 2018).

6.4 Apprenticeship Training

Over the years, several inefficiencies have often stimulated the argument for apprenticeship training on African soil (Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013). In most African countries, as evident in the literature review in chapter (4.4), it is familiar for young entrepreneurs to acquire a new job skill through an informal apprenticeship. Most of these young people engage in apprentices training with little or unpaid assistants working under masters to acquire skills (Adenle, 2017; Nkirina, 2010; Nafukho & Helen, 2010). In most cases, this Apprenticeship takes a span of about five years. The motive of this training is to acquire the basic skills. Respondent KY-1008 mentioned that;

"...Apprenticeship is important. Most of my employees who had apprenticeship training always produced fantastic results and outcomes. They are already knowledgeable and have energy to produce the needed task or job when given. They have the skills and the exposure already" (Respondent KY-1008).

"...When individuals engage in apprenticeship it gives them the real exposure to the business of interest" (Respondent GH-1004).

Both feedback (Respondent KY-1008) and (Respondent GH-1004) suggested that apprenticeship training exposure individuals to their business. It is also an avenue for

individuals to acquire the necessary skills. From Baloch et al. (2017) research findings, apprenticeship training is a vital measure to gain fantastic for potential entrepreneurs to gain a background understanding of chosen business or trade line. Another Respondent suggested that

"I have also train a lot of people in the form of Apprenticeship. Most of them have graduate from the training and have also started their business. In a way, I feel I am contributing to national development by training people to create job for themselves..." (Respondent GH-1005). GH-1005 believes that apprenticeship training is very important because it provide avenue for individuals to create jobs for themselves. This are measure of contributing to national development through job creation. Bjursell and Rebecka, (2018) argued that apprentices acquire the necessary skills and learn a business related activities in order to create business for themselves.

"That's the best. Most of my employees are from vocational schools and apprenticeship training programmes. They are specialist in local craftsmanship"...(Respondent GH-1002). Respondent GH-1002 emphasised on the vital role of both vocational and Apprenticeship. GH-1002 established that such individuals are skilled and specialist in craftsmanship because of their previous early knowledge.

"I firmly believe that it gives them the required individuals the skills and confidence". KY-1001. KY-1001 also suggested that even though Apprenticeship provide the skills for individuals, it also boost their confidence level.

Similarly KY-1009 was of the same opinion as GH-1005;

"...apprenticeship is a good approach for every individual before embarking on self-employment because that the way you get to learn so many other things in the business management, which includes financials, the marketing strategies and customer service, how

to deal with customer are very important..." (Respondent KY-1009). KY-1009 also argues that apprenticeship training is important because, its a way an individual learns about the basic skills before starting their own business. In view of this, KY-1003 a was of the view that

"Apprenticeship, from my experience I will recommend to anybody to have some sort of apprentices training before they start their business" (Respondent KY-1003). KY-1003 was of the view that it will be vital for every individual to have some level of entrepreneurial training before commencement of business

Response from (GH-1004, GH-1005, KY-1003, KY-1008 and KY-1009) from Ghana and Kenya respectively imply that apprenticeship experience for early entrepreneurs is a fantastic opportunity to empower entrepreneurs at the initial stage of their career path. In support of this argument, Nkirina (2010) indicated that Apprenticeship is a vital stage of an individual evolving to establish their business progressively.

6.5 Family and Friends support

Most of the individuals who participated indicated that support from family is an important element of an individual's intentions in operating and starting a business.

"Financial support for my family has been the best. My wife has been the backbone of emotional support. Without them, I won't have the zeal to continue what I do... The financial support we can survive as a business but emotional support we need it in our everyday activities as a business. An institution is, and emotional support are the most vital one" (Respondent GH-1001). Comments from GH-1001 indicate that family support is vital, and GH-1001 also established that families provide financial and emotional support. Even though the business gained ground along the lines and was able to support its support financially, the

entrepreneur still needed emotional support from families during the business's day-to-day activities.

Furthermore, participant KY-1001 also suggested that;

"Some friends and family patronise my services, which services as revenue. Some friends and family refer clients to my business... The first contact of motivation for establishing a business is mostly friends and family... The support from them are sometimes not necessarily financial but can be in the form of advice..." (Respondent KY-1001). KY-1001 was of the opinion that family and friends do not only provide emotional and financial support, but also serve as a customer base and also refer client to their business.

Similar to KY-1001, GH-1005 was of the opinion that;

"My wife has been the main source of support... My family also supported me... They invested into the business... My friends were my customers... They motivated me and encouraged me" (Respondent GH-1005). Respondent GH-1005 also suggested that family and friends provide support and encouragement to serve as a customer base for the business while investing in the business.

Family plans a key role, most of the respondents ascertain that family provide both financial and emotional support. Family and friends are also the first point of customer base for most entrepreneurs.

6.6 Government Policies

An interview guide was used to acquire information that addressed the awareness of government policies and their effects on SMEs.

According to the respondent GH-1001;

"They are policies. Theoretically, they exist. The point is you go to some of these government department and they have nothing to offer you." Respondent GH-1001. The respondent believed that there are policies which exists but the respondent felt the policies are not effective.

Similar to GH-1001, GH-1005 also was of the view that;

"There are so many government policies available to support small businesses, but the communication of such policies to SMEs are not effective. Most of us don't know whether these policies exist. The mode of communication is poor. These policies are sometimes not well defined. There are no clarities in these policies. Most people do not know much about these policies even if they exist. And such policies are not well defined. The process to even to go through to get grant is not even" (Respondent GH-1005). GH-1005 acknowledged the availability of policies but argued that those policies are not effective and are poorly communicated. The respondent further suggested that the policies are not well defined, which makes it difficult in terms of access to grants.

Furthermore, KY-1001 also acknowledged that there are several policies which are implemented by the Kenya government in other to address and mitigate risk

"There have been several trainings initiated by the government for businesses to understand the impact of the various on business and how to mitigate risk. However, the government should make some sort of funding available for businesses to flourish. The government should provide the necessary support to promising entrepreneurs right from training until the beginning and during their business operation". (Respondent KY-1001)

Table 6.1 Key Findings

<p>Startup Motivation</p>	<p>Cognitive factors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Some entrepreneurs consider startup motivations subjective, with much emphasis on personal truth, intrinsic values and beliefs of the individual -Individuals with previous experience in the business and trade areas are most likely intended to start a business -Negative experiences (lack of recognition, promotion, acknowledgement, recognition and benefit) trigger startup motivation -Constant exposure to entrepreneurial training influence trigger the awareness of starting a business -Practical experience create exposure for business <p>Self-Efficacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Self-efficacy of entrepreneurs can be define as the intrinsic belief of an individual's core competence which include skills, zeal, desire, passion, fear, ambition and motivation to start a business. -Graduate students with the fear of being unemployed after graduating to have the motive of starting their business. -Passion and skills are a key trigger to start a business <p>Entrepreneurial capacities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Individuals are likely to start a business if they able to spot opportunities, identify and spot opportunities and intend to grow and manage their business.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The persistent increase of unemployment rate encourages to individuals start a business -Individuals intend to seek better welfare by starting their own business -Uncertainty about the future motivates individuals to start their business.
<p>Entrepreneurial Education and Training</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entrepreneurial education from the university is important and trains individuals to become entrepreneurs - Provide necessary skills and also serve as source of understanding latest trends and news. - Entrepreneurs will be triggered to have some training to prevent mistakes and errors in their business. - Vital way to acquire skills to mitigate the risk of challenges at the early stage of every business - Early stage of every business to prevent "failure" or "collapse of the business." - Universities help understand basic parameters surrounding everyday business endeavours theoretically. - Periodic and constant entrepreneurial training create awareness which triggers the intentions of entrepreneurs - Entrepreneurial training/Education in schools does not promote practical experience. - Promote dynamism and encourage entrepreneurs to adapt to change

Apprenticeship training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote skilled and specialists in craftsmanship - Apprenticeship training is very important because it provides an avenue for individuals to create jobs for themselves - Provide basic skills for entrepreneurs before they start their own business - Apprenticeship training exposure individuals to their business
Family and Friends	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Financial support -provide emotional support -networking and customer base through referral -Investors
Government Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Policies exists but they are ineffective -Poor communication of policies -Government policies are not well-defined -Lack of funding to support SMEs -Government grant can be supportive when process of acquiring are flexible

Chapter 7: Discussion and Contribution

The development of SMEs is the centre for every sub-Saharan African country but particularly for Ghana and Kenya, where business failure rates range between three (3) to five (5) years of operation. The SMEs considered were centred on the number of workers or employees still in business operation and successfully established enterprises. The findings of this thesis will address the impact of entrepreneurial training in Sub-Saharan Africa.

7.1 Conceptual: Startup Motivation

Five critical cohesive themes of cognitive factors measured the analysis of startup intentions and motivation after analysing the primary data in table 8.1. The most common findings to understand startup motivation is proxy to either an individual who was employed prior to starting a business or experiences and information which triggered them to leave a job either voluntarily or involuntarily. From the primary data collected, both countries Kenya and Ghana possesses similar trait.

Figure 6: Startup Motivation Framework *inspired by the author*

From the findings in both respective countries, most of the entrepreneurs who participated in the interview consider startup motivations subjective, with much emphasis on personal truth, intrinsic values and beliefs of the individual.

Table 7.1 Motivation

Self-Efficacy	Entrepreneurial capacities	Family and Friends	Economic status	Government policies
Skills	Spot opportunities,	Emotional support,	Opportunities	Grant
Zeal	Unemployment rate	Networking and	Finance	Taxes
Desire	welfare	resourcing,	Risk Tolerance	Advisory service
Motivation	uncertainty	Knowledge Transfer,	Networking	
Passion		Financial support		
Ambition				
Fear				

Source: Data analysis

In support of these findings, Millman et al. (2010) an individual's motivation to exhibit conscious effort to execute a plan or take a bold decision; therefore, It is crucial to understand the various motivation factors that trigger their intent. To establish the connection, scholars have examined these factors that influence the motive of entrepreneurs towards entrepreneurship (Akanni et al, 2021; Adegbite et al., 2021). These personal biological traits include age, level of education, gender, and culture (Lorz, 2011; Hui-Chen, Kuen-hung and Chen-yi, 2014; Estay et al., 2013; Davis, 2015; Chikandiwa et al 2020). From findings, it was revealed that apart from personal biological traits such as age, level of education, gender and culture, personal experience in business areas are essential motivators to trigger an individual intending to start a business. KY-1003, KY-1006, KY-1009, GH-1002, and GH-1008 argued that Personal skills had had a massive impact on my business. KY-1009 also suggested.. skills and passion are the core that pushed my business. Most of the participants from Kenya argued that personal Skills is the major contributor to starting their business. Meek (2012)

argued that this approach deals with entrepreneurs' motivations and expectancy factors to develop a particular intention is important. Furthermore, in the literature review (chapter 5.3.3), Edi et al. (2019) suggested that self-efficacy defines the intrinsic belief of an individual's core competence to complete a task. Self-efficacy becomes a key asset when individuals are challenged with a difficult situation and can mitigate it when they want to establish a business (Udayanan, 2019). Other key elements such as desire, passion for a particular venture or business also emerge.

Furthermore, the findings also revealed that constant exposure to entrepreneurial training influence triggers the awareness of starting a business. This implies that entrepreneurs' exposure to the practical world to understand their business or trade area at their early stages influences their intention. This type of training can be in the form of apprenticeship training or coaching, which sets techniques adopted to casually transmit learning skills, support, and other beneficial endeavours relating to a vocation or work from an expert or tutor. Informal Apprenticeship is more unrestricted than traditional Apprenticeship, where apprentices sometimes come from external sources rather than family (Baloch, Rahim and Manzoor, 2017 Akanni et al, 2021; Adegbite et al., 2021), as stated clearly in chapter 3.1. Notwithstanding, a master artisan training informal apprentices might also train their child as a traditional apprentice. This implies that practical experience creates exposure for business across most Sub-African countries. From the data, GH-1004 suggested that individuals with practical experience and engagement in Apprenticeship are vital because they are exposed to the business of interest. However, Timmons (1987) believed entrepreneurship could not be ascertained through formal education to some extent. He further argued that entrepreneurial activities could be learned from personal experience, which best explains the importance of practical training for SMEs. Puta (2014) also believed that entrepreneurship training could transcend from parent to children without formal

education or training. In recent global crises, it is vital to know the entrepreneurial strength of existing entrepreneurs' attitudes regarding whether they can be sustainable considering these persistent changes affecting business activities, especially among small and medium enterprises.

Despite positive experiences influencing individuals' motivation to start a business, negative experiences (lack of recognition, promotion, acknowledgement, recognition and benefit) trigger startup motivation. From the findings, several negative experiences influence individuals to start their businesses. Most individuals at various workplaces in African countries are challenged while working for others. However, there are massive opportunities for growth and success for those willing to learn and understand most SMEs' intricacies. Given this, Vaillant and Lafuente (2019) suggest that their motive behind startup varies from person to person, which explains why entrepreneurs differ from one another. This explains why the justification for applying entrepreneurs' cognitive decisions varies from those without personal experience. This further highlight and presents the findings from the primary data obtained from (GH-1001, GH-1007, KY-1004, and KY-1009) who attributed the motive of starting their business to a negative or destructive experience from their previous jobs. Each participant had a different experience before starting their business, and these were primarily negative parameters. These negative parameters relate to a lack of benefit, promotion, recognition, and acknowledgement, as indicated in table 7.1.

The start-up motivation framework is a conceptual model. It provides a theoretical framework for understanding the various factors that influence individuals' motivation to start their own businesses. The list of triggers in Table 7.1 includes both push and pull factors that can influence entrepreneurship. Push factors are those that motivate individuals to start their own businesses in order to escape their current situation, while pull factors are those that attract individuals to start their own businesses in a new environment. Examples of push

factors include high unemployment rates, fear of failure, negative experiences in one's job, and practical training programs, while examples of pull factors include the ability to spot business opportunities, positive experiences in one's job, and entrepreneurial education and training. This model is based on various studies (Anderson et al. 2018; Mai and Gan 2007; Shapero 1982) on entrepreneurship and provides a comprehensive approach to understanding the motivations driving entrepreneurship, making it useful for policymakers, educators, and business leaders.

Self-Efficacy:

The findings revealed that personal belief in one's abilities and competence to start and succeed in a business could trigger entrepreneurial intentions. This also aligns with chapter 5.3.3, which explains that building self-efficacy through acquiring relevant skills, knowledge, and experience can enhance the motivation to pursue entrepreneurial endeavours. Developing self-efficacy through acquiring skills and knowledge enhances motivation and fosters entrepreneurial intentions.

The findings also support the argument of Caldwell and Hayes (2016) and Kasouf et al 2015 who described building self-efficacy as an individual's core capabilities to strive towards success. A belief in one's abilities and competence drives individuals to exhibit conscious effort, execute plans, and make bold decisions to pursue entrepreneurship. These personal traits, including skills, passion, ambition, and motivation, can drive individuals to recognize entrepreneurial opportunities, overcome fear and uncertainty, and pursue their intentions.

Entrepreneurial Capacity:

Furthermore, the finding also revealed that identifying entrepreneurial opportunities and having the necessary skills and resources to capitalise on them can trigger entrepreneurial intentions. This makes entrepreneurial capacity a vital element of the cognitive which triggers

the intentions of SMEs. This is because of the literature review in Chapter 5. Chinomona et al. (2020) argued that developing an entrepreneurial mindset and acquiring the capacity to navigate challenges and uncertainty can motivate individuals to pursue their entrepreneurial aspirations. The findings support their argument that to acquire the capacity, identifying opportunities to capitalise is vital in modelling and shaping an entrepreneur's intention towards business ventures. Personal experience in business areas motivates individuals intending to start their own ventures. Building personal skills and passion becomes the core driving force behind entrepreneurial intention

The findings of both countries revealed that entrepreneurs must incorporate the necessary skills and core competencies to strive for success and remain competitive in the business environment.

Family and Friends:

From the findings, both entrepreneurs in both respective countries suggest that emotional support and encouragement from family and friends can trigger entrepreneurial intentions. Their ideas also support the remarks made by Shonubi and Taiwo (2013) and Chikandiwa et al., (2020) suggested that family and friends have a direct observable concept to ensure that individual personal characteristics behave in a particular way through motivation. Encouragement of risk-taking attitudes from friends and family can influence individuals to pursue entrepreneurial opportunities. Emotional support and encouragement from friends and family motivate individuals pursuing entrepreneurship. Successful role models among friends and family inspire individuals, influencing their consideration of entrepreneurship as a viable career path.

Family and friends also serve as role models within one's social network, who have successfully established their businesses and can inspire and influence individuals to consider

entrepreneurship a viable path (Akanni et al, 2021). Emotional support from friends and family offers encouragement, while networking and resourcing provide access to valuable connections, mentors, and potential investors. Knowledge transfer from experienced individuals and family members helps to aspire and existing entrepreneurs understand business challenges, and financial support in the form of loans or investments alleviates initial capital constraints.

Economic Status:

In addition, Economic constraints and limited job opportunities can trigger entrepreneurial intentions among individuals from lower economic statuses. Economic constraints and limited job opportunities push individuals from lower economic statuses towards entrepreneurial intentions. The prospect of upward mobility, financial independence, and addressing market gaps can motivate individuals to start their own businesses. Addressing market gaps, achieving financial independence, and upward mobility motivate individuals to own businesses. Economic factors, such as high unemployment rates and limited welfare support, can push individuals towards entrepreneurship as a means of financial stability and independence.

Government Policies:

Supportive government policies and initiatives, such as access to funding, business development programs, and regulatory ease, can trigger entrepreneurial intentions. Supportive government policies, such as access to funding, business development programs, and regulatory ease, encourage entrepreneurial intentions.

Entrepreneurship-friendly policies that promote innovation, create a favourable business environment, and offer incentives can motivate individuals to venture into entrepreneurship.

During the thematic analysis of the data collected (appendix see F), it emerged that Startup motivation encompasses a mental state that varies from individual to individual. Some entrepreneurs consider startup motivations subjective, with much emphasis on personal truth, and the way they think is mainly subjected to the intrinsic values and beliefs of the individual. This is because Startup motivation is triggered mainly by several factors that change an entrepreneur's thinking. Building networks, accessing grants, favourable tax policies, and advisory services provided by the government or other entities attract individuals towards entrepreneurship.

7.2 Contextual: Instigators of Entrepreneurial Intention

The findings also introduce a novel model that contextualises the understanding of the instigators of entrepreneurial intention, which is deemed crucial for facilitating a conducive environment for entrepreneurial activities. SMEs, environmental capital resources, personal experience, entrepreneurial education, and government policies influence individuals' motivation and intention to engage in entrepreneurship (Ojeifo et al., 2021). By recognising, understanding and leveraging these instigators, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can cultivate an ecosystem that nurtures entrepreneurial aspirations, fosters innovation, and drives economic growth. This instigator model in 8.2 emanated from the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Ajzen (1991) and the Entrepreneurial Event Model (EME) by Shapero and Sokol (1982). Ajzen (1991) suggest that personal experience and entrepreneurial education can influence entrepreneurial intention through an individual's attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, whiles Shapero and Sokol (1982) suggest that various triggers, including personal experiences, environmental factors, and education, contribute to the occurrence of an "entrepreneurial event" or the decision to start a business. Both models underpin personal experience, and educational background can shape an individual's beliefs and perceptions, affecting their intention to engage in entrepreneurship.

The Instigator Model, as presented in the study, examines the various factors contributing to developing entrepreneurial intentions as indicated in figure 7 below. These findings align with the core view of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TBP); these findings substantially augment our understanding of the driving factors behind entrepreneurial actions. The study's outcomes provide a valuable extension to the TBP framework and shed light on the complex interplay of social support, educational gaps, and policy influences. The instigator model provides a detailed understanding of the complex instigators and their interactions, highlighting how motivation and decision-making processes in entrepreneurship are influenced, similar to the TBP. A significant finding from the research is that the instigator model also plays a vital role in understanding the rationale of family and friends in providing emotional and financial support to entrepreneurs despite their limited comprehension of the business intricacies. The study also highlights a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application in the real world, indicating that school entrepreneurial education needs improvement. Additionally, government policies were found to have positive and negative impacts on businesses, with concerns primarily revolving around their effects on existing ventures rather than entrepreneurial intentions.

This research deepens our understanding of TBP and provides a foundation for more targeted policy interventions and educational programs. By connecting these findings to the broader literature, this study enhances the existing body of knowledge, offering practical insights for policymakers, educators, and entrepreneurs, thereby advancing the field of entrepreneurship studies. These highlights the dynamic nature of instigators and their cumulative effect on entrepreneurial intention of SMEs.

Figure 7: SMEs instigators for entrepreneurial training and education. *Inspired by author*

The instigator model provides frameworks for understanding how diverse instigators of entrepreneurial intention derive from different factors and interact with each other to influence individuals' motivation and decision-making processes in entrepreneurship. The model offers a unique insight into the complex dynamics that shape entrepreneurial intention and can inform policy interventions and educational programs to foster entrepreneurship.

Instigators

Personal Experience

The findings also suggested that family and friends play a crucial role in providing emotional and financial support for entrepreneurs, even if they may not fully understand the nature of the business. This finding highlights the significance of their support in fostering positive entrepreneurial intentions. Some participants acknowledged that their family and friends do

not understand their business's nature yet still provided the necessary support when needed. More so, family and friends' support significantly influences SMEs' intentions, and they form the primary source of motivation and financial and emotional support for most entrepreneurs (Rachmawan et al., 2015). On the other hand, family and friends' support significantly influences SMEs' intentions, acting as a primary source of motivation, financial assistance, and emotional support for entrepreneurs. Additionally, unfavourable government policies like high taxes can discourage entrepreneurial intentions.

Entrepreneurial Education and Training

The study's findings also suggested that entrepreneurial training/education in schools does not promote practical experience in the real world. The research also indicated that entrepreneurial training in academic institutions often needs more practical experience, emphasizing the need for universities to incorporate hands-on approaches in entrepreneurial education. This can be achieved by establishing partnerships with actual small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and implementing mandatory internships where students can apply theoretical knowledge in real-world settings. Additionally, promoting apprenticeship training through higher education can enhance practical learning opportunities (Herrington & Coduras, 2019; (Nkirina, 2010; Anderson et al., 2018). The results revealed that entrepreneurial education and training are not the primary triggers for entrepreneurial intentions but provide the essential business acumen and concepts needed for everyday business. Apprenticeship training exposes entrepreneurs to learning practically and gaining insight into their trade area. Furthermore, the study revealed that while entrepreneurial education and training are not the primary triggers for entrepreneurial intentions, they provide essential business knowledge and concepts for daily business operations.

This has to serve as a wake-up call for most higher institutions to incorporate a practical approach to learning entrepreneurial education in business. To achieve this, universities should align with actual SMEs with compulsory modules to assign each student to a particular trade area as an internship. This will enable a student to apply the theoretical aspect taught in class. Furthermore, apprenticeship training should also be encouraged through higher education.

Government Interventions and Initiatives

Government policies were found to have positive and negative impacts on businesses, with participants expressing more concern about their effects on their businesses rather than their entrepreneurial intentions. This suggests that government policies influence entrepreneurs' decision-making and the overall business environment; Ndofirepi and Rambe, 2017; Alakaleek, 2019.

Family and Friends

The findings also revealed the critical role families play in the progress of SMEs. Friends and family in both respective countries have been seen as a support system to help many business owners manage stress, maintain perspective and improve the balanced working environment, even amid the confusion and crushing responsibility deterring the primary purpose of managing the business. This thesis findings highlighted the vital role played by families in the survival and existence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). In both respective countries (Ghana and Kenya) used as area of case study, friends and family members have emerged as a backbone support for several businesses, offering much-needed assistance in managing stress, maintaining perspective, and fostering a balanced working environment (Agyemang, & Ankomah-Asare 2020). This support becomes particularly crucial in

understanding the challenges, confusion, and overwhelming responsibilities that often deter entrepreneurs from focusing on their primary business objectives.

Moreover, the findings highlight that beyond the emotional and moral support provided, entrepreneurs primarily benefit from the monetary assistance and investments extended by their family and friends. This financial support serves as a fundamental pillar for African entrepreneurs, enabling them to establish a solid business foundation or serve as a safety during times of economic hardship and uncertainty especially during the covid-19 period. This makes financial support the core aim of African entrepreneurs to establish a business foundation or provide a backbone in times of economic hardship. Furthermore, the financial contributions from family and friends address one of the most critical concerns for entrepreneurs' access to capital. Due to stringent requirements or a lack of collateral, African entrepreneurs often need help securing traditional financing options, such as bank loans. In such instances, the support received from loved ones becomes a lifeline, enabling entrepreneurs to launch their ventures or sustain their businesses during trying economic times rather than relying on expensive interest rate from banks (Amoako & Agyapong, 2020).

The importance of family and friend support in SMEs cannot be overstated. The findings revealed that it is a reliable source of encouragement and motivation, propelling entrepreneurs forward despite daunting challenges. The understanding and assistance of loved ones create a conducive environment for business owners to thrive, fostering a sense of resilience and determination. This statement is also supported by (Bastian, 2017).

In conclusion, the findings of this thesis point out the curial role played by family and friend support in the growth and sustainability of SMEs. Entrepreneurs in both countries have benefited from the moral, emotional, and financial backing provided by their loved ones. This support system not only helps entrepreneurs manage stress and maintain perspective but also

serves as a critical source of capital, especially in African contexts where traditional financing avenues may be limited. Recognising and leveraging the power of family and friend support can be a pivotal factor in the success of SMEs, creating a conducive environment for entrepreneurial endeavours to thrive and flourish.

Apprenticeship Training

The approaches to learning entrepreneurial training have changed the perception of restrictions imposed on traditional classrooms based on the only place to learn and examine are changing. Baloch et al. (2017) research suggested that Apprenticeship at an entry level for entrepreneurs is an essential measure of acquiring the necessary skills, which is fantastic for potential entrepreneurs to gain a background understanding of their chosen business line. The findings revealed that Apprenticeship promotes skilled and specialists in craftsmanship. This dynamism of the Apprenticeship helps promote the necessary skills by providing labour services in exchange for receiving training and skills (Bjursell & Rebecka, 2018). Furthermore, the findings also indicated that apprenticeship training is fundamental because it allows individuals to create jobs for themselves. This support of Watson and McGowan (2019) argued that apprenticeship learners are equipped with the core knowledge needed to create jobs with much primary focus on developing a positive attitude, perception, and behaviours deemed necessary to achieve success. This makes a vital need for government to promote by addressing persistent unemployment issues. Furthermore, the findings in both respective countries, Ghana and Kenya, also show that Apprenticeship provides essential skills for entrepreneurs before starting their businesses and exposes individuals to their businesses. This makes apprenticeships a critical element in incubatory business services; they provide the necessary training, which helps entrepreneurs start, expand, and sustain their businesses.

7.3 Legacy: Entrepreneurial education and Training

Entrepreneurship education and training learned can enhance skills and innovation strategies in various business operations (Nkirina, 2010; Anderson et al., 2018). The principal role of entrepreneurship education and business training must be considered. The thematic analysis revealed that Most of the participants in respective countries (Ghana and Kenya) believed that entrepreneurial education from the university is essential and trains individuals to become entrepreneurs. However, they argue that the significant issue is graduating and not using the skills acquired for either university or training. The concept of entrepreneurial education training was defined across the interview with the participant as some participants were in a dilemma about whether they influence entrepreneurs' intentions. However, most of the participants acknowledged the vital role entrepreneurship role plays. The interview questions were drafted to understand what will transpire for entrepreneurs or owners of the business to undertake entrepreneurial training or education.

The findings revealed that most of the respondents in the respective countries, Ghana and Kenya, are willing to undertake entrepreneurial training if there beneficial for their business or will prevent their business from collapsing. Many scholars have acknowledged the influential role entrepreneurial training plays in transforming entrepreneurs (Watson & McGowan, 2019; Anderson et al., 2018; Akanni et al, 2021; Adegbite et al., 2021). Some participants also indicated that entrepreneurial education and training in the university are essential in providing an individual with the necessary skills and a source of understanding the latest trends. Both respondents from Ghana and Kenya saw entrepreneurial education and training as important ways to acquire skills to mitigate the risk of challenges at the early stage of every business. This argument supports Adegbite et al., (2021), they suggested that emerging startups are thriving to survive; it is essential to foster entrepreneurial training and education early.

Furthermore, most of the participants in both Ghanaian and the Kenyan economies (GH-1002, GH-1005, GH-1007, KY-1004, KY-1009, KY-1002) were of the view that they will undertake entrepreneurial training early stage of every business to prevent "failure" or "collapse of the business". Masadeh (2008) argued that most SMEs often fail because entrepreneurs need more training and skills to promote productivity and ensure sustainability. The findings and view of Masadeh both suggest that it is essential for an individual to undertake entrepreneurial training. In addition, the findings revealed that periodic and constant entrepreneurial training creates awareness that triggers entrepreneurs' intentions. These findings also support the views of Adenle 2017 who believed that even entrepreneurs with technical competencies only sometimes have the necessary training to capitalise on their managerial and administrative capabilities required to reduce operational risk (Adenle, 2017).

The findings also revealed that as much as universities' entrepreneurial education and training help theoretically understand basic parameters surrounding everyday business endeavours, promote dynamism and encourage entrepreneurs to adapt to o change, they only sometimes promote the practical experience. Participants view about the view of entrepreneurial training supports the earlier research findings of (Short et al. 2010; Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013; Ndofirepi and Rambe, 2017; Alakaleek, 2019). Figure 8.1 reveals the various factors that will influence SMEs to undertake entrepreneurial training. These highlights were key factors derived from the thematic analysis.

Key drivers of entrepreneurial training can be summarised as follows:

1. Preventing mistakes and errors through acquiring the necessary skills.
2. Understanding and learning from failure as a means to grow and improve.
3. Mitigating risk by developing strategies and approaches to minimise potential challenges.
4. Embracing a dynamic mindset to adapt to changing circumstances and market trends.

5. Building networking relationships to access resources, opportunities, and support.
6. Staying updated with the latest trends and industry developments.
7. Fostering creativity and idea generation to drive innovation.
8. Being resilient in the face of business collapse and learning from the experience

Entrepreneurial education and training can significantly impact various aspects of entrepreneurship, including preventing mistakes and errors, acquiring skills, mitigating risk, understanding the latest trends, and adapting to change (Lorz and Kohn 2015; Mpogole and Baiyegunhi, 2020). Such education and training can lead to higher entrepreneurial awareness and enable individuals to start businesses more confidently. Entrepreneurial education and training can help prevent mistakes and errors by providing individuals with the knowledge and skills to identify and avoid common pitfalls in starting and running a business (Alakaleek, 2019). It can also help individuals acquire new skills and knowledge, enabling them to manage their businesses more effectively and efficiently.

Furthermore, deduction from various factors that influence SMEs to undertake entrepreneurial education and training are summarised into three main categories: Entrepreneurial Awareness, Entrepreneurship for Startups, and the dynamic nature of Entrepreneurship. From the findings of the analysis of the stages of entrepreneurial education and training, three (3) key levels emanated, as highlighted earlier in this chapter. The influence of awareness, start-up, and dynamic factors reinforces entrepreneurship's iterative and interconnected nature. These factors collectively contribute to the development of well-rounded entrepreneurs who can navigate the complexities of the business ecosystem and drive sustainable growth. The influence and significance of each factor may vary depending on individual circumstances. Concerning findings from these respective countries (Ghana and Kenya), variations exist in intercultural contexts. However, key elements such as creativity, mitigating risk and acquiring skills were pinpointed in all the various elements across the

legacy model in Figure 8.3. Nevertheless, recognising the impact of awareness, start-up, and dynamic factors can inform the design and implementation of effective entrepreneurial education and training programs that nurture and support aspiring entrepreneurs on their journey to success Alakaleek, 2019).

Figure 8: Stages of entrepreneurial training *inspired by the author*

The legacy model of the stages of entrepreneurial training illustrates how various factors related to awareness, start-up, and dynamic influences influence the stages of entrepreneurial education and training. These factors play a crucial role in equipping aspiring entrepreneurs with the knowledge, skills, and mindset necessary to understand the challenges and opportunities of entrepreneurship.

"Entrepreneurship Awareness" in this contest refers to the scope of knowledge surrounding entrepreneurship and individuals adopting a positive attitude to trigger the intent toward self-employment. Entrepreneurial awareness will create the need for individuals to venture into job creation and a business of their own in future. At this stage, individuals develop an understanding of entrepreneurship and its associated concepts. Factors such as

creativity, the collapse of business, preventing mistakes, and acquiring essential skills contribute to raising awareness about the entrepreneurial journey. In addition, it is perceived as an essential strategy to promote entrepreneurial awareness among early entrepreneurs or young and promising entrepreneurs. Therefore, this study's finding revealed that most individuals undertook entrepreneurial education and training programmes to be aware of entrepreneurial opportunities and to capitalise on them. This includes creativity, finding relevant strategies for promoting awareness of entrepreneurial opportunities and preventing the proposed and intended business from collapsing. This stage focuses on cultivating a foundational knowledge base and mindset that fosters entrepreneurial thinking. These findings support early research, as clearly stated in Chapter 2.2 of the literature review (Short et al., 2010; Shonubi & Taiwo, 2013; Koe & Majid, 2014; Ndofirepi & Rambe, 2017; Alakaleek, 2019).

The second stage is entrepreneurship for startups. These categories define entrepreneurial programs that generally enhance or promote individuals who already have an existing idea or need to capitalise on societal problems to become self-employed. Aspiring entrepreneurs actively pursue their business ideas and venture creation in this stage. Networking, mitigating risks, adapting to change, idea generation, creativity, acquiring skills, and understanding the potential challenges, including the collapse of a business, are key factors influencing this stage. The start-up stage emphasizes applying knowledge and skills acquired during entrepreneurial training. From the analysis, Individuals will further undertake entrepreneurial education and training for several reasons. First, they will network with other entrepreneurs and adapt to change to have a fair idea about their business venture. Others also take entrepreneurship to mitigate risk in their business and prevent It from collapsing. This is because most businesses are subjected to failure between three to five years of operation (Jones et al., 2018). This does entrepreneurial training and education pivot to start their

business as some researchers believe it is essential to acquire skills (Estay, Durrieu, and Akhter, 2013; Daisy, Tanusree and Raiswa, 2017).

The third category focus on the 'dynamic nature of the entrepreneurial activity.' The category primarily focuses on individuals who are already existing entrepreneurs and want to incorporate dynamism in their business operations. As entrepreneurs progress, they enter the dynamic stage characterized by ongoing growth, innovation, and adaptation. Networking, dynamism, risk mitigation, understanding the latest trends, adapting to change, creativity, and acquiring advanced skills continue to shape this stage. The dynamic stage emphasizes continuous learning, staying agile, and leveraging emerging opportunities to sustain and expand the entrepreneurial venture. Most SMEs and businesses must know how to react to their customer's needs and want in the business environment. This helps address vital ethical issues affecting how their business operates, including production, packaging and transporting, to ensure the effective use of resources. These dynamisms can be new skills or strategies (Bastian, Yusuf, and Amine, 2018; Alexandria, Brent and Alicia, 2018; Fatoki, 2018). The findings also revealed that individuals' dynamics to undertake entrepreneurial education and training seek to address issues related to networking, mitigate risk, understand the latest trends, adapt to change, be creative, and acquire skills.

In addition, from the analysis it revealed that entrepreneurial education and training can help SMEs better understand the latest industry trends and adapt to market changes. This can be particularly important in a dynamic and ever-changing market environment where businesses must continuously innovate and evolve to remain competitive (Mpogole and Baiyegunhi, 2020). Networking is also an essential aspect of entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurial education and training can provide individuals with the necessary tools to develop and maintain a network of contacts in their industry. Such networks can be valuable sources of support, advice, and new business opportunities. Finally, entrepreneurial education

and training can help individuals develop their creativity and generate new ideas. It can enable individuals to think outside the box and develop innovative solutions to complex business problems.

7.4 Effects of government policies on SME performance in Sub-Saharan Africa (Ghana and Kenya)

The finding revealed that policies exist to support SMEs, but they could be more effective in both countries (Ghana and Kenya). The literature in 4.6.1 indicated that several entrepreneurial training programs had been initiated to promote economic growth (Amoah & Amoah, 2018; Kinya et al., 2018). These training initiatives were fully designed to align the needs of entrepreneurs to trade and consumer requirements (Sheriff & Muffatto, 2015; Agyemang, & Ankomah-Asare 2020) with the hope of promoting an entrepreneurial environment and the private sector in most African Countries.

The reviewed literature in both countries indicated that the governments and other international organisations had prioritised SMEs to ensure high performance through supportive policies that provide a conducive environment for operating in most African countries. Furthermore, the findings also revealed that even though these policies exist, they need to be better communicated to SMEs and be clearly defined. Over the years, the Ghanaian government has demonstrated on fertile grounds its role in supporting and developing SME activities. This is vividly shown in the literature review in chapter four (4), as the role of SMEs in support of the economy is evident in the government's policies to support the behaviour intention of SMEs (Awiagah et al., 2015). According to Abor and Biekpe (2006), the development and nature of SME promotion in Ghana can be traced back to the 1970s. Several government institutions have recently been set up to facilitate, develop and strengthen SMEs. The Ghanaian government has introduced several Economic recovery programmes to support SMEs since 1983 (Peprah et al., 2016; Ssenyonga et al., 2020).

Similarly, in the case of Kenya, SMEs play a vital role in the development of the Kenyan economy. SMEs in Kenya are perceived as the panacea to the country's persistent unemployment rate (Nafukho & Helen, 2010). SMEs play a significant role in all sectors of the economy as an essential source of employment and income in Kenya. Most SMEs in Kenya face financial challenges (Nafukho & Helen, 2010), endangering their survival ability. The statistical record shows that SMEs contribute to job creation by reducing unemployment (Chu et al., 2007; Ssenyonga et al., 2020).

Table 7.2 Summary of contributions

Contributions	Highlights
<p>Theoretical contribution Modification of a theory</p>	<p>Conceptual Model</p> <p><i>1. Startup Motivation Framework:</i> It provides a theoretical framework for understanding individuals' motivation to start their businesses. (see figure 8.1). The most common findings of this thesis to understand startup motivation is proxy to either an individual who was employed prior to starting a business or has experiences in their trade area with vital information which triggered them to leave a job either voluntarily or involuntarily to start their own business.</p> <p>1.1.Five critical cohesive themes of cognitive factors measured the analysis of startup intentions and motivation after analysing the primary data in (see Table 8.1). Participants were allowed to share their feelings, emotions and experience to understand the motivating factors to establish their business. These were categories into 5 cohesive themes; Self-Efficacy, Family and</p>

Friends, Entrepreneurial capacity, Economic status, and Government policies (*see chapter 8.1*).

Contextual model

- 2. *The instigator model*** : provides a framework for understanding how diverse instigators of entrepreneurial intention derive from different factors and interact with each other to influence individuals' motivation and decision-making processes in entrepreneurship (*see figure 8.2*). The model aims to provide a framework for understanding the unique challenges, motivations, and support systems relevant to SMEs. It considers the specific context in which SMEs operate, including factors such as family and friend support, entrepreneurial training, government policies, and environmental capital resources.

Legacy model

- 3. *The legacy model*** of the stages of entrepreneurial training provides a conceptual framework for understanding the progression and critical elements involved in entrepreneurial education and development (*see figure 8.3*). It guides individuals and institutions engaged in promoting entrepreneurship by highlighting the essential stages and aspects that contribute to entrepreneurial success. This will align universities with SMEs' needs, where modules will be developed to address their needs. This will enable a student to apply the theoretical areas to address before venturing into their business operation. Furthermore, apprenticeship training should also be encouraged through higher education. Stages of

	<p>Entrepreneurial Education and Intention. (<i>See factor 8.3</i>). Startup motivation can be categorised into three main: Entrepreneurial Awareness, Entrepreneurship for Startups, and the dynamic nature of Entrepreneurship</p>
<p>Contribution to Practice</p>	<p>Government</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Government policies have very little influence on the performance of SMEs. SME implementers have very little knowledge about the existence of policies in both respective countries (Ghana and Kenya). 2. Poor communication of policies to support SMEs in Ghana and Kenya needs to be addressed and rectified. Governments in both Ghana and Kenya can bridge the gap between SME support policies and their successful implementation by prioritising effective communication and information dissemination. This will primarily contribute to the growth and development of SMEs by promoting a conducive environment for entrepreneurial activities, especially among SMEs. 3. The government must involve local communities to ensure community engagement, the government should undertake a needs assessment by organising meetings in various regions involving SME implementers, employees, community leaders, suppliers, and other stakeholders. The insights gathered from these interactions should be integrated into the development of a revised policy framework.

	<p>University</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Higher institutions to incorporate a practical approach to learning entrepreneurial education. This integration of academia and industry promotes a more practical and experiential approach to entrepreneurial education, equipping students with the necessary competencies to thrive in the business world and fostering stronger ties between universities and the SME sector. 2. Universities should align with actual SMEs with compulsory modules that each student will be assigned to a particular trade area as an internship. universities should consider aligning their educational programs with actual SMEs by incorporating compulsory internships in specific trade areas for students. This approach provides valuable practical experience and exposure to entrepreneurship's real-world challenges and opportunities. By engaging with SMEs during internships, students can apply theoretical knowledge hands-on, develop relevant skills, and gain insights into the specific industry. <p>3. Apprenticeship</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Paid Apprenticeship should be encouraged. This initiative would provide valuable hands-on experience, mentorship, and financial support to individuals interested in starting their businesses. By promoting paid apprenticeships, these countries can enhance entrepreneurs' practical training and skill development, increase job creation, and foster a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation. Addressing financial constraints also ensures that
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	<p>individuals from diverse backgrounds have equal access to entrepreneurial opportunities.</p>
Geographical contribution	<p>1. The study was conducted in both Ghana and Kenya, which brings a unique contribution to the sub-Saharan region to understanding the impact of entrepreneurial training on the intentions of SMEs</p>
Contribution to Research Methods	<p>1. This study took into consideration actual entrepreneurs who are already in business operations. The previous studies only considered students as the primary sample size when issues related to entrepreneurial intentions. Unlike previous studies that primarily focused on students as the sample size for examining entrepreneurial intentions, this study considered actual entrepreneurs already engaged in business operations. The research provides valuable insights into the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions and decision-making in practical settings by including real entrepreneurs. This approach offers a more comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial process and allows for exploring challenges, motivations, and experiences established entrepreneurs face. By broadening the scope of participants to include actual business owners, the study contributes to a more accurate and understanding of the entrepreneurial business environment, enabling policymakers and stakeholders to develop targeted interventions and support mechanisms that cater to entrepreneurs' specific needs and aspirations in the real world.</p>

Chapter 8: Conclusion and Implication

This thesis highlighted and underpinned various gaps in understanding the impact of entrepreneurial training on the intentions of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa. This has pinpointed an influx of support from diverse stakeholders to foster and enhance entrepreneurial activity in Sub-Saharan Africa. The thesis focuses on the critical concept of entrepreneurship education and training to establish prominent traits and understand its impacts on entrepreneurs already in business. This thesis enhanced the understanding of the methodological approach in collecting, analysing, and interpreting the findings. The literature review examined various concepts related to entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial training, and education, identifying several research gaps and methodological deficiencies.

A theoretical model known as Triadic model framework was developed from the literature review gaps which lead to the methodological approach. These gaps were critically examined and addressed by developing an appropriate methodology for the pilot studies. A conceptual, contextual and legacy model framework were developed from the findings of this thesis. The findings of this thesis have highlighted on the role of entrepreneurial education and training in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. While they may not be the primary triggers for entrepreneurial intentions, they provide aspiring entrepreneurs with the necessary business acumen and foundational concepts for everyday business operations. The findings also highlights the importance of integrating practical and theoretical components within entrepreneurship education programs.

This thesis is an integral approach which analyses entrepreneurship training programmes' critical role in today's working environment among SMEs. This thesis's findings explain why entrepreneurial training programmes are increasing among African SMEs. The results from this thesis described the impact of entrepreneurial activity on the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in the selected African countries (Ghana and Kenya).

Furthermore, the geographical contributions of the study are noteworthy. By investigating the experiences and perspectives of entrepreneurs in Ghana and Kenya, the research has provided valuable insights into the specific contextual factors that influence entrepreneurial intentions in these regions. The findings have highlighted the significance of factors such as family and friend support, government policies, and the involvement of local communities in fostering an entrepreneurial ecosystem.

In addition, the study has contributed to developing and refining theoretical models related to entrepreneurial training and education. The research has advanced our understanding of the complexities of fostering entrepreneurial intentions and success by critically evaluating existing models and addressing their limitations. This thesis has deepened our theoretical knowledge and provided practical implications for policymakers, educational institutions, and other stakeholders involved in promoting entrepreneurship. The findings underscore the need for a holistic approach that combines theoretical knowledge, practical training, and tailored support to empower aspiring entrepreneurs and enhance their chances of success.

The following research questions were addressed in this thesis to provide a guide in understanding the subject area and its practical implication in the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

RQ1: What impact have entrepreneurship training programmes had on entrepreneurs' capacity and determination in light of efforts by policymakers, educational institutions, global organisations, private entities, and NGOs?

This question provided insight into the applicability of reality, especially from the perspective of the region's public resources available to SMEs. Considering the collective efforts of policymakers, educational institutions, global organisations, private institutions,

and NGOs in implementing entrepreneurship training programs, there has been a significant impact on an entrepreneur's ability and intention to strive for success. By aligning curriculum and training modules with practical experience, educational institutions have equipped aspiring entrepreneurs with the necessary skills, knowledge, and mindset to address the challenges of job creation, growing and promoting businesses in Ghana and Kenya, respectively.

The involvement of policymakers in creating supportive policies and regulations has created a conducive environment for entrepreneurial activities to prosper. It also explored the general motivation factors that enhance positive intentions toward success. This will further benefit policymakers to understand and ensure the right policies are implemented to promote entrepreneurship within SMEs. The combined efforts of these stakeholders have fostered a culture of entrepreneurship, promoted innovation, and empowered individuals to pursue their business ideas. By addressing entrepreneurs' specific needs and aspirations, these initiatives have contributed to an increased entrepreneurial intention, motivation, and overall success rate. Furthermore, educational institutions will appreciate the essence of promoting training needs required to be incorporated into the curriculum. Also, this thesis will help NGOs and investors understand entrepreneurs' intentions and ensure that appropriate investments are encouraged to prevent the waste of resources. Finally, for SMEs, Promising and young entrepreneurs, and individuals, the study will highlight how they see themselves in the business ecosystem and pinpoint some push and pull factors that influence their intentions as entrepreneurs.

RQ2: How can the persistent rise in business failures among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Africa be interpreted in the context of efforts to enhance entrepreneurial capabilities through educational reforms and training initiatives?'

The thesis emphasises that while entrepreneurial education and training provide essential business acumen and concepts, there may be other triggers for entrepreneurial success. However, educational reforms and training programs fail to address SMEs' real-world challenges. In that case, entrepreneurs may need more skills and support to understand the difficulties of running a business effectively.

The findings from this thesis highlight various parameters that cause business failures among SMEs. Some key parameters and factors which will trigger an individual to undertake entrepreneurial training and education were addressed in this thesis. Several challenges pinpointed in the literature lead to the high failure rates of SMEs in Africa that align with the respondents' findings (see figure 8.1, 8.2, and 8.3). The continuous increase in business failure among Small and Medium Enterprises in sub-Saharan Africa indicates a potential failure in educational reforms and entrepreneurial training programs to enhance entrepreneurs' abilities. This observation contributes to the knowledge base of this thesis by highlighting the practical implications of the research findings.

The persistently high rates of business failure suggest a gap between the knowledge and skills imparted through educational initiatives and the practical requirements of entrepreneurship. This discrepancy highlights the need for continuous evaluation and improvement of entrepreneurial training programs, ensuring they align with the evolving needs and realities of the business environment. By addressing these gaps, educational reforms and training initiatives can better equip entrepreneurs to mitigate risks, adapt to changes, and enhance their chances of success, ultimately reducing the prevalence of business failure among SMEs. This highlighted the multiple areas in entrepreneurial training and education among SMEs that need to be addressed, which can positively impact the intention to strive for success. The findings from this thesis also provide an understanding of the

strength of purpose, considering several business failures despite several government policies and educational and training reforms in recent years in sub-Saharan African countries.

'What factors influence SMEs' desire to develop the intentions to undertake entrepreneurial training initiatives?'

The research question outlines various trigger events that induce existing and upcoming SMEs to adopt positive or negative traits that influence their intentions. These questions aided and contributed a quota to the vast knowledge of literature and enabled policymakers and other institutions to adopt the right policies, training, and strategies to promote entrepreneurs' business activities. The factors influencing SMEs' desire to develop intentions for entrepreneurial training initiatives are multifaceted and encompass various triggers of motivation and intention. The research question raised in the study serves as a significant contribution to the existing literature by addressing these influential factors.

The findings of this thesis found that emotional support and encouragement from family and friends are vital in triggering entrepreneurial intentions. Additionally, the thesis highlighted the importance of financial support and investments from family and friends as a core aim for African entrepreneurs, providing motivation and a foundation for their business activities.

Furthermore, the thesis emphasised the significance of practical experience and real-world exposure in entrepreneurial education. It pointed out the limitations of theoretical training alone and stressed the need for practical, hands-on approaches such as internships and apprenticeships. This recognition of the importance of practical training contributes to a deeper understanding of the triggers that drive SMEs' intentions to seek entrepreneurial training initiatives.

The findings provided valuable insights for policymakers and institutions, guiding them to adopt the right policies, training programs, and strategies that align with the triggers of motivation and intention identified in the study. By addressing these factors and promoting an environment conducive to entrepreneurship, policymakers and institutions can effectively support SMEs in pursuing entrepreneurial training and ultimately enhance their business activities.

8.1 Implication for Research

This thesis contributes to understanding the impact of entrepreneurial training on the intentions of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa. The researcher adapted Ajzen's (1991) and Shapero's (1982) frameworks and developed a conceptual framework (see figure 5.5) from the amalgamation of intention theories and models. This was applied in line with the research questions to generate a detailed interview guide to understand the entrepreneurial intentions of SMEs in Ghana and Kenya. The findings highlighted factors that influence start-up motivation. The most common conclusions of this thesis to understand start-up motivation are proxy to either an individual who was employed before starting a business or experiences and information which triggered them to leave a job voluntarily or involuntarily.

The implications of the research findings extend to the researcher, providing valuable insights and directions for future studies in entrepreneurial training and education.

Firstly, the research highlights the importance of considering actual entrepreneurs already in business operations as a sample size rather than solely focusing on students. This methodological approach contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial intentions and provides a richer dataset for analysis. Future researchers can build upon this approach by conducting longitudinal studies to explore further the long-term effects of entrepreneurial training on actual entrepreneurs' success and business outcomes.

Secondly, identifying research gaps and methodological deficiencies in the literature review underscores the need for rigorous and well-designed studies in the field. Researchers can address these gaps by incorporating more diverse and representative samples, employing mixed-methods approaches, and exploring additional variables that may influence entrepreneurial intentions and training effectiveness.

Moreover, the finding that entrepreneurial education and training are not the primary triggers for entrepreneurial intentions but provide essential business acumen and concepts highlights the importance of a holistic approach to entrepreneurship support. Researchers can delve deeper into understanding the specific factors that influence intentions and examine how educational reforms and training initiatives can be integrated with other supportive mechanisms, such as mentoring programs, access to financing, and networking opportunities.

Furthermore, the research contributes to the knowledge of entrepreneurship in different geographical contexts, specifically Ghana and Kenya. Future studies can expand upon this by exploring the cultural, economic, and institutional factors unique to other regions or countries, thereby enhancing our understanding of the contextual nuances of entrepreneurial training and its impact on intentions and business success.

By incorporating these implications, researchers can advance the field of entrepreneurial training and education and contribute to developing effective policies and strategies to support SMEs and promote entrepreneurial intention success.

Furthermore, the results of this thesis provided evidence that the trigger for start-up motivation of an individual is influenced by three factors; Self-efficacy, Entrepreneurial capacity and cognitive factors (see table 8.1). The findings of this thesis emerged that Start-up motivation encompasses a mental state that varies from individual to individual. Some entrepreneurs consider start-up motivations subjective, with much emphasis on personal

truth, and the way they think is mainly subjected to the intrinsic values and beliefs of the individual. This is because Start-up motivation is primarily triggered by several factors that change an entrepreneur's thinking.

In addition, the findings also revealed that factors that influence SMEs to undertake entrepreneurial education and training are summarised into three main categories: Entrepreneurial Awareness, Entrepreneurship for start-ups, and the dynamic nature of Entrepreneurship see (figure 8.3). Entrepreneurship Awareness" in this contest refers to the scope of knowledge surrounding entrepreneurship and individuals adopting a positive attitude to trigger the intent toward self-employment. Also, entrepreneurship for start-ups is to generally enhance or promote individuals who already have an existing idea or need to capitalise on societal problems to become self-employed and, finally, the dynamic nature of the entrepreneurial activity.' The category primarily focuses on individuals who are already existing entrepreneurs and want to incorporate dynamism in their business operations.

Geographically, This thesis was conducted in Ghana and Kenya, bringing a unique contribution to the sub-Saharan region to understanding the impact of entrepreneurial training on the intentions of SMEs. This study took into consideration actual entrepreneurs who are already in business operations. The previous studies only considered students as the primary sample size when issues related to entrepreneurial intentions.

8.2 Implications for Policies

Government policies have very little influence on the performance of SMEs, and SME implementers have very little knowledge about the existence of policies in both respective countries (Ghana and Kenya). Many educational institutions and policymakers are subjected to benefit from this thesis as it provides a differentiated view of the rationale why entrepreneurship training may, at first glance, have an insignificant or negative effect. The

researcher believes entrepreneurial training is a vital way to promote entrepreneurial activities.

Firstly, recognising the crucial role of family and friends in providing support and financial assistance to SMEs highlights the importance of incorporating policies that facilitate access to such support networks and encourage entrepreneurship within local communities.

Furthermore, identifying poor communication of policies in supporting SMEs calls for policy reforms to enhance transparency, accessibility, and dissemination of information to ensure effective implementation and support for SMEs. Poor communication of policies to support SMEs in Ghana and Kenya needs to be addressed and rectified. Most Sub-Saharan countries like Ghana, Kenya, and Rwanda frequently have several SMEs that fail within the first five years of business operation and have a high unemployment rate (Jones et al. 2018). Some researchers have argued that failures do not mean a business is out of business (Davis, 2015). In order to address these issues, the perceived effectiveness of government policies is essential for addressing the goals of SMEs (*see chapter 8.5*). The findings from this thesis have consistently strongly highlighted poor predictors of support over a range of policies to address the needs of SMEs. In the literature review, several studies have communicated evidence that the procedures in Ghana and Kenya effectively increase policy support, with mixed results (*see chapter 4.6*). However, the findings from the views of the respondent support otherwise. Most respondents believed that even though the policies exist, they are poorly communicated.

Additionally, the emphasis on the practical application of entrepreneurial education and the involvement of SMEs in university programmes underline the need for policy interventions that promote collaboration between educational institutions and industry stakeholders.

And also, paid apprenticeships should be encouraged, and this is because Apprenticeship training addresses the restrictions placed on classroom learning. This is because the findings revealed that it help exposes entrepreneurs to the practical world to understand their business or trade area. Also the literature review (see chapter 3.3.1), many researchers have argued that coaching is a set of techniques adopted to casually transmit learning skills, support, and other beneficial endeavours relating to a vocation or work from an expert or tutor. With this in mind, coaching and mentorship justify the approach of learning quickly at the workplace with valuable information, support, and direction. Another essential element is the incubatory business services; they provide the necessary training, which helps entrepreneurs start, expand, and sustain their businesses, while entrepreneurship education triggers individuals' interest in entrepreneurship. These findings provide valuable insights for policymakers to shape policies that foster an enabling environment for SMEs and promote entrepreneurial development.

8.3 Implications for Educators

To address this issue, entrepreneurship education and training are fundamental to understanding SMEs' nature and measures to mitigate risk. This can only be achieved when all the various stakeholders contribute to a quota understanding of actual entrepreneurs' proper entrepreneurial training or education (see figure 8.3).

Firstly, recognising that entrepreneurial training and education should not solely rely on classroom-based instruction emphasises the need for educators to incorporate non-classroom elements such as practical experiences, internships, and apprenticeships. This highlights the importance of creating opportunities for students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts and develop practical skills necessary for entrepreneurial success.

Furthermore, the emphasis on the role of family and friends as sources of support and motivation for aspiring entrepreneurs suggests that educators should encourage the involvement of these external stakeholders in the educational process. This can be achieved through guest lectures, mentorship programs, and networking events, providing students access to valuable connections, insights, and inspiration from successful entrepreneurs in their social networks. As discussed earlier, most SMEs are often family-owned businesses, and the family members perform the operational activities. Most of these individuals have access to formal or no entrepreneurship training, and most of this training transpires from generation to generation. Even though most governments across the Sub-Saharan African region have initiated several policies to promote entrepreneurship (see table 4.2 and table 4.1). The government must involve local communities by conducting the needs assessment, holding meetings in each region with SME implementers, employees and other stakeholders like the community leaders and suppliers and incorporating their findings in developing a new policy framework.

The findings also underpin the vital role of addressing communication gaps and ensuring that educational policies and initiatives supporting entrepreneurship are effectively communicated to educators. This necessitates the development of clear guidelines, training programs, and resources for educators to effectively deliver entrepreneurial training and education, and to keep them updated with the latest policies and practices. The literature reviews on training and education regarding entrepreneurship are subjected to three key elements; i) training and job creation, ii) training and intention iii) training and sustainability. However, to encourage teaching practices, similarly, findings from this thesis revealed that specialised modules should be created to address these key areas: Entrepreneurial Awareness, Entrepreneurship for start-ups, and the dynamic nature of entrepreneurship (figure 8.3). To

understand entrepreneurial training and apprenticeship programmes, it is vital to understand such training's essential role in entrepreneurs' intentions.

The findings also revealed that higher institutions (universities) should incorporate a practical approach to learning entrepreneurial education. Universities should align with actual SMEs with compulsory modules that each student will be assigned to a particular trade area as an internship (see figure 8.2). Considering these findings, it is evident that the scope of entrepreneurial training is already at the utmost. Hence, some will influence the entrepreneurial intention to address critical elements, as stated in figure 8.3. With this understanding in mind, educational institutions and educators should embrace diversity to encourage at various stages of undertaking entrepreneurial education and training.

In the context of these two countries, the findings revealed that family and friends provide vital sources of emotional, operational and financial support to keep entrepreneurs and business owners focused. From the results, family and friends form a more comprehensive client and customer who also act as networking platforms through word of mouth to promote business. It was also evident in both countries that family and friends provide the necessary support to address stress and working environment demands as well as deal with personal duties.

The findings emphasise the value of integrating classroom and non-classroom approaches, involving external stakeholders, and improving communication channels to enhance entrepreneurial education and training effectiveness for educators. These implications can guide educators in designing and implementing comprehensive and impactful entrepreneurial education programs that help individuals with the vital knowledge, skills, and support networks to succeed in their entrepreneurial endeavours.

8.4 Limitations of the study

Significant concerns have been about the global job crunch, such as the high unemployment, unfavourable conditions for start-up businesses, business failures, and vulnerable people, especially in most Sub-Saharan African countries. Business failures are rampant in most African countries (Adenle, 2017; Naicker & Nsengimana, 2022). Most businesses in Africa fail between three to 5 years of operation (Jones et al., 2018). This discourages most promising entrepreneurs from venturing into entrepreneurship and most SMEs in sub-Saharan Africa. Davis (2015) suggested that many barriers influence SMEs' intentions, especially in their early business operation stages.

This thesis encountered several shortfalls which limited the steady progress of the study;

First and foremost, **COVID-19**: did not only have consequences for various economies across the globe; research and societal activities were also affected, which has led to dramatic changes in how businesses act and consumers behave. The researcher had issues reaching several entrepreneurs due to most companies being shut down and travel restrictions in place the early and mid-way through this thesis.

Secondly, **Generalisation**: both respondents from Ghana and Kenya provided similar and identical results, which can be perceived as evidence of solid validation. However, it will serve as a basis for sampling a large number of participants across borders. The findings and conclusions of the study may be specific to the contexts of Ghana and Kenya or the particular sample of participants. It possibly will not be suitable to generalise the results to other countries or the whole Sub-Saharan African populations (Baah, et al., 2020).

Also, **Subjectivity and bias**: The study's findings may be influenced by the subjective perspectives and experiences of the participants. Potential biases in the data collection and analysis processes could impact the validity and reliability of the results. Similarly, Lorz (2011), the objective of this research is to understand the impact of entrepreneurial training

on the intentions of actual entrepreneurs rather than the nature of the training on the entrepreneurial intention of the individual. In order to promote and enhance the comparability among the nature of entrepreneurial training programmes, it is vital to understand the core values of good practises entrepreneurs undertake to ensure business sustainability, as described by Lorz (2011).

Researchers need to acknowledge these limitations and highlight areas for further research to build upon the existing knowledge and address these limitations in future studies.

Chapter 9: Recommendation

This chapter highlights the recommendation based on the findings of the thesis. The findings recommended that educational institutions prioritise entrepreneurial education and integrate it into diverse disciplines. Policymakers should develop supportive policies for SMEs, focusing on skills development, resource access, and market opportunities. Individuals should seek out social influencers and mentors to inspire and guide them. Building self-efficacy through training and support networks is also crucial. Addressing these recommendations can foster entrepreneurial intentions and contribute to the growth and success of SMEs.

9.1 Theory

Theoretical evidence must be captured to improve the whole concept of entrepreneurial training and education. Future research must highlight the key differences and understand the impact and appropriate approach to customising an entrepreneurship suit for specific target groups or individuals. From the literature review, there is a blur dimension in distinguishing between enterprise and entrepreneurship education, with both concepts overlapping.

It is also evident that entrepreneurial education and training are crucial for equipping individuals with the vital knowledge and skills base for business success. Therefore, educational institutions should focus on developing comprehensive and practical entrepreneurial curricula that go beyond theoretical concepts. This can be achieved by incorporating real-world experiences, internships, and apprenticeships, allowing students to apply their knowledge in practical settings.

Future research must highlight the key differences and understand the impact and appropriate approach to customising an entrepreneurship suit for specific target groups or individuals. From the literature review, there is a blur dimension in distinguishing between enterprise and entrepreneurship education, with both concepts overlapping.

The findings highlight the importance of considering factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions, such as personal experiences, social networks, and government policies. Future research should integrate various perspectives and theories to develop a more holistic understanding of entrepreneurship. This can contribute to developing comprehensive theoretical frameworks that capture the complexity of entrepreneurial motivations and intentions.

Furthermore, in other to Bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application in entrepreneurship is crucial. This can be achieved through collaborative efforts between academia, industry, and government agencies. Academics should actively engage with SMEs, entrepreneurs, and policymakers to ensure that theoretical concepts are relevant and applicable in real-world business contexts.

Finally, the field of entrepreneurship is dynamic, and new challenges and opportunities constantly arise. Therefore, it is essential to continually evaluate and update theoretical frameworks and models to reflect the changing landscape of entrepreneurship. This can be achieved through ongoing research, collaboration among scholars, and regular feedback from practitioners.

9.2 Policy

The findings of this thesis have significant policy implications, highlighting the crucial role of start-up motives and motivations in driving business growth. Policymakers should consider these factors when designing policies to support start-ups, regardless of whether individuals enter entrepreneurship due to unemployment or other reasons.

It is recommended that policy measures focus on addressing and nurturing the motivations that drive individuals to become entrepreneurs. This can be achieved by providing targeted support and resources that align with entrepreneurs' diverse motivations and needs. Policymakers should also prioritize providing entrepreneurial training and education beyond

theoretical knowledge and incorporate practical experiences, internships, and apprenticeships in collaboration with SMEs.

Moreover, policy initiatives aim to improve communication channels to effectively disseminate information about support programs and resources available to SMEs, ensuring that entrepreneurs are aware of and can access these opportunities. By considering the underlying motivations of entrepreneurs and implementing policies that cater to their specific needs, policymakers can foster a supportive environment that encourages entrepreneurial success and contributes to overall economic growth.

The government must engage local communities in a comprehensive needs assessment process to ensure effective policymaking. This can be achieved through region-specific meetings involving SME implementers, employees, community leaders, and suppliers. By incorporating the insights and perspectives of these stakeholders, the government can develop a new policy framework that addresses the unique requirements and challenges faced by SMEs in different regions across most Sub-Saharan African countries, thus fostering a more inclusive and responsive approach to economic development.

9.3 Practice

Universities and educators should address SMEs' needs, and modules should be developed to address their needs. Entrepreneurship education and training should be tailored to meet the specific needs of SMEs, taking into account their nature and unique challenges. Training programs should focus on practical approaches that address risk mitigation, financial management, marketing strategies, and other vital areas relevant to SMEs' operations. This will enable a student to apply the theoretical areas to address before venturing into their business operation.

To address this issue, entrepreneurship education and training should provide some fundamental approaches to understanding both SMEs' nature and measures to mitigate risk. This can only be achieved when all the various stakeholders contribute to a quota understanding of entrepreneurs' training needs. As discussed earlier, most SMEs are often family-owned businesses, and the family members perform the operational activities.

It is vital for all stakeholders, including government agencies, educational institutions, industry associations, and experienced entrepreneurs, to collaborate and share their knowledge and expertise. This can be achieved through partnerships, mentorship programs, and networking events, where successful entrepreneurs can share their experiences and guide aspiring entrepreneurs. Most of these individuals have access to formal or no formal entrepreneurship training, and most of this training transpires from one generation to the other. Most governments across the Sub-Saharan African region have initiated several policies to promote entrepreneurship.

Given the prevalence of family-owned businesses in the SME sector, there should be a focus on multigenerational learning and knowledge transfer. Experienced family members should actively participate in training programs to share their practical insights and experiences with younger generations. This can help preserve valuable business knowledge and ensure the continuity of successful entrepreneurial practices.

By implementing these recommendations, entrepreneurship education and training programs can better equip SMEs with the necessary skills, knowledge, and support to thrive in their business endeavours, contributing to the overall growth and development of the entrepreneurial intention within the business ecosystem.

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Appendix

Appendix A- Interview guide

PART - INTERVIEW GUIDE

Opening paragraph

A report by the African Development Bank (ADB) in 2021 indicates that Small and medium-sized businesses are likely to lead the economic recovery from the covid-19 pandemic on the African continent. Many reports and research conducted in the context of Africa indicates that the greatest challenges however are access to credit, which remains a hurdle for SMEs in Africa. This discourages most SMEs from to collapse. And many young and promising entrepreneurs are discouraged from engaging in entrepreneurial activities. Addressing this issue has been a priority for governments and regional organisations for several years to promote positive intention towards entrepreneurship.

Theme 1-Background and Experience

1. Have you started your own business? If so, when?
2. Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to (intend to or not intend to) become an entrepreneur?
3. Have you undertaken any entrepreneurial training before? If yes provide more information

Theme 2-Entrepreneurial Education and training

Over the years, there have been emerging debates evolving whether entrepreneurship can be taught or not. Interestingly, Timmons (1987) argued that entrepreneurial activities could be learned from one's personal experience. Putta (2014) also suggested that entrepreneurship can be nurtured and fostered which is transcend from parent to children without formal education or training. But Matlay (2018) argued differently that a variety of entrepreneurship education taught in classrooms contributes to developing both generic and specific decision-making skills of promising and future entrepreneurs.

4. Where is it appropriate, in your mind and experience, to undertake entrepreneurial training?
5. Do you think universities have the necessary platforms to inform people's skills to become entrepreneurs? If Yes can you explain?
6. What do you think about apprenticeship training before embarking on self-employment?
7. Do you consider, without entrepreneurial training your business can survive? Please give reasons for your answer.
8. In what circumstance would you consider further entrepreneurship training?

9. Technical and vocational training are crucially important for new business – to what extent do you agree with this statement?

No-Entrepreneurship training

Over the years, there have been emerging debates evolving whether entrepreneurship can be taught or not. Interestingly, there have been several kinds of research on entrepreneurship education (Colette, Frances and Claire 2005). Puta (2014) also believed that entrepreneurship training could transcend from parent to children without formal education or training. With this in mind, many researchers have argued several businesses can succeed without entrepreneurial training.

10. Reflecting on your own experience, how did you manage your business without any entrepreneurial training?

11. Do you without any entrepreneurial training your business can succeed? Please explain further....

12. In what circumstance will you consider entrepreneurial training....

13. At what point will you recommend entrepreneurial training to others? And why...?

Theme 3-Personal Experience

There has been an increase in debates in recent years surrounding whether SMEs should have practical experience in their business area in the form of apprenticeship, an internship in their society, or the real-world before commencing their actual business activity (Andreas, Rhodri, and Stephanie, 2006).

10. Reflecting on past experiences, in working life or elsewhere, which examples have played an influential role in your business?

11. Do you think being an entrepreneur means you have control over your life? Please explain further...

12. To what extent do you think that personal skills are vital to prevent business failure? Which skills, in particular?

13. What regret have you encountered, if any, as an entrepreneur?

14. Do you remember any memorable scenario or situation that made you consider entrepreneurship as a realistic career path?

Theme 4-Small business support and Government.

Government and associated bodies have launched many initiatives over recent years to support entrepreneurs and the SME sector. Programmes have been initiated to transform the dreams of inexperienced entrepreneurs to develop successful businesses into reality. Initiatives such as these are spreading all over the continent, providing capital support and guidance on how to manage and grow businesses.

15. In your experience, what major role has local and national government played to support SMEs?
16. Can you remember anytime a government policy has demoralised you, or demotivated you with regards to a particular business activity or entrepreneurial decision of yours?
17. Do friends and family play a key role in your business? If yes can you explain, to what extent?
18. Without support from family and friends can your business continue? Why?

Appendix B- Participant form

The Impact of Entrepreneurial training on Entrepreneurial intention of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa

An exploratory of Ghana, and Kenya.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Researcher:	Yaw Afari Personal information withheld. School of Business and Creative industry University of the West of Scotland
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Date: 11/09/2021

Research Title: The Impact of Entrepreneurial training on Entrepreneurial intention of SME's in Sub-Saharan Africa. A cross-sectional exploratory of Ghana, Kenya, and Rwanda

Invitation Paragraph

You are invited to participate in this study. However, before deciding to take part, it is essential that you read and understand both the reasoning for this study that is being conducted and what it entails. Therefore, please allow time to read the information carefully. If there are any questions that you wish to ask, please feel free.

To confirm, you **DO NOT** have to participate in this study if you do not wish to. Nevertheless, if you do decide to take part you can withdraw at any time without providing a reason.

Researcher Introduction

What is the purpose of the study? The area of study is to give a vivid understanding of how entrepreneurial training influence the intention of SMEs in Sub-Saharan African countries. The study will focus on entrepreneurship education and training to establish prominent traits and understand its impacts on entrepreneur's intention who are already operating their business. The study area will highlight on motivation traits that will influence the intents of entrepreneurs in Sub-Saharan African countries.

Why have I been chosen? You have been chosen because you are part of the SMEs found on the business registry

Do I have to take part? Participation in the study is entirely voluntary, and those involved can leave the study at any time.

What will I have to do if I take part? You only need to complete an interview

What are the possible benefits of taking part? It is important to share your experience and the challenges that affect your business. Research findings indicate that most businesses fail within 5 years. Your experience is important and influence other

What are the possible disadvantages and/or risks of taking part? Participating will not cause any harm or dissatisfaction.

What happens when the research study stops? You will be sent an email to inform you about the progress of the study

What if something goes wrong? Do not hesitate to contact when you feel something went wrong

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential? All data collected for this study will be deemed anonymous and kept strictly confidential

What will happen to the results of the research study? The findings will help other stakeholders understand the intentions of SMEs after undertaking entrepreneurship training

Who is organising and funding the research? Personal funding

Who has reviewed the study? Lead supervisor -Dr Robert J. Crammond; Second supervisor-Dr Dominic Elliott; Assessors- Dr Dalia Alazzeh

Confidentiality? All data collected will be kept confidential and anonymous

What if I want to find out more or have a complaint about the research? Yaw Afari, School of business and creative industry, University of the West of Scotland.

Email: [REDACTED] Personal information withheld.

TITLE: *The Impact of Entrepreneurial training on Entrepreneurial intention of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa; An exploration of Ghana, and Kenya.*

CONSENT FORM

Researcher:	Yaw Afari Personal information withheld. [REDACTED] School of Business and Creative industry University of the West of Scotland
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Please tick (✓), where appropriate

<i>I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet dated ... for the above study.</i>	
<i>I have had sufficient opportunity to ask questions.</i>	
<i>I understand that my participation in this study is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time, without stating any reason.</i>	
<i>I agree to the interview being audio recorded.</i>	
<i>I agree to any selected anonymised quotes being used in publications.</i>	
<i>I agree that this form bears my name and signature.</i>	
<i>I agree to participate in the study.</i>	

Name of Participant (PRINT)

Date

Signature

Name of Researcher (PRINT)

Date

Signature

One copy retained by participant; one received by researcher

DEBRIEFING SHEET

TITLE: *The Impact of Entrepreneurial training on Entrepreneurial intention of SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa; An exploration of Ghana, and Kenya.*

Many thanks for your participation in this study.

If you have any questions about the study, the research in general, or would like to find out about the results, then you can contact the sole researcher.

The details are below:

Yaw Afari

[REDACTED]

School of Business and Creative industry

University of the West of Scotland

[REDACTED]

Personal information withheld.

Again, thank you for your participation

Appendix E- Interview Data

GH-1001

Have you started your own business?

I have started my business in 2014 but was registered in 2018. Initially started my business without the hope of it growing.

Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to become an entrepreneur?

In 2012, when I was almost a year to graduate from university, the rate of unemployed graduates triggered me to start my own business. I decided to create something for myself in other not to depend on or join many unemployed graduates already in the system.

Before starting your business, did you have any form of entrepreneur training, either short term or long term?

Apart from the academic curriculum, which touched on briefly. But I have not had any in-depth training over the years. However, I studied some subject areas in the school that highlighted vital areas related to business but were not detailed.

Where is it appropriate, in your mind and experience, to undertake entrepreneurial training?

I think from the early stages, at least the middle school level. I was looking at the trend in Africa. This will trigger most individuals to have positive intentions towards establishing their own business at a younger age.

Do you think universities have the necessary platforms to inform people's skills to become entrepreneurs? If Yes, can you explain?

Not all, most universities do trains people to become entrepreneurs. But the issue has got to do with a student graduating and not using their skills. Most people are always waiting to be employed. You then question yourself what the importance of these universities is. You wonder if these universities actually train people to become entrepreneurs.

Universities should train students to identify business opportunities. Students should not graduate and rely on governments for jobs.

Do you think your business will survive without entrepreneurial training?

Individuals without entrepreneurial training or any basics understanding of managing a business their rate of survival is very low. It will take the inner quality of an individual to succeed. Most of my failures and early mistake as an entrepreneur were as a result of no entrepreneurial training. Because there were a lot of errors, I made in my business at the beginning. It really impacted my business heavily. As an entrepreneur, it took me four (4) years to register my business. I lost soo many contracts. I did not know the importance of business registration. I was able to 8secure funding and contracts as soon as my business was registered. I feel entrepreneurial training is very important. Because if I had entrepreneurial training. I would have no business registrations should have been one of the first things I should have done. Other aspects of training such as bookkeeping and position yourself for funds are vital knowledge you acquire through entrepreneurial training. I feel there are only a few people who will be successful without entrepreneurial training.

In what circumstance will you consider entrepreneurial training?

I will consider specific training depending on how its how it will help me improve my business. I will only take training that will address some of the challenges I'm facing in my business. I have learnt from mistakes and experience. I will be very selective on the kind of training which will help my business grow. If the training is something, I have already acquired through my experience or my failures .. I will not bother going to such training. I will only go for training which will help me improve my business, help address several challenges

So what are the significant challenges in your business?

Present capital to inject, as I do not have a clear picture of how I want my business to be in the next five years. Even though I have about 22 employees. I only visualise my business in the next five years, but it has not been documented down. I don't have a business plan. How to articulate my plans in a document is a significant challenge I have at the moment.

What about technical and vocational intuitions?

They are very importance. They also have the capacity to empower entrepreneurs. I have seen my competitors from vocational intuitions doing great jobs. They are technological incline.

Did any of your family and friends have a role to play on your career path as an entrepreneur?

Initially, my family did not support the idea. After 2-3 years of starting my business, they began to show massive support. Financial support for my family has been the best. My wife has been the backbone of emotional support. Without them, I won't have the zeal to continue what I do. Even though at the beginning, they wanted me to start a cooperate job or take a salary job after university. But after they saw I was showing soo much zeal. They then supported me.

Currently, my business can generate enough to cater to the cost, and we can manage our day-to-day activities. The financial support we can survive as a business but emotional support we need we need it in our everyday life as a business. An institution is, and emotional support are the most vital one.

Have you talked about your business with people?

Yes, especially young graduates who come to me for training. I try to encourage them to capitalise on opportunities rather than salary jobs.

In your own experience, do you think government policies support SMEs?

They are policies. Theoretically, they exist. The point is you go to some of these government department and they have nothing to offer you.

GH-1002**When did you start your business?**

My business started six years ago. The motivation was solely passion. I started dealing in leather products, from the wallet, belts, footwear, leather bags. I found it a way to make extra income. That was how I started my own business. A little bit of remodelling and customisation came into play. That's how my business has been evolved over the years.

The business is growing, and the production aspect is meeting demand.

What time in your life did you decide to start your own business?

I started this idea of trying to set myself up way back in school. I engaged in several business while I was in school, but they failed. I have always had the zeal to start my own business. I registered my business while I was still doing my national service. Even though after my national services, I had a well-paid job that worked for two years and quit. People thought I was crazy to quit a well-paid job to start my own business without prospects. I saw the journey. I saw the opportunities and wanted to take advantage of those opportunities. The business currently employ about 17 people who are mostly youth.

Did you have any form of training before venturing into entrepreneurship?

I can say yes and no. I had a few short term training as to when to spot opportunities. But I contribute my success to my former boss. He was my coach. He provided me with vital information, and I also learnt great from him. He was young and doing very well. I learnt a lot from. But entrepreneurial skills from him. I will say my training is a form of everyday experience. Even though after school, I enrolled into some design thinking modules with CEBS.

So these training, did you have them before starting your business or during your business?

The company was in operation, and also I was doing short-term training as a booster or overcoming challenges.

Do you think the universities have the capacities to influence individuals intentions?.

I feel they have the capacity to, but much investment has not been channelled to that aspect. I feel the kind of attention paid to those in different areas such as health, engineering the same should be directed toward entrepreneurship. I feel universities should put up modules that adapt to current circumstances. I feel they have the capacity and the resources, but it is a matter of changing the scope to adjust to the current approach existing in our daily lives. They should invest and train students at the early stages. They should empower students to change their mindset to accept entrepreneurship. There should be some level of practicality of entrepreneurship in our schools and universities. They should bring in seasonal entrepreneurs to come and impact the lives of these students. By the time they complete school, these students will have decided the kind of path they want to take.

What do you think about vocation and apprenticeship programmes.?

That's the best. Most of my employees are from vocational schools. They are specialist in local craftsmanship. They design the product to meet the prototype given to them. And their skills help my business module. I have also trained many people in the form of apprenticeships. Most of them have graduated from the training and have also started their business. In a way, I feel I am contributing to national development by training people to create a job for themselves. I feel proud of the process and whom my business is going. But the major issues has got to do with market access. I also help them to market themselves. And also, when these people finish these apprenticeships they do have the capital to start up their own business.

Do you have regrets about being an entrepreneur?

No, I have never had regrets for the path I choose. Although sometimes it is very challenging. The major challenge is staying relevant to meet customer demand. Also, when I was trying funding and got new equipment. When I was not making a profit at the initial stages, I was

scared my business might collapse. I invest so much into business just to stay up to date, from design thinking to production unit

In your own experience, do you think government policies support SMEs?

There are so many government policies available to support small businesses, but such policies' communication to SMEs is not effective. Most of us don't know whether these policies exist. The mode of communication is poor. These policies are sometimes not well defined. There are no clarities in these policies. Most people do not know much about these policies, even if they exist. And such policies are not well defined. The process to even to go through to get a grant is not even

Do friends and family play a key role in your business? If yes, can you explain to what extent?

My wife has been the mains source of my finance. She believed in my dream, supported me throughout. She has been the primary source of support. My family also helped me. They invested into me. My friends were my customers. They motivated me and encouraged me. I was constantly accepting feedback. It made me meet the customer satisfaction they were always looking out for.

KY-1001

Have you started your own business?

Yes, I have started my business, and it's ongoing, and it's in its four years now. I decided to start my own business because of an experience in the security area.

Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to become an entrepreneur?

I was once working for a security company, and I understood the dynamism of how the security companies work. This dynamism includes how security agencies resource security personnels and mediator of businesses or organisations looking for people with security licences. Also, looking at the benefit I was getting from my previous jobs, it was not appropriate enough. I was mostly demoralised because my company could not fight for our welfare, and I always stood at risk of losing my licence. These were the key factors that motivated me to establish my own business with about 20 employees. My business aims to make some organisations know the track history of some Security personals with licences. This will give the opportunity for them to rate the security personals and also the security personals will learn how much to pay rate the will be paid for each assigned duty.

Before you started your business, did you have any form of entrepreneur training, either short term or long term?

I have had entrepreneurial training before I commenced my business before an individual start operating a business, it's mandatory for individuals to undergo some level of training as to how to handle people. The training is a six-month training and a mandatory examination is followed up. I have also had the opportunity to attend a lot of pieces of training because I studied human resources at the university level. I had a chance to participate in a lot of entrepreneurial training. In terms of my security, I had to opportunity to undertake training which involves risk assessment, understanding people and how people react to different situations form different background.

Where is it appropriate, in your mind and experience, to undertake entrepreneurial training?

In my view before you can achieve a successful business, it is important to undertake several trainings to understand your business and everything related to management. Periodic trainings are also important when it comes to managing a business.

Do you think entrepreneurship can be taught or not?

Currently the trend of entrepreneurship is changing. With the internet, anybody can start operating their business anywhere, anytime and anyplace. I believe that entrepreneurship can be taught or not taught. Most people are successful operating their business without any entrepreneurial training. I believe from my experience if you understand your business, they don't need entrepreneurial training. People without the required skills can employ people with the required skills to take up most managerial roles. But however, it better to run successful business when an individual has entrepreneurial training to understand the kind of industry they operate

Do you think your business will survive without entrepreneurial training?

I can say Yes and No that the universities has got the requisite skills to equip individuals with the required training. Yes because, you get to understand the latest trends and issues related to your business and how to deal with them. With regards No, there are no much internship avenues during schools where individuals will and practice what have been taught in schools and at the same time ask question in class about their experience. I have learnt that what is taught in class is not what is really what is happening in the real world.

What do you think about apprenticeship training before embarking on self-employment?

It is important for people to have some apprenticeship. I firmly believe that it gives them the required individuals the skills and confidence. Individuals get to understand the marketing strategies, source of funding and how the business is managed. The apprenticeship gives individuals first-hand information about their trade area. You learn to understand people that have already been employed and also understand whether the business is making a profit or lost. The also inmoves technical and vocational training as well. They prepare individuals with hands-on experiences.

Reflecting on your own experience, how did you manage your business without any entrepreneurial training?

However, the business I started was based on personal experiences and my field in HR. I have managed a lot of people, this has given me the opportunity to understand people and undertake strategic decisions.

Critical attention should be paid to business especially at the initial stages, usually within the first year of operation.

Do you regret your life as an entrepreneur?

I do not regret as entrepreneur. I will have regret if my business is not in operation. So far, my business is running even though there are high risk, I try as much as possible to find solutions to mitigate risk.

Do friends and family play a key role in your business? If yes can you explain, to what extent?

My friends and family have been influential in my business. It is very difficult to start a business if your friends and family do not support your business. Some friends and family patronise my services, which serves as revenue. Some friends and family refer clients to my business. The first contact of motivation for establishing a business is mostly friends and family. The support from them are sometimes not necessarily financial but can be in the form of advice.

In your experience, what major role has local and national government played to support SMEs?

The government has been very influential, especially when this period of Covid. There has been several trainings initiated by the government for business to understand the impact of the various on business and how to mitigate risk. However, government should make some sort of funding available for business to flourish. Government should provide the necessary support to promising entrepreneurs right from training till the beginning and during their business operation.

KY-1002

Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to (intend to or not intend to) become an entrepreneur?

Yes I have started my business in 3 years now. I work and was not getting recognition for the innovative idea was giving to the company and not also being acknowledged. I felt I was mostly taken advantage of and this heavily influenced my decision to become an entrepreneur. This is when I vowed not to work for anyone else. So, my decision was influenced by personal experience.

Where is it appropriate, in your mind and experience, to undertake entrepreneurial training?

No entrepreneurial training. The only experience I had was work experience and I kind of studied along the way. The course I studied at university was accounting and its entrepreneurial related. This also to some extent influence on my journey as entrepreneurial. I personally think with other courses, entrepreneurship courses and training are not that really enforced on people that much unless you want to do it. This is something most educational intuitions can look into it and improve.

Some business do not need any entrepreneurial training but business which requires certification, requires or individual that requires some sort of certification before they start their business requires entrepreneurial training to ensure their business run smoothly.

Technical and vocational training are crucially important for new business – to what extent do you agree with this statement?

Apprenticeship, from my experience I will recommend to anybody to have some sort of apprentices training before they start their business. I wont recommend to any one to start on their own. I will always recommend entrepreneurial training to people before they start their business. The training serves as a bonus to them because it make managing their business easier to operate. Constant learning and reading about your trade area helps. I made a lot of mistakes along the line, I never had any mentor. My experiences in my previous job has helped me in my business. Things like customer services, I had to learn it from my previous job. Experience is really important to run a business, because you need to know how to speak to people, you should know how to market.

Most business can survive without entrepreneurial training. There are basic skills I learnt personally myself which is currently applicable in my business without any entrepreneurial training. It depends on the kind of business as well. The training will boost performance. But business will survive without training. Business-related to an individual, a specialist will need some level of training to keep their business running. However not the training aspect alone can influence peoples intention but other factors comes into play. It also depends on the industry as well. The training alone is not a deal-breaker.

What regret have you encountered, if any, as an entrepreneur?

I currently have control of over my life. I can decided whether I want to work or not. I can also outsource some of my services to people. This does make me to be heavily involved all the time. When I used to work for other companies, they decided my working hours (9-5pm).

To what extent do you think that personal skills are vital to prevent business failure? Which skills, in particular?

Personals skills are very important to ensure business success. Customers services skills is something

I developed whiles I was working for other people. I was also working in development teams which gave me the opportunity to interreact and train people as well. my skills is a key and huge impact on establishing my business.

I have encourage several challenges which demotivated along the line as an entrepreneur. Sometimes dealing with angry customers or clients and want to get rid of them but you can not get rid of them because you need money into your business. And also when you are a small business owner and you are to manage and balance everything together, thus being the manager, the accountant, boss, customer service, the web designer.. everything. Or you try to bring someone on board and not getting the level of efficiency you expect from them can be very frustrating.

Do friends and family play a key role in your business? If yes can you explain, to what extent?

Family and friends do not play any direct influence in my business; I won't say they play a direct key role because some of them don't understand my business, especially when they have less interest in the industry you operate. For example when their mindset is not geared towards entrepreneurship. For example, my parents are not entrepreneurs and anything about entrepreneurship they do not want to hear it. My parents are old school... get your degree, get a job in a company. So they are very traditional in that sense. They don't run businesses themselves. So when I try to talk about entrepreneurship, they are not really interested. Even though without their interest, it does not really impact my business. But in terms of emotional support that are always there for me. My husband, siblings, friends are always there for me emotionally. In terms of financial support I don't really get that because they mostly don't understand my business so they fail to support.

Without their support, my business can still move on. If I have an idea, I go ahead to execute my idea. I feel I am someone I can personally survive. I'm quite an independent person in nature and usually I don't wait for validation to do things. But honestly, support from family will be fantastic but it's not a deal-breaker.

In your experience, what major role has local and national government played to support SMEs?

Government support has been fantastic, especially within the current pandemic era. There has been financial support for small business struggling to survive. This financial aid and grant has been great. Without financial aid my business will really struggle to survive.

GH-1004

Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to (intend to or not intend to) become an entrepreneur?

Yes I have started my business last 3 years. When I finished university, I was working really hard for a highly reputable company; I felt I was not appreciated, and I was not getting what I wanted. I was picking up shifts and covering for other colleagues because we were short of staff. When it got to the time I was to be promoted, it was given to someone else. The person was employed 2 weeks before the promotion, but he was given the promotion. This really motivated me to start my own business. I opened a similar business and I have become a competitor. I have about 11 workers working for me.

Have you undertaken any entrepreneurial training before? If yes provide more information

I never had any formal training in entrepreneurship. But I sometimes have some self-studies, either by browsing through Google and other websites. I don't think the universities have got the required platform to train people in entrepreneurship. The universities train people to become scientists and other skills. To be an entrepreneur is a broad area. Even though most universities provide some sort of grants for individuals with entrepreneurial ideas which are mostly theoretical based. It is very difficult to see some sort of practical entrepreneurial training from the universities.

What do you think about apprenticeship training before embarking on self-employment?

When individuals engage in apprenticeship it gives them the real exposure to the business of interest. But it won't give them an overall overview as to how to manage their business. But basic practical skills can be acquired, which forms the bases and understating of the business. This will make their service delivery unique. However, being an apprentice will not give you managerial skills in most cases. But this solely depends on the kind of business you want to do as well.

Do you consider, without entrepreneurial training your business can survive? Please give reasons for your answer.

Without entrepreneurial training most business can survive. This is if you don't have the necessary skills to get your business moving, you can hire people with the skills to do the job for you. Even though you need to have the basic skills. But when things become tough or you find yourself in a tight position, you can hire people to do the job for you and pay them. But certainly, entrepreneurial training helps in operating a business and entrepreneurial training does not guarantee successful business.

Do you think being an entrepreneur means you have control over your life? Please explain further...

When you are an entrepreneur and you manage your own business, you intend to work hard and put in extra hours to ensure things move smoothly. You turn to control your business at your own pace, you know when to take breaks. You also gain your privacy and freedoms as well.

Can you remember anytime a government policy has demoralised you, or demotivated you with regards to a particular business activity or entrepreneurial decision of yours?

Every business needs to understand the regulatory underline depending on the business in other not to fall foul of the law. And secondly when managing your business, you must constantly learn, read and be ready to take risk.

Do you have a regret as an entrepreneur?

Since I started my business there has been challenging times. Especially devoting more hours and thinking about another aspect of my business. (this includes how to get clients, how to get my products on board, how to meet clients needs, among others). When this comes in mind, I wish I was working for myself and getting paid.

Without support from family and friends can your business continue? Why?

Family are friends are very important very in my business. They mostly provide you with the necessary support in terms of finance and emotional support.

In your experience, what major role has local and national government played to support SMEs?

Government support has been visible especially when this pandemic started.

GH-1005

When did you start your business?

My business started 4 years ago. The motivation was solely passion. I started dealing in leather products. From wallet, belts, footwear footwear, leather bags. I found it a way to make extra income. That was how I started my own business. A little bit of remodelling and customisation came into play. That's how my business has been evolve over the years. The business is growing, and the production aspect is meeting demand.

What time in your life did you decide to start your own business?

I started this idea of trying to set myself up way back in school. I engaged in several business while I was in school but it failed. I have always had the zeal to start my own business. I registered my business while I was still doing my national service. Even though after my nation services I had a well paid job which worked for two years and I quit. People thought I was crazy to quit a well paid job to start my own business without prospect. I saw the journey, I saw the opportunities and wanted to take advantage of those opportunities.

Did you have any form of training before venturing into entrepreneurship?

I can say yes and no. I had a few short term training as to when to spot opportunities. But I contribute my success to my former boss. He was my coach. He provided me with vital information and I also learnt great from him. He was young and doing very well. I earned a lot from. But entrepreneurial skills from him. I will say the my training is a form of informal experience. Even though after school I enrolled into some design thinking modules with CEBS.

So these training, did you have them before starting your business or during your business?

The company was in operation and also I was doing short-term training as booster or to overcome challenges.

Do you think the universities have the capacities to influence individuals intention?.

I feel they have the capacity to, but much investment has not been channelled to that aspect. I feel the kind of attention paid to those in different areas such as health, engineering the same should be directed toward entrepreneurship. I feel universities should put up modules that adapt to current circumstances. I feel they have the capacity, they have the resources, but it is a matter of changing the scope to adapt to current approach existing in our daily lives. They should invest and train students at the early stages. They should empower student, to change their mindset to accept entrepreneurship. There should be some level of practicality of entrepreneurship in our schools and universities. They should bring in seasonal entrepreneurs to come and impact into the lives of these students. By the time they complete school, this student will have decided the kind of path they want to take.

What do you think about vocation and apprenticeship programmes.?

That's the best. Most of my employees are from vocational schools. They are specialist in local craftsmanship. They design product to meet the prototype given to them. and their skills really help my business module. I have also train a lot of people in the form of apprenticeship. Most of them have graduate from the training and have also started their business. In a way, I feel I am contributing to national development by training people to create job for themselves.

I feel proud of the process and who my business is going. But the major issues has got to with access to market. I also help them to market themselves. And also when these people finish these apprenticeship they do have capital to start up their own business.

Do you have regrets of being an entrepreneurial?

No, I have never had regrets for the path I choose. Although sometimes it is very challenging. The major challenge is staying relevant to meet customer demand. Also when I was trying funding and get new equipment. At the initial stages when I was not making a profit, I was scared my business might collapse. I invest so much into business just to stay up to date from design thinking to production unit

In your own experience, do you think government policies support SMEs?

There are so many government policies available to support small businesses, but the communication of such policies to SMEs are not effective. Most of us don't know whether these policies exist. The mode of communication is poor. These policies are sometimes not well defined. There are no clarities in these policies. Most people do not know much about these policies even if they exist. And such policies are not well defined. The process to even to go through to get grant is not even

Do friends and family play a key role in your business? If yes can you explain, to what extent?

My wife has been the mains source of my finance. She believed in my dream, support me through out. She has been the main source of support. My family also supported me. They invested into me. My friends were my customers. They motivated me and encourage me. I was constantly accepting feedback. They made me meet the customer satisfaction they were always looking out for.

KY-1003

Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to (intend to or not intend to) become an entrepreneur?

Yes I have started my business in 7 years now. My decision to become an entrepreneurial was as result of a bad experience. I was working tirelessly, putting in a lot of work and was not getting recognition for what I was entitled to and not also being acknowledged. I felt I was mostly taken advantage of and this heavily influenced my decision to become an entrepreneur. This is when I vowed not to work for any one else. So, my decision was influenced by personal experience. I started a tourism company which most expatriate patronise our service. This business has employed many people. I have about 35 employees. This employees are both full time and part time staffs.

Where is it appropriate, in your mind and experience, to undertake entrepreneurial training?

I started my business without any form entrepreneurial training. The only experience I had was work experience and I kind of studied along the way. The course I studied at university was accounting and its entrepreneurial related. This also to some extent influence on my journey as entrepreneurial. I personal think with other courses, entrepreneurship courses and training are not that really enforced on people that much unless you wanting to do it. This is something most educational intuitions can look into it and improve.

Some business do not need any entrepreneurial training but business which requires certification, requires or individual that requires some sort of certification before they start their business requires entrepreneurial training to ensure their business run smoothly.

Technical and vocational training are crucially important for new business – to what extent do you agree with this statement?

Apprenticeship, from my experience I will recommend to anybody to have some sort of apprentices training before they start their business. I wont recommend to anyone to start on their own. I will always recommend entrepreneurial training to people before they start their business to avoid mistakes. The training serves as a bonus to them because it make managing their business easier to operate. Constant learning and reading about your trade area helps. I made a lot of mistakes along the line, I never had any mentor. My experiences in my previous job has helped me in my business. Things like customer services, I had to learn it from my previous job. Experience is really important to run a business, because you need to know how to speak to people, you should know how to market.

Most business can survive without entrepreneurial training. There are basic skills I learnt personally myself which is currently applicable in my business without any entrepreneurial training. It depends on the kind of business as well. The training will boost performance. But business will survive without training. Business-related to an individual, a specialist will need some level of training to keep their business running. However not the training aspect alone can influence peoples intention but other factors comes into play. It also depends on the industry as well. The training alone is not a deal-breaker.

What regret have you encountered, if any, as an entrepreneur?

I currently have control of over my life. I can decided whether I want to work or not. I can also outsource some of my services to people. This does make me to be heavily involved all the time. When I used to work for other companies, they decided my working hours (9-5pm).

To what extent do you think that personal skills are vital to prevent business failure? Which skills, in particular?

Personals skills are very important to ensure business success. Customers services skills is something

I developed whiles I was working for other people. I was also working in development teams which gave me the opportunity to interreact and train people as well. Personal skills have had a huge impact on my business. I have encountered several challenges that demotivated me as an entrepreneur. Sometimes dealing with angry customers or clients and want to get rid of them, but you can not get rid of them because you need money for your business. And also, when you are a small business owner, you are to manage and balance everything together, thus being the manager, accountant, boss, customer service, web designer.. everything. Alternatively, you try to bring someone on board and not getting the level of efficiency you expect from them can be very frustrating.

Do friends and family play a key role in your business? If yes can you explain, to what extent?

Family and friends do not play any direct influence in my business; I won't say they play a direct key role because some of them don't understand my business, especially when they have less interest in the industry you operate. For example when their mindset is not gear towards entrepreneurship. For example, my parents are not entrepreneurs and anything entrepreneurship they do not want to hear it. My parent are old school... get your degree, get a job in a company. So they are very traditional in that sense. They don't run businesses themselves. So when I try to talk about entrepreneurship, they are not really interested. Even though without their interest, it does not really impact my business. But in-terms of emotional support that are always there for me. My husband, siblings, friends are always there for me emotionally. In terms financially support I don't really get that because they mostly don't understand my business so they fail to support.

Without their support, my business can still move on. If I have an idea, I go ahead to execute my idea. I feel I am some I can personal survive. I'm quite an independent person in nature and usual I don't wait for validation to do things. But honestly, support family will be fantastic but its not a deal-breaker.

In your experience, what major role has local and national government played to support SMEs?

Government support has been fantastic, especially within the current pandemic era. There has been financial support for small business struggling to survive. This financial aid and grant has been great. Without financial aid my business will really struggle to survive.

KY-1004

Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to (intend to or not intend to) become an entrepreneur?

I started my business learning from grandparent. My grandparent always took me to their business whenever they go. The business was a family owned business and I learnt a lot form them. I have always wanted to be like them. Their business was successful so it motivated me to also establish myself

Have you undertaken any entrepreneurial training before? If yes provide more information

I have had the opportunity to attend a few entrepreneurial training to advance my self to gain the necessary skills.

Do you without any entrepreneurial training your business can succeed? Please explain further

I feel entrepreneurial training helps most business to succeed

What regret have you encountered, if any, as an entrepreneur?

It was time consuming and stressful. But I do not regret embarking on this entrepreneurial journey

Without support from family and friends can your business continue? Why?

Family are friends are very important very in my business. They mostly provide you with the necessary support in terms of finance and emotional support.

KY-1008

Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to (intend to or not intend to) become an entrepreneur?

So has I finished campus I got an internship at on the cooperate firms which deals in design, three months later, they converted me to a permanent role of the company rather than just normal job. These started me with more serious form my entrepreneurial journey.

Yes, I have started my business back in campus in the university of Nairobi, school of the art and design, which was in 2009 when I was in my second year.

Have you undertaken any entrepreneurial training before? If yes provide more information

I have not taken any entrepreneurial training before, I wish I could have taken a professional entrepreneurial programme. I have just had this student learning attitude towards entrepreneurship. Just understating how things works and aligning them to the goals. This has gotten me to the point I am now.

Do you without any entrepreneurial training your business can succeed? Please explain further

Its very hard for a business to succeed, but that comes in the context of time. I feel entrepreneurial training is important or justifiable guarantee or success in a business typically in the traditional way to combat business failures. Especially in the early stages of a business.

What do you think about apprenticeship training before embarking on self-employment?

Apprenticeship is important. Most of employees who had apprenticeship training always produce fantastic results and outcome. They are already knowledge and have energy to produce the needed task or job when given. They have the skills and the exposure already.

To what extent do you think that personal skills are vital to prevent business failure? Which skills, in particular?

I feel that it is very important for entrepreneurial training to be embedded into the day-to-day educational system and the curriculum. It was runs concurrently. The educational system only encourages people to employment rather than entrepreneurship. People are scared of going out there to try and do business es. So it becomes very hard to introduce this kind of setting

up business after the tertiary level. Because they were not introduced at their early stages of their life. They are not present in the curriculum and the education systems.

There are so many ways to learn things from. It was important to formalise how people learn things in business, that's how formal and entrepreneurial education came in. it is important for one to be open minded in learning because learning is out there and its literally free. Because of formalisation, the aspect of value was attached to it in terms of money. From reflections from my own experience, I feel or it is important one annex the entrepreneurs lessons at a time.

I don't have any formal entrepreneurial training, but I was humble enough and willing to learn irrespective of my level of education and my financial capability, learn from the start, learning from the go, learning from the people who are in the entrepreneurship area. Learning does not end, so what we are referring in this context is formal entrepreneurship training. My way of learning helped to for my business to succeed. It's a matter to responding to change and understanding the dynamics of the business in rational to local and international context

KY1009

Have you started your own business?

Yes, I have started my own business . my business I started in 2012 though it didn't pick up immediately ,in 2013 is when i vented into it seriously ,it wasn't easy then I went on till now .there has been so many challenges along the way but on and on i have been able to do it .

can you recall a time in your life that change your heart and mind to intend to or not to become entrepreneur.

yes, I was paid really poorly but I had experience of what I'm doing ,so i thought maybe if I start my own thing how will it be .so i gave it a try and for sure there was a big difference .what I was earning i was earning back then was peanuts. Starting my own business really though at first it was hard i was struggling but there was hope ,I did so much ,the money that I, the profit that i was making were good some point after the first time the second day is normally the hardest .Yes but after that things was that much much better.

Have you undertaking any entrepreneur training before if yes provide more information?

No I have not taking any entrepreneur training before it was i just started with the experience that I had and I picked up from there and moved on .

where is it appropriate in your mind and experience to undertake entrepreneur training?

I believe taking an entrepreneur training is it is good and can help you in so many ways .you find maybe your skill in what you are doing but the financial needs you don't know how to

manage the finances and so many others so you might be knowing what to do but also you need marketing bits ,you will need .there is so many things that you need to learn about .

In my view it's appropriate to do the training .Do you think universities have the necessary platform to inform people's skills to become entrepreneurs? if yes, can you explain .

Yes universities have the platform because they prepare student for business activities. It only that not many people want to venture into business but once you gone through the academia of journey in the university, such business programmes I studied study add and sharpen my skills. you have and it will be good for the business.

What do you think about apprenticeship training before embarking on self-employment?

I think apprenticeship is a good approach for every before embarking on self-employment because that way you get to learn so many other things in the business part the financial part the marketing bit and customer care ,how to deal with customer are very important .so having that in mind and being trained in all those things will help you on self-employment .

Do you consider without entrepreneur training your business can survive, please give reasons for your answers ...

Yes I believe your business can survive. All you need is to be smart in how you are tackling the business. I know so many who have not done the entrepreneur training but their business is driving .it's all about what you have in mind.

Are you passionate about that business?

First if you are not passionate that business will never survive, but if you are passionate you will give it your all, you will do anything that you need to do to make that business work. Another thing is when you are going into the business, I'm sure you have a reason so let your reason be let, have a reason, ask yourself why are you doing this ,that way I know you will survive . Training is good but with time if you haven't done any training before I am sure with time you will get to do those training as you go on with your business .

In what circumstances will you consider entrepreneur training?.

I will consider this as and maybe you are done with your training earlier and there are bits that you need to understand more to the deeper. So I believe that is what further entrepreneurship training means.

Technical and vocational training at crucial important for new business to what extent do you agree with that statement?.

It is very true it is really good for someone who is venturing into a self employment to have a bit of training or something .there are so many things that are being introduced in the world right now and then traditional way of doing business is in the past ,it will be really important to have some training and it will help you in your business

Reflecting on your own experience, how did you manage your business without any entrepreneur training.

My skills and passion are the core that really pushed towards my business. I was able to ,i manage to the business without the training but of course with time i used to read books i used to talk to my other entrepreneurs and also attend seminars and trainings that were organized by other organizations and it really helped.

Do think without any entrepreneur training your business can succeed,

yeah like i said earlier, passion, why? Why are you doing the business?

So business can succeed but you have to be really determined. In what circumstances will you consider entrepreneur training with the new way of doing things in life? You need training to know all those things like social media, marketing, digital marketing and so many things. It's good to have entrepreneur training to know what is going on in the world ,what's new and what's going on so that your business can also be up to date . you don't want to do business the old way. you want to do business the new way because that is the only way your business can thrive.

At what point will I recommend entrepreneur training to others and why?

i will recommend entrepreneur training to others to learn about the new things that is happening in the world, the new market, that way you are not left behind.so I recommend training to others so that they can learn the new tricks in the market. Reflecting on past experience in what life or elsewhere which examples have played an influential role in your business. I will say customer care because where I have worked before there were a lot of I was dealing with customers directly and then I learnt how to deal with the client. Customer care is really important in your business and that has really played a big role in my business.

Do you think being an entrepreneur means you have control over your life? Please explain further. Oww yes, you get to plan so ahead so you have control over your life. unlike employment you have to go from eight to five. Here you plan though it really demands a lot of time but you get to plan yourself.

To what extent do you think that personal skills have actually prevented business failure?

Which skills in particular, yes personal skills are very factual to prevent business failure because that is the main thing needed in business. The skill in doing what you do in the business if you are good in IT ,if you have that skill that is what is really needed there. And now other things will come in but that skill is the key.

what regrets have you encountered if any as an entrepreneur.

i want say i have no regrets, i know i have had my share of hard times but i have never regretted the days that i know things are really low maybe you have not made anything but it has it own ups which i am really happy about and i am glad i did venture into entrepreneurship.

Do you remember any memorable scenario or situation that made you consider entrepreneurship as a realistic career path?

i will say i was pushed, i found myself into entrepreneurship because of a few things, jobs were hard to come by so the job that i could get was not paying well so i decided to try

entrepreneurship and i gave it my all because that was the only thing i had so i took it rain with it so fast.

In your experience what made the role of local and national government play in to support your business?

or i will say the government have tried so much to support the SMEs. You will say in government tenders there is a slot for you that I took advantage of. I did a number of projects for the government and yeah I will say that's encouraging and if only they can continue that way it will really help the youth.

Can you remember anytime the government policy has demobilized you or demotivated you with regards to a particular business activities or entrepreneur?

oh yes i remember there are times you could do a project or do some business activities for the government and they delay in payments. Their policy is that they will pay you thirty days as the youth of SMEs am starting business i don't have the money to wait for thirty days so most likely will take a loan and if the money delays the interest keeps accumulating so there were times you will do something for government and instead of you and the thirty days they take even three months without paying you. And it's really demoralizing to do such business .you feel like giving up but you have to hold on.

Do friends and family play a role in a business?

I will say and no, yes because some of them when i was really looking for, when i was starting i didn't have the capital and all that and sometimes if you approach them and ask them for a loan some helped even some of my friends and another thing also is no because sometimes family think they are really helping you and feels like they don't want to, so it's a yes and no thing, yes for some and no for some so yeah

without support from family and friends can your business continue?

Yes without support from family and friends, your business can continue because most of the time the people who are your clients actually most of the clients are not even your family members these are people you meet and they trust you, but for family they will start asking so many questions when they have and smallish will just testing, I knew you could not do this thing so yeah. without friends and family you can succeed, you can go very far, you can still do your business and go back home and laugh with them. Thank You.

Appendix F: Demographic participant for the Pilot studies

<i>Samples</i>	Gender	Nature of Business	Level of Education	Previous work experience	Years of Experience	Number of employees
<i>G1, 2021</i>	F	Retail (service)	Masters	Yes	7	8
<i>G2, 2021</i>	M	Security (service)	Degree	Yes	5	32
<i>G3, 2021</i>	M	Cleaning (service)	Masters	Yes	6	16
<i>G4, 2021</i>	M	Retail (service)	Degree	Yes	4	7
<i>E1, 2021</i>	F	Retail (Service)	Degree	Yes	8	10
<i>E2, 2021</i>	F	Cleaning (Service)	Degree	Yes	4	20
<i>E3, 2021</i>	F	Retail (Service)	Degree	Yes	2	12
<i>E4, 2021</i>	M	Pharmaceutical (service)	Masters	Yes	3	10

Appendix G: Data Analysis

Themes/Question	Key Extract	Initial coding	Cohesive themes
<p>Theme 1-Start-up Motivations</p> <p>1. Have you started your own business? If so, when?</p> <p>2. Can you recall a time in your life that changed your heart and mind to (intend to or not intend to) become an entrepreneur?</p>	<p>“My business started six years ago. The motivation was solely passion.”</p> <p><i>“Initially started my business without the hope of it growing”</i></p> <p><i>“I decided to start my own business because of an experience in the security area.”</i></p> <p>“I started this idea of trying to set myself up way back in school. I engaged in several business while I was in school, but they failed”</p> <p>“When it got to the time I was to be promoted, it was given to some else. The person was employed two weeks before the promotion, but he was given the promotion. This really motivated me to start my own business.”</p> <p>“Personal skills have a huge impact on your business. I have encountered several challenges which demotivated along the line as an entrepreneur.”</p> <p>“I engaged in several business while I was in school, but it failed. I have always had the zeal to start my own business. I registered my business while I was still doing my national service.”</p> <p><i>“The rate of unemployed graduates triggered me to start my</i></p>	<p>Motivation, Passion</p> <p>Desire, Substantive growth ambition</p> <p>Experience</p> <p>Experience, entrepreneurial training</p> <p>Better reward, Welfare, Recognition Lack of promotion</p> <p>Skills</p> <p>Zeal, desire, experience</p>	<p>Theme 1</p> <p>Cognitive factors</p> <p>-Good/Bad Experience -Entrepreneurial training -Practical training</p> <p>Self-efficacy Skills Zeal Desire Motivation Passion Ambition fear</p> <p>Entrepreneurial capacities</p> <p>-Spot opportunities, -Unemployment rate -welfare -uncertainty</p>

<p>3. Have you undertaken any entrepreneurial training before? If yes provide more information</p>	<p><i>own business. I decided to create something for myself in other not to depend on or join many unemployed graduates already in the system."</i></p> <p><i>"Also, looking at the benefit I was getting from my previous jobs, it was not appropriate enough. I was mostly demoralised because my company could not fight for our welfare.</i></p> <p><i>"I saw the opportunities and wanted to take advantage of those opportunities"</i></p> <p><i>"My decision to become an entrepreneurial was as result of a bad experience"</i></p> <p><i>Apart from the academic curriculum, which touched on briefly. But I have not had any in-depth training over the years. However, I studied some subject areas in the school that highlighted vital areas related to business but were not detailed</i></p> <p><i>"I had a few short-term trainings as to when to spot opportunities"</i></p>	<p>Unemployment rate, fear, Uncertainty</p> <p>Welfare</p> <p>Opportunity</p> <p>Bad experience</p> <p>no in-depth practical training</p> <p>vital areas related to business but were not detailed</p> <p>Identify Opportunity</p>	
<p>Theme 2-Entrepreneurial Education and training</p> <p>4. Where is it appropriate, in your mind and experience, to undertake</p>	<p><i>School trigger most individuals to have positive intentions towards establishing their own business at a younger age.</i></p>	<p>Formal Education (early</p>	<p>EE and ET</p> <p>- Practical and Experiential Learning</p>

<p>entrepreneurial training?</p> <p>5. Do you think universities have the necessary platforms to inform people's skills to become entrepreneurs? If Yes can you explain?</p> <p>6. What do you think about apprenticeship training before embarking on self-employment?</p> <p>7. Do you consider, without entrepreneurial training your business can survive? Please give reasons for your answer.</p> <p>8. In what circumstance would you consider further entrepreneurship training?</p>	<p><i>"I personal think with other courses, entrepreneurship courses and training are not that really enforced on people that much unless you wanting to do it. This is something most educational intuitions can look into it and improve"</i></p> <p><i>"I feel they have the capacity to, but much investment has not been channelled to that aspect."</i></p> <p><i>"I feel universities should put up modules that adapt to current circumstances"</i></p> <p><i>"Even though most universities provide some sort of grants for individuals with entrepreneurial ideas which are mostly theoretical based. It is very difficult to see some sort of practical entrepreneurial training from the universities ".</i></p> <p><i>But the issue has got to do with a student graduating and not using their skills</i></p> <p><i>It becomes very hard to introduce this kind of setting up business after the tertiary level. Because they were not introduced at their early stages of their life. They are not present in the curriculum and the education systems.</i></p> <p><i>"Engagement in apprenticeship it gives the real exposure to the business of interest. But it won't give them an overall overview as to how to manage their business"</i></p> <p><i>"Universities should train students to identify business opportunities"</i></p>	<p>stage)</p> <p>Compulsory modules</p> <p>Capacity</p> <p>Advance modules</p> <p>No practical trainings in universities</p> <p>Lack of skills, Business opportunities</p> <p>Encourage entrepreneurial education in the curriculum</p> <p>Encourage apprenticeship</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk Management and Problem-solving - Technology and Innovation - Cultural and Contextual Relevance - Personal Development and Mindset - Networking and Collaboration -Vocational training -Apprenticeship
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<p>9. Technical and vocational training are crucially important for new business – to what extent do you agree with this statement?</p>	<p><i>“Individuals without entrepreneurial training or any basics understanding of managing a business their rate of survival is very low. It will take the inner quality of an individual to succeed”</i></p> <p><i>“They should invest and train students at the early stages. They should empower students to change their mindset to accept entrepreneurship.”</i></p> <p><i>“They should bring in seasonal entrepreneurs to come and impact the lives of these students. By the time they complete school, these students will have decided the kind of path they want to take.”</i></p> <p><i>“I will consider specific training depending on how it will help me improve my business”.</i></p> <p><i>“Most of my employees are from vocational schools. They are specialist in local craftsmanship.”</i></p> <p><i>“They also have the capacity to empower entrepreneurs”</i></p>	<p>Core skills</p> <p>Early entrepreneurship training</p> <p>Early investment</p> <p>Empowerment</p> <p>Specific benefit</p> <p>Promote craftsmanship</p> <p>Capacity development</p>	
<p>Do you have regrets about being an entrepreneur?</p>	<p><i>“The major challenge is staying relevant to meet customer demand. Also, when I was trying funding and got new equipment. When I was not making a profit at the initial stages, I was scared my business might collapse. I invest so much into business just to stay up to date, from design thinking to production unit”.</i></p> <p><i>“You manage your own business, you intend to work hard and put in extra hours to ensure things move smoothly. You turn to control your business at your own pace, you</i></p>	<p>Customer demand, Funding, Profit margin, Investment</p> <p>Control, Privacy and</p>	<p>-Ethical and Sustainable Business Practices</p> <p>- Market Research and Customer Analysis</p> <p>- Financial Planning and Management</p>

	<i>know when to take breaks. You also gain your privacy and freedoms as well.”</i>	freedom	Business Control and Governance - Entrepreneurial Freedom and Autonomy
<p>No Entrepreneurial training</p> <p>10. Reflecting on your own experience, how did you manage your business without any entrepreneurial training?</p> <p>11. Do you without any entrepreneurial training your business can succeed? Please explain further....</p> <p>12. In what circumstance will you consider entrepreneurial training....</p> <p>13. At what point will you recommend entrepreneurial training to others? And why...?</p>	<p><i>“I started my business without any form entrepreneurial training. The only experience I had was work experience and I kind of studied along the way”</i></p> <p><i>“I will always recommend entrepreneurial training to people before they start their business.”</i></p> <p>“Without any business studies or entrepreneurial training my business can survive. My grandparent run their business without any training and they were successful”</p> <p><i>“I feel that it is very important for entrepreneurial training to be embedded into the day-to-day educational system and the curriculum.”</i></p>	<p>Experience</p> <p>Entrepreneurial training before business starts.</p> <p>Business can survive without training</p> <p>Encourage entrepreneurship training and Education</p>	<p>-Value of Experience</p> <p>-Pre-Business Training</p> <p>- Business Survival and Training</p> <p>- Mentoring and Networking Opportunities</p> <p>- promotion of entrepreneurship training</p>
Small business support and Government			-Policy Education and Awareness

<p>15. In your experience, what major role has local and national government played in supporting SMEs?</p>	<p>“There are so many government policies available to support small businesses, but such policies' communication to SMEs is not effective. Most of us don't know whether these policies exist.”</p>	<p>Poor education of policies, ineffective policies</p>	<p>- Policy Effectiveness and Efficiency</p>
<p>16. Can you remember any time a government policy has demoralised you or demotivated you with regard to a particular business activity or entrepreneurial decision of yours?</p>	<p>“Government support has been visible especially when this pandemic started”</p> <p><i>“Their policy has taken a toll on our business. Taxes and constant increase of goods and services affect my start up business, I did not have enough money to invest and loans accumulated high interest rates.”</i></p>	<p>Government support</p> <p>High taxes, inflation, high interest on loans</p>	<p>- Government Support Programs</p> <p>- Taxation and Financial Burden</p> <p>- Family Engagement and Support</p>
<p>17. Do friends and family play a key role in your business? If yes can you explain to what extent?</p>	<p><i>My family also helped me. They invested into me. My friends were my customers. They motivated me and encouraged me.</i></p> <p><i>“My parent don't run businesses themselves. So when I try to talk about entrepreneurship, they are not really interested.”</i></p>	<p>Support, investors, Motivation</p> <p>no interest/from family members</p>	<p>- Investor Support and Engagement</p> <p>- Motivational Initiatives</p>
<p>18. Without support from family and friends, can your business continue? Why?</p>	<p><i>“Family are friends are very important very in my business. They mostly provide you with the necessary support in terms of finance and emotional support”</i></p> <p><i>“when i was starting by business capital was an issue and all did was support me financially in the form of loan. Most of this help are from my friends”</i></p>	<p>Family and friends provide, finance and emotional support</p> <p>Friends, loans (financial)</p>	

